

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH OF THE SCO COUNTRIES: SYNERGY AND INTEGRATION

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

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这些会议文结合了会议的材料 – 研究论文和科学工作者的论文报告。它考察了职业化人格的技术和社会学问题。一些文章涉及人格职业化研究问题的理论和方法论方法和原则。

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CONTENTS

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

俄罗斯发展火灾危险等级和植被火灾行为预测系统

Development fire danger rating and vegetation fire behavior prediction system in Russia

Volokitina Aleksandra Vitalievna, Sofronova Tatiana Markovna,

Korets Mikhail Anatolievich 9

蛋糕添加剂的质量分数和类型对干饼干功能特性的影响

The influence of the mass fraction and type of cake additives on the functional properties of dry biscuits

Lesovskaya Marina Igorevna 17

对伏尔加河下游地区非洲小米品种生育期的研究

Study of the vegetation period of African millet varieties in the Lower Volga region

Kireeva Olga Valerievna, Stepanchenko Denis Alexandrovich 25

土壤改良剂和螯合肥对萨拉托夫地区高粱叶片吸收能力的影响

The influence of soil improvers and chelated fertilizer on the assimilation capacity of sorghum leaves when grown in the Saratov region

Stepanchenko Denis Alexandrovich, Kireeva Olga Valerievna 32

栗树土壤上棉花种植的土地改良技术

Land reclamation techniques in cotton cultivation on chestnut soils

Ovchinnikov Maxim Alekseevich, Ovchinnikov Alexey Semyonovich,

Podkovyrov Igor Yurevich 39

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

基于混合流水线“机器学习-优化”的组合优化问题求解的理论论证

Theoretical justification of combinatorial optimization problems solving based on hybrid pipelines “machine learning–optimization”

Tyryshkin Sergey Yurievich 44

恶劣天气条件下船舶航行的风险评估

Risk assessment for navigating ships in difficult weather conditions

Astreina Lyudmila Borisovna, Shtyrkhunova Natalya Aleksandrovna,

Pershina Larisa Aleksandrovna 49

主干天然气管道的耐久性取决于其制造技术 Durability of main gas pipelines, depending on their manufacturing technology <i>Volgina Natalya Ivanovna, Khlamkova Svetlana Sergeevna, Shulgina Aleksandr Vasilyevich</i>	55
现代化联合收割机接收大豆种子经济效益指标的数学计算 Mathematical calculation of economic indicators of the effectiveness of receiving soybean seeds in a modernized combine <i>Prisyazhnaya Irina Mikhaelovna, Prisyazhnaya Serafima Pavlovna</i>	62
具有改进特性的跟踪型模数转换器 (ADC) Analog-to-digital converter (ADC) of tracking type with improved characteristics <i>Ischemguzhin Alexander Izmailovich, Monov Ivan Evgenievich, Kotov Viktor Vladimirovich</i>	71
评估受害者身份特征造成的信息风险：识别和预防方法 Assessment of information risks caused by the features of victim identity: methods of identification and prevention <i>Marinov Alexander Andreevich, Larionova Larisa Alexandrovna</i>	79
生物识别安全：便利性与隐私性 Biometric Security: Convenience vs Privacy <i>Guseinova Rukizhat Bashirovna, Mutayeva Sayeda Ibraghimovna</i>	88
创新型传动工业机器人机械臂的概念 Concept of an innovative transmission industrial robot manipulator <i>Khokhlov Denis Valerievich, Vanin Alexander Alexandrovich, Melnik Anna Vitalievna, Gusakov Vladimir Alexandrovich</i>	92
计算机模拟矿物尺寸破碎过程中可控裂纹形成的新方法 Computer Modeling of a New Method for Controlled Crack Formation during Dimensional Comminution of Minerals <i>Puzankov Maxim Sergeevich, Sergeev Yuriy Sergeevich, Sergeev Sergey Vasilievich</i>	99
研究基于碳纤维和聚合物基体的混合复合材料的结构和性能 Investigation of the structure and properties of hybrid composite materials based on carbon fiber and polymer matrix <i>Zhalybina Anastasia Yurevna, Eremeeva Kristina Alexandrovna</i>	106

苏联和俄罗斯异丁烷与烯烃烷基化工艺形成和发展的主要阶段（综述） Main stages of the formation and development of the process of alkylation of isobutane with olefins in the USSR and in RUSSIA (review) <i>Evseev Sergey Sergeevich, Akhmadova Khava Khamidovna,</i> <i>Magomadova Madina Khusenovna</i>	112
关于将客户关系管理系统作为有效支持投资和建设项目技术支持的工具 On the use of CRM systems as a tool for effective technical support of investment and construction projects <i>Starikov Vladislav Nikolaevich</i>	120
全同态加密方案的理论基础、实际应用及稳定性分析 Analysis of theoretical basis, practical implementations and Stability of full homomorphous encryption schemes <i>Retivykh Vladimir Viktorovich, Retivykh Alexey Viktorovich</i>	126

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

教育是知识的基础 Education as the basis of knowledge <i>Kazantsev Sergey Vladimirovich</i>	134
在经济数字化背景下，神经网络在利益相关者管理中的应用 The use of neural networks in stakeholder management in the context of digitalization of the economy <i>Tretyakov Oleg Vladimirovich</i>	142
全球经济动荡背景下的预算政策：比较分析 Budgetary policy in the context of global economic turbulence: a comparative analysis <i>Omelyanovich Lidiya Aleksandrovna, Manzhula Tatyana Yuryevna</i>	150
实施KPI以提高葡萄酒行业组织的劳动生产率和竞争力 Implementation of KPI to increase labor productivity and competitiveness of the winemaking industry organization <i>Gagarinskaya Galina Pavlovna, Dykina Svetlana Zakharovna,</i> <i>Gagarinskiy Alexander Vladimirovich, Dykin Pavel Valentinovich</i>	160
伊朗冲突：未来地缘经济中的潜在贸易决策 Iran conflict: potential trade decisions in the geoeconomics of the future <i>Kharlanov Alexey Sergeevitch</i>	167

2020–2024年伊尔库茨克州乌斯季奥尔达布里亚特自治区农场动物粗饲料和多汁饲料供应形成特点

Features of the formation of the supply of roughage and succulent feed for farm animals in the Ust-Orda Buryat Okrug of the Irkutsk region for 2020-2024
Kalinina Lyudmila Alekseevna, Kalinin Nikolay Vladimirovich, Barkova Natalia Viktorovna176

评估一个地区人力资源潜力的方法论

Methodological approaches to assessing the human potential of a region
Beskrovnaya Oksana Vladimirovna, Chapkina Nadezhda Anatolyevna183

水运技术管理中小企业业务流程分析与优化问题

Problems of analysis and optimization of business processes in small and medium-sized enterprises of technical management in water transport
Krasiuk Alla Borisovna, Cherenkov Vadim Sergeevich190

银行机构与餐饮企业之间的合作：从收购到整合

Partnership between banking institutions and catering enterprises: from acquiring to integration
Kushnir Iryna Mykolajvna, Byshenko Alexander Vitalievich199

财务困境和破产概率的实证分析：以 Ambev S. A. 为例

An Empirical Analysis of Financial Distress and Bankruptcy Probability: The Case of Ambev S. A.
Gyulasaryan Mikayel Rafayel, Matevosyan Ashot Varazdat, Matevosyan Mane Henrik206

中小企业主财务决策中的行为偏差：以哈萨克斯坦为例

Behavioural biases in financial decision-making of sme owners: case study of Kazakhstan
Balgabayev Daulet, Abraliyev Onalbek214

现代条件下的公司风险管理

Risk management of the company in modern conditions
Gerzelieva Zhanneta Ilyasovna221

北方地区劳动关系监管和社会保障的经济和法律问题

Economic and legal aspects of regulating labor relations and social protection of the population in the North
Chapkina Nadezhda Anatolyevna, Kochetova Veronika Sergeevna227

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俄罗斯发展火灾危险等级和植被火灾行为预测系统
**DEVELOPMENT FIRE DANGER RATING AND VEGETATION FIRE
BEHAVIOR PREDICTION SYSTEM IN RUSSIA**

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摘要：本文基于俄罗斯不同地区长期开展的基础火学研究，探讨了在俄罗斯建立火灾危险等级评估和植被火灾行为预测系统的可行性。文中构建并展示了植被火灾管理流程图，包括航空航天监测系统、气象数据信息数据库以及火灾危险等级评估和火灾行为预测系统。此外，本文还开发并回顾性地测试了一个用于植被火灾行为预测的计算机程序。

关键词：植被燃料分类，制图，火灾危险等级评估，火灾行为预测。

Abstract. *The article considers the feasibility of developing a system for fire danger rating and vegetation fire behavior prediction in Russia based on long-term fundamental pyrological research in different regions of the country. A schematic diagram of vegetation fire management has been developed and presented in the paper; including an aerospace monitoring system, an information database of meteorological data, and a system for fire danger rating and fire behavior prediction. A computer program for vegetation fire behavior prediction has been developed and tested retrospectively.*

Keywords: *vegetation fuel classification, mapping, fire danger rating, fire behavior prediction.*

Introduction

Vegetation fires (forest, steppe, swamp, etc.) remain a problem not only for Russia, but also for many other countries. The situation is becoming more complicated due to the observed climate warming. Periods of severe droughts are becoming more frequent, the number of fires is growing, some of them reach large sizes, create emergencies and cause huge damage. It is very difficult to suppress large vegetation fires, often they stay active till heavy rainfalls. Prevention of large fires can be a solution to this problem. Its most important components are: 1) timely detection of emerging fires; 2) their timely suppression, and 3) efficient hot spotting. In addition to weather conditions, the number of fires that occur and their development is affected by: the nature of vegetation, its phenological state, the number of sources of ignition, pyrological partitioning of the territory, and other factors that are currently practically not taken into account when assessing fire danger. The most important and most dynamic factor is the weather factor. To date, there are no reliable methods for long-term forecasting of dry periods. It should be noted that the conditions for the development of large vegetation fires do not appear immediately but develop gradually in each area. A reliable daily assessment of these conditions and daily fire danger rating for 7-10 days in accordance with the weather forecast will help gradually, as the threat increases, carry out preventive measures, prepare manpower and resources, and transfer additional suppression forces from other districts and relevant departments to the area. Therefore, *an improved fire danger rating is very important*, and it should take into account not only weather, but also other factors (vegetation, its phenological state, the number of ignition sources, pyrological partitioning, etc.).

During severe droughts, the number of fires that occur increases considerably, as well as the difficulty of suppressing and hot-spotting each fire. Therefore, there is usually a lack of suppression forces. In such conditions, it is necessary to choose and suppress first of all those emerging fires that can quickly become large and catastrophic. This choice can be facilitated *by predicting the behavior* (i.e., fire spread, intensity, development, and effects) of emerging fires, as well as predicting the results of their suppression with different force sizes.

Background

The practical use of fire danger rating and fire behavior prediction systems developed in the USA and Canada confirms the impossibility of solving the problem of vegetation fires only by increasing technical power. Our study of these systems during internships has convinced us that it is impossible to directly borrow and

apply them in Russia's natural conditions. The main reason is the difference in methodological approaches to pyrological research in natural conditions and, as a result, the difference in pyrological classification of vegetation fuels, including forest ones. Thus, attempts to implement the Canadian system in Russia, which began in the 1990s, did not lead to the desired results, and only slowed down the development of the Russian system. It was also found that the level of Russian fundamental pyrological developments is not at all inferior to, but even exceeds international ones in some areas. The gap is observed only in technical terms, since the Russian academic science does not allocate funds for applied developments, their testing and implementation.

The center of fundamental Fire Science in Russia has long been considered to be the Sukachev Institute of Forest SB RAS, a separate division of the Federal Research Center Krasnoyarsk Science Center of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences. To date, the Institute has all the prerequisites for the phased development of the Russian system for fire danger rating and vegetation fire behavior prediction:

1) fundamental and applied developments (classification of vegetation fuels (VF) and methods of their automatized mapping [1,2]; improved methodology for daily fire danger rating [3]; a simple and practical fire spread model [4], for which methods and technologies for creating an information database of VF maps have been developed; a program for predicting vegetation fire spread, fire intensity and effects [5]; the results of research are reflected in monographs and recommendations.

2) a highly qualified team of fire scientists, including GIS specialists;

3) within the framework of the State Contract (2008-2010) between the Sukachev Institute of Forest SB RAS and the Forest Industry Agency for the Krasnoyarsk Territory, software programs were developed and currently registered for making maps of vegetation fuels (VF maps) using forest inventory information and on their basis predicting the behavior and effects of vegetation fires; the programs were tested in plain and mountain terrain. The developments were awarded a Diploma at the 8th International Specialized Exhibition "Fire Safety of the 21st Century" in 2009 in Moscow, Russia.

The creation of the Russian system for fire danger rating and fire behavior prediction should be based on the above-mentioned developments of the Sukachev Institute of Forest, as well as on the use of materials from the Federal Forestry Agency Information System of Remote Sensing Monitoring, Aerial Forest Protection data, and forest inventory information available for most of Russia. The Institute for Space Research [6] has been long and successfully developing a system for monitoring vegetation fires that is necessary for predicting their behavior.

Results and Discussion

In Russian forest fire protection practice, there are 3 types of forest fire danger rating (FDR): fire weather danger rating, fire hazard assessment, and local fire danger scales that take into account a range of factors.

All 3 types of FDR require improvement. The Sukachev Institute of Forest has ready-to-implement developments for all 3 types of FDR. Thus, in order to improve the daily FDR according to weather conditions, a new PVG index of the Sukachev Institute of Forest, proposed by M. A. Sofronov [3], was improved and prepared for implementation; in fact, it is a further improvement of the V. G. Nestorov's indices [7] and PV-1 index of Leningrad Research Institute of Forestry [8], which are still used in forest management [9]. The PVG index developed at the Sukachev Institute of Forest has a number of advantages: it takes into account not only humidity, but also the hygroscopicity of vegetation fuels (first of all, the primary fire carriers), functions at subzero temperatures that is very important for the regions of Transbaikalia and the Far East, and also has more differentiated account of rain precipitation compared to the PV-1 index. A table of rain precipitation coefficients has been created for practical use.

Figure 1 shows a principle scheme for vegetation fire management, which includes a system for fire danger rating (FDR) and fire behavior prediction (FBP), divided into 2 subsystems of FDR and FBP. The FBP subsystem is GIS-based with a number of software programs based on VF maps with fire-related characteristics of vegetation areas. Methods for making multi-scale VF maps are developed at the Sukachev Institute of Forest depending on the information available for a particular area (airborne images, vegetation maps, forest inventory data, etc.) [1].

To predict the behavior of vegetation fires, large-scale VF maps (1:10,000-1:50,000) are required. Creation of such maps became possible after many years of fundamental fire science research, with a detailed VF classification being developed. N. P. Kurbatsky's classification of 7 VF groups was further developed. After analyzing our own and published data, we managed to divide all VF groups into types. Moreover, the most detailed classification was developed for the first VF group — the primary fire carriers. This group of forest floor cover includes: mosses, lichens, and small vegetation remnants. This group is shown in color on the map, and other information is shown in the pyrological description attached to the map. Since it is time-consuming and expensive to create VF maps independently, we turned to the GIS-based forest inventory information available for most of the Russian forest area.

A software program was developed to convert the forest inventory information into a pyrological description. Based on the data from the previous forest inventory for the most fire-prone Chunsy Forest District in the Krasnoyarsk Angara Region, VF maps were made for the spring (fall) and summer periods. The VF

maps served as a basis for improving fire hazard assessment. Now this assessment is performed roughly at the level of the 1940s-1970s using forest fire maps of 1:100,000 scale, made during forest inventory on the basis of the forest type FDR scale by Prof. I. S. Melekhov [10]. Although the author of this assessment pointed out the possibility for its improvement based on the study of fire-related (pyrological) characteristics of vegetation fuels and, above all, the primary fire carriers. Russian studies of the VF pyrological characteristics began under the leadership of I. S. Melekhov in different regions of the Russian Federation. Pyrological characteristics of the primary fire carriers were obtained and, first of all, the dynamics of fuel moistening and drying was studied. The latter made it possible to perform a more accurate assessment of fire hazard. Based on the VF maps, it is now possible to create maps of the current fire hazard (CFH). A retrospective performance test of these maps proved their high accuracy. For instance, out of 125 fires in the Chunksy Forest District of the Krasnoyarsk Angara Region, 117 occurred in the inventory plots marked as ready to burn and 8 occurred in the plots classified as being in a transitional state on the CFH map. There were no registered fires in the plots classified as ‘not ready to burn’ on the CFH map for the given class of dryness based on weather conditions.

One more software program was developed and registered to predict the behavior of vegetation fires based on VF maps [5]. According to the program, under the specified conditions, the fire spread is calculated along tactical parts of the fire — front, rear, and flank, as well as their fire intensity and the required number of suppression forces to suppress the fire. The program also predicts the possibility for a surface fire to develop into a crown or ground fire, as well as the immediate fire effects expressed by the tree mortality percentage depending on fire intensity, tree species and average diameter. A retrospective performance test of the software program proved its reliability (Figure 2 and Table).

Figure 2. Prediction of the forest fire spread in the Nature Reserve Stolby.

Figure 1. Principle scheme for vegetation fire management

Table. Characteristics of fire No. 5 calculated using the developed software

Fire Characteristics	Time Passed after the Start of Prediction, h		
	1	2	3
Fire area, ha	2.7	5.2	8.5
Fire perimeter, m	620	870	1120
Perimeter spread rate, m/h	226	260	240
Area spread rate, ha/h	2	2.9	3.6
Fire front average spread rate, m/h	33	35	34
Fire edge average intensity, kW/m	112	109	107
Fire intensity assessment	medium	medium	medium
Assessment of manpower and means for fire suppression			
Optimum suppression rate, m/h	680	780	720
Suppression duration, h/area of burnt area after suppression, ha			
3 firefighters	7 / 16	–	–
5 firefighters	3 / 8	5 / 20	7 / 40
7 firefighters	1.5 / 4.5	2.5 / 11	3.5 / 20
10 firefighters	1 / 3.5	1.5 / 9.9	2.5 / 17
15 firefighters	0.5 / 3	1 / 7	1.5 / 15
20 firefighters	–	–	1 / 14

Conclusion

To improve forest fire protection in Russia, it is necessary to develop a Russian FDR and FBP system. All the prerequisites for its creation are available: in different regions of Russia, long-term fundamental pyrological studies have been carried out and helped to develop a detailed classification of vegetation fuels and methods of their mapping. There are methodological recommendations for improving the assessment of all types of fire danger in the forest. Software programs have been developed and registered for timely mapping of vegetation fuels and for predicting the behavior of vegetation fires. An algorithm of a training program for fire control and suppression managers has been developed.

An obstacle to the development and implementation of the proposed system is the departmental and financial disintegration of industry and academic institutes of the forest field, limited funding for forestry, and a lack of knowledge workforce.

Acknowledgments

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蛋糕添加剂的质量分数和类型对干饼干功能特性的影响
**THE INFLUENCE OF THE MASS FRACTION AND TYPE
OF CAKE ADDITIVES ON THE FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES
OF DRY BISCUITS**

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摘要：本研究采用方差分析法（ANOVA）评估了油粕种类及其质量分数对黑麦亚麻籽干饼干品质特性的影响。结果表明，油粕种类是影响品质的主要因素，具有统计学意义。质量分数是次要因素，需要进一步研究其在工艺过程中的应用条件。基于抗氧化能力、还原性化合物含量、抗过氧化能力和膨胀能力等指标，在所考虑的添加剂中，质量分数为50%的芝麻油粕是黑麦亚麻籽干饼干的最佳添加剂。

关键词：干饼干，油粕，膨胀能力，抗氧化能力，还原性化合物，过氧化能力，双因素分析，方差分析。

Abstract. *Using the ANOVA method, the influence of the type of oilseed cake and its mass fraction on the quality characteristics of rye-flax dry biscuits was assessed. It was established that the type of oilseed cake used holds priority and statistical significance. The mass fraction is a secondary factor that requires further clarification of the conditions for the additive's use in the technological process. Based on antioxidant capacity, content of reducing compounds, resistance to peroxide oxidation, and swelling capacity, the most effective additive for rye-flax dry biscuits among those considered is sesame oilseed cake at a mass fraction of 50%.*

Keywords: *dry biscuits, oilseed cake, swelling capacity, antioxidant capacity, reducing compounds, peroxide oxidation, two-factor analysis, ANOVA.*

Dry biscuits are a type of unleavened bread that has been used for more than a century in long maritime and terrestrial expeditions, known historically as 'sled bread' or 'ship's hardtack' [1]. With minor variations in the recipe, this is a nutritious product with a high fiber content, produced from rye flour as well as whole grains. Dry biscuits remain a sought-after product to this day [2]. They are valued for their practicality, neutral flavor, and crisp texture. Dry biscuits do not require

special storage conditions. They are convenient to carry and consume as a snack, pairing well with sweet, salty, meat, or fish products. Along with crackers, dry biscuits belong to the category of dry bakery products. The key distinction of dry biscuits from crackers is their low fat and sugar content, i. e., their dietary properties.

The main factors explaining why dry biscuits remain among the top consumer preferences are presented in Figure 1, which shows that an important determinant of consumer choice is the variability of the food system, enabling the incorporation in dry biscuit formulations not only of grain processing products (flour) but also of whole grain resources and by-products of food production.

Figure 1 — Determinants of consumer choice of galettes

An economical and environmentally friendly option is the use of rye press cake obtained after emulsion separation during the grinding of rye malt. In [3], it is shown that during the production of a new type of multigrain bread, rye grain is sprouted, ground in a blender, then the emulsion ('rye cream') is separated, and the semi-solid press cake is utilized as a secondary raw material for producing an additional product — galettes [4]. The food matrix inherently possesses adaptogenic potential that does not require enhancement through technological additives and is amenable to the addition of supplementary natural complexes, such as ground flax seeds. It is a superfood rich in polyunsaturated omega-3 fatty acids (alpha-linolenic acid), soluble and insoluble fiber, as well as lignans (phytoestrogens exhibiting regulatory and antioxidant functions). In combination with rye oilseed cake, ground flaxseed forms a concentrate of protein, microelements (magnesium, manganese, potassium), and vitamins (primarily B vitamins). This product is capable of exerting a beneficial effect on the condition of the organism, and therefore possesses functional properties.

The flavor diversity of dry biscuits composed of rye oilseed cake and ground flaxseed can be enhanced through the use of oilseed cake additives. The bioenergetics of metabolism is based on electron-dependent mechanisms, and adaptation to environmental conditions is always associated with the function of

reducing compounds (reductants) and antioxidants. All antioxidants are capable of donating electrons and thus function as reducing compounds; however, not all reducing compounds exhibit antioxidant properties. Consequently, it is essential to evaluate and regulate the levels of both components within the food system to effectively control product quality. Products of lipid peroxidation serve as markers of oxidative stress; therefore, determining the rate of malondialdehyde (MDA) accumulation constitutes an important method for quality assessment. Dietary fibers exhibit antioxidant functions by acting as scavengers of free radicals and carriers of phenolic compounds that neutralize these harmful particles. Due to the high hygroscopicity of dietary fibers, swelling capacity is used as an indirect indicator of their content in products. Therefore, all these indicators are interrelated and collectively define the adaptogenic properties of dry biscuits as an important quality criterion. The evaluation of each parameter is conducted using established methods, which, however, do not permit establishing the significance of two factors affecting the quality indicators — the type of oilseed cake (factor 1) and its mass fraction (factor 2). To address this relevant issue, an adequate analytical tool is not instrumental analysis but statistical analysis, such as two-factor ANOVA (analysis of variance) [5].

The aim of the present study was to reveal the significance of the type and mass fraction of oilseed cake additives for the quality indicators. The study's objectives included determining indicators of antioxidant activity, the content of reducing compounds, MDA accumulation, and swelling of rye-flax dry biscuits supplemented with various oilseed cake additives; the application of the ANOVA method to evaluate the significance of each factor on quality parameters.

Materials and Methods. The study material consisted of dry biscuits prepared from dispersed rye malt germinated according to the method described [6], and ground flax seeds in a 6:4 ratio (Fig. 2, a). The experimental baking was carried out at the Food Production Institute of Krasnoyarsk State Agrarian University. The dry biscuits were baked under conditions of 180 °C for 20 minutes. Additives for the dry biscuit formulation consisted of four types of dry ground oilseed cake, obtained from the OZON online marketplace (sesame, milk thistle, hemp, pumpkin) (Fig. 2, b).

Figure 2 — Types of oilseed cake incorporated in the dry biscuits

The swelling capacity of the dry biscuits was determined according to the current regulation **GOST 10114-80 “Flour confectionery products.” Method of determining wettability (standard swelling values** in the range of 185...192%). The content of reducing compounds was determined by permanganate oxidation using the back titration method according to GOST R 55684-2013. Antioxidant activity of the samples was determined by the chemiluminescence method using the automated complex “Biochemiluminometer 3606” (SCTB “Nauka”, Krasnoyarsk). The registered parameter was the total photon count S over the observation period (120 s), while the accounting parameter was the ORAC value (*Oxygen Radical Absorbance Capacity*, a measure of the capacity to absorb oxygen radicals), representing the unit of antioxidant potential for various food products and additives [7].

The MDA level ($\mu\text{mol/L}$) was determined using the TBARS test (Thiobarbituric Acid Reactive Substances), based on the reaction of MDA with thiobarbituric acid (TBA) upon heating in an acidic environment. Calculations utilized the increase in MDA measured by the difference between freshly baked biscuits and those stored for one month under standard conditions. Statistical analysis was performed using two-factor ANOVA (Two-Way ANOVA). Data processing was carried out with the Microsoft Excel application. *Data verification was carried out using statistical analysis with Fisher’s criterion.*

Results and Discussion. Figure 3 presents the results of the instrumental assessment of the dependence of rye-flax dry biscuit quality on four parameters: swelling capacity (a), antioxidant capacity (b), reducing compounds (c), and MDA accumulation (d).

Figure 3 — Quality indicators of biscuits with oilseed cake additives at different mass fractions

The results of the analysis of the effects of two factors (f1 — type of oilseed cake, f2 — mass fraction) are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 — Contribution of data variability from each factor to the total variance of the resultant function:

Figure 4a shows that for the swelling index, the mass fraction is a significant factor, whereas the type of oilseed cake in the food system is not. The contribution of factor 2 to the total variance in the sample was 71.3%, with a calculated Fisher's criterion value of 10.56 compared to the threshold value of 6.99 (degrees of freedom $v_1=3$, $v_2=9$). The results are statistically significant at $p<0.01$, with a confidence level of 99%.

As shown in Figure 4b, unlike swelling capacity, the type of oilseed cake is a more significant factor for antioxidant capacity than its mass fraction in the food system. The contribution of factor 1 to the total variance of the sample was 40.05%, with a calculated Fisher criterion of 4.12, exceeding the threshold value of 3.86. It is also necessary to take into account the magnitude of the residual variance ($Q_0 = 55.47$), which determines the influence of factors not considered in this analysis. Therefore, the use of these results can only be of a tentative nature and does not require confirmation of statistical significance.

Figure 4c shows that, regarding the content of reducing compounds, as in the previous case, the type of oilseed cake ($Q_1 \gg Q_2$) is a significant factor, rather than its mass fraction. The result was anticipated, since antioxidants are reducing compounds. The contribution of factor 1 to the total variance in the sample was 59.69%; the calculated Fisher criterion value of 8.51 exceeds the threshold of 6.99 (degrees of freedom $v_1=3$, $v_2=9$), indicating that the results are statistically significant at $p<0.01$ ($P=99\%$). A fifth (21.04%) of the total variability in the data sample is attributed to residual dispersion.

Figure 4, d demonstrates that the type of oilseed cake has a more significant impact on MDA accumulation during biscuit storage than its mass fraction. The contribution of factor 1 to the total variance in the sample was 53.19%, and the calculated Fisher criterion value of 8.51 exceeds the critical threshold of 6.29 (for degrees of freedom $v_1=3$, $v_2=9$); therefore, the results are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ (95% confidence level). The residual dispersion accounts for one quarter (25.35%) of the total variability in the sample data.

Upon confirming the significance of the factors, instrumental analysis data could be used to determine specific technological conditions for the application of oilseed cake additives in the formulation of dry biscuits. For three of the four parameters, the type of oilseed cake was identified as a statistically significant factor. The subsequent stage involved determining the optimal mass fraction range for each type of oilseed cake additive. Figure 5 presents parameter values averaged across the full mass fraction range for each type of oilseed cake.

Figure 5 — Dependence of mean sample indicators on the mass fraction of oilseed cake additives

From Fig. 5, a and b, it is evident that the antioxidant capacity and content of reducing compounds were higher in dry biscuits containing sesame and hemp oilseed cake additives. These data were predictably consistent with the MDA measurement results (Fig. 5, c), where MDA accumulation occurred more slowly in those samples. MDA accumulation in dry biscuits with pumpkin and milk thistle oilseed cakes occurred at a rate 1.3 to 2 times higher than in the other two types of biscuits. This is possibly attributable to the lower content of unsaturated fatty acids and vitamin E compared to sesame and hemp oilseed cakes. A comparison of the swelling capacity of dry biscuits with these additives demonstrated (Fig. 5, d) that

to enhance the quality of dry biscuits, it is preferable to use sesame oilseed cake rather than hemp oilseed cake (Fig. 6).

Figure 6 — Dose dependence of the swelling capacity of dry biscuits on the sesame oilseed cake additive

The figure shows that dry biscuits containing a 50% mass fraction of sesame oilseed cake exhibited the lowest swelling capacity, which will contribute to prolonging the shelf life of the dry biscuits as the target product.

Conclusions

1. Using the ANOVA method, it was determined that the type of oilseed cake used holds priority and a statistically significant effect on the quality indicators of dry biscuits. The mass fraction is a secondary factor that requires specification to optimize the conditions for additive application in the technological process.

2. Regarding antioxidant capacity, reducing substances content, and resistance to peroxide oxidation, the best additive among those considered for rye-flax biscuits is sesame oilseed cake at a 50% mass fraction.

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对伏尔加河下游地区非洲小米品种生育期的研究
**STUDY OF THE VEGETATIVE PERIOD OF AFRICAN MILLET
VARIETIES IN THE LOWER VOLGA REGION**

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摘要：本文分析了全俄植物产业研究所（以N. I. Vavilov命名）收藏的非洲小米品种的营养生长期研究成果。

关键词：育种，营养生长期，非洲小米，变异性

Abstract. *The article provides an analysis of research on the vegetative period of African millet varieties from the collection of the All-Russian Institute of Plant Industry named after N. I. Vavilov.*

Keywords: *breeding, vegetative period, African millet, variability*

The vegetative period is the duration from seed germination to the onset of the plant's biological maturity. African millet (*Pennisétum gláucum*) is an important cereal crop in arid regions; the length of the vegetative period directly influences yield, adaptability, and resistance to stress conditions. The vegetative period is a key indicator for evaluating the adaptive potential of African millet cultivars, their yield, and their suitability for various agroclimatic conditions.

The duration of the vegetative period of African millet varieties mainly depends on growing conditions and typically ranges from 70 to 120 days. Varieties with a short vegetative period are important for regions where the vegetative period is limited by seasonal factors or a high risk of drought, as they enable harvesting before the onset of unfavorable conditions. Varieties with a long vegetative period generally exhibit greater accumulation of aboveground biomass and seed yield.

Identification and utilization of information regarding the duration of the vegetative period enable breeders to:

1. to accurately adapt varieties to specific agroclimatic conditions taking into account the duration of the growing season;

2. to develop varieties with the required maturation periods to ensure high yield;

3. to enhance stress resistance by modeling optimal timing of plant development;

4. Improving productivity through the combination of an appropriate rate and an efficient nutrient accumulation period.

In breeding, phenological observations, temperature regime monitoring, and genetic analysis are employed to identify genes controlling developmental timing. These methods enable the development of hybrids with a predetermined duration of the vegetative period.

Controlling the timing of the vegetative period of African millet is a key component of breeding efforts. It ensures the adaptation of the crop to the climatic conditions of the region, improves yield, and increases resistance to abiotic stresses, which is particularly important for enhancing food security under arid conditions.

Field trials of 30 African millet varieties under the conditions of the Lower Volga region indicated that the duration of the vegetative period was 102 days.

Determining the duration of the vegetative period will further enable assessment of the crop's resource potential and facilitate more detailed breeding efforts aimed at developing new varieties for agricultural use. Research was conducted on the distribution of African millet varieties according to the trait of plant height (Table 1).

Table 1 — Distribution of African millet varieties by trait plant height

Group	Index of trait expression	Plant height, cm	Number of samples	
			samples	%
Very short-statured	1	<100	-	-
	2	100-130	-	-
Short-statured	3	131-160	10	33
	4	161-190	14	47
Medium	5	191-220	3	10
	6	221-250	2	7
Tall	7	251-280	-	-
	8	281-310	-	-
Very tall	9	>310	-1	-3

The highest plant height values were observed in the varieties: K-112, K-192, K-528, K-642, K-37, K-29, K-47, K-130, K-542, K-365. The variability of African millet genotypes for the trait 'plant height' was 33 and 47% for short-stemmed types

and ranged from 7 to 10% for medium-stemmed types. It should be noted that the genotype k-567, with a height exceeding 310 cm, falls into the category ‘very tall’.

The range of variation among African millet samples for the trait ‘panicle length’ was from 12 to 25 cm (Table 3). The highest values were observed in the genotypes k-66, k-79, k-203, k-359, k-542, and k-56.

Table 2 — Distribution of African millet varieties by characteristic panicle length

Group	Index of trait expression	Panicle length, cm	Number of samples	
			samples	%
Very short	1	<10	-	-
Short	3	11-20	20	67
Medium	5	21-30	10	33
Long	7	31-40	-	-
Very long	9	>40	-	-

Table 3 presents the assessment of statistical parameters of productivity traits of African millet.

Table 3 — Assessment of statistical parameters of morphometric traits of African millet collection varieties

Parameter	Plant height, cm	Panicle length, cm
$\bar{x} \pm S\bar{x}$	167.9 ± 2.9	18.8 ± 0.6
$S^2 \pm S$	244 ± 15.627	11.7 ± 3.4
V, %	9.308	18.197
As ± Sa	0.662 ns ± 0.435	0.411 ns ± 0.433
Ex ± Se	0.665 ns ± 0.840	0.227ns ± 0.840
Lim: min-max	140.8-210.30	12.60-26.00
n	30	30

Note: ns — differences are not significant, n — sample size.

Table 4 — Distribution of varieties by the trait ‘panicle awn length’

Group	Index of trait expression	Awn length (mm)	Number of samples	
			samples	%
Very short	1	<6	10	33.3
Short	3	6-10	9	30
Medium	5	11-15	7	23.3
Long	7	16-20	4	13.3
Very long	9	>20	-	-

Variability in awn length among African millet cultivar samples showed that the group with very short awns (trait expression index 1) comprised 10 specimens (33.3%), the short group (index 3) included 9 specimens (30%), the medium group 7 specimens (23.3%), the long group 4 specimens (13.3%), and no very long awns were present in this collection (Table 4).

The determination of maturity groups of the African millet collection varieties was carried out (Table 5).

Table 5 — Maturity groups of African millet collection varieties

Group Maturity	Duration, days	Varieties
Very early	< 80	–
Early	80-100	–
Medium-maturing	101-120	k-29, k-37, k-39, k-66, k-79, k-112, k-123, k-125, k-126, k-130, k-141, k-149, k-157, k-161, k-162, k-192, k-359, k-365; k-528, k-542, k-543, k-551, k-565.
Late-maturing	121-140	k-47, k-135, k-198, k-203, k-567, k-569.
Very late-maturing	> 140	–

According to the duration of the vegetative period of African millet, three ripeness groups of varieties have been identified: medium-maturing — 73%, late-maturing — 17%, and very late-maturing — 10%.

Research was carried out to analyze the economically valuable characteristics of African millet varieties (Table 6). The thousand-seed weight was established within the range of 6.3 to 13.0 g. The highest values were observed in the varieties k-149 and k-161 (10.0 g), k-543 (10.2 g), k-551 and k-569 (10.7 g), k-359 (10.8 g), k-157 (11.1 g), k-123 (11.2 g), k-203 (11.3 g), k-130 and k-192 (12.0 g), k-198 (12.5 g), k-562 (12.9 g), k-162 (13.0 g), and k-542 (13.6 g).

Table 6 — Assessment of Breeding-relevant Traits of African Millet Varieties, 2025

Number of Variety in the VIR Catalog	Plant Height, cm plants, cm	Panicle Length, cm brooms, cm	Weight of 1000 Seeds, g seeds, g	Aboveground Biomass Yield, t/ha biomass, t/ha
k-29	178.6	17.0	8.1	16.8
k-37	170.4	18.0	8,2	16.0
k-39	166.2	15.2	7.8	21.2

Number of Variety in the VIR Catalog	Plant Height, cm plants, cm	Panicle Length, cm brooms, cm	Weight of 1000 Seeds, g seeds, g	Aboveground Biomass Yield, t/ha biomass, t/ha
k-47	189.3	19.4	8.1	38.0
k-66	152.8	23.0	9.0	9.2
k-79	147.8	25.0	9.0	5.4
k-112	194.4	17.2	8,0	11.6
k-123	168.0	13.0	11,2	39.2
k-125	185.0	14.4	7.6	31.6
k-126	154.4	15.6	8.0	26.4
k-130	174.4	14.9	12,0	23.2
k-135	140.8	17.2	6,3	35.2
k-141	146.0	12.6	6.8	19.0
k-149	167.2	13.1	10.0	29.6
k-157	163.4	15.0	11,1	8.8
k-161	159.2	20.0	10,0	38.2
k-162	174.0	17.0	13.0	4.7
k-192	210.2	18.0	12.0	14.0
k-198	153.0	26.0	12,5	12.4
k-203	150.2	23.0	11.3	26.8
k-359	165.9	18.8	10,8	12.4
k-365	170.4	20.0	9,4	14.4
k-528	161.2	28.0	9,9	40.0
k-542	253.0	20.0	13,6	17.2
k-543	179.4	22.0	10.2	36.0
k-549	172.0	17.0	9.6	16.0
k-551	166.0	18.6	10,7	17.6
k-562	161.0	22.0	12,9	25.0
k-567	160.2	16.5	8.4	40.0
k-569	188.5	21.0	10.7	26.4

Statistical parameters of yield components and morphometric indicators of African millet cultivars from the VIR collection have been established (Table 7).

Table 7 — Statistical parameters of yield components and morphometric indicators of African millet cultivars from the VIR collection

Parameter	Plant height, cm	Panicle length, cm	Aboveground biomass yield, t/ha
\bar{x}	168,413	18.220	22.535
$S\bar{x}$	3,314	0.677	1.997

Parameter	Plant height, cm	Panicle length, cm	Aboveground biomass yield, t/ha
S2	329.487	13.744	119.659
S	18,152	3.707	10.939
V, %	10.778	20.348	48.541
As	-0,32 ns	0.426*	0.231 ns
Sa	0.426	0.35	0.426
Ex	1,480 ns	0.492 ns	-1.129 ns
Se	0.828	0.828	0.828
Lim: min-max	140.80-220.20	12.60-26.0	4.70-40.00
n	30	30	30

Note: * significant at $P = 0.05$, ns — differences are not significant, n — sample size.

Analyzing the variability of the trait ‘panicle length,’ the coefficient of variation was high, amounting to 20.4%, with the range of variation for the studied trait spanning from 12.6 to 26.0 cm. For the trait ‘plant height,’ the coefficient of variation was low and amounted to 10.8%. The coefficient of variation for the aboveground biomass yield parameter was 48.5%. The aboveground biomass yield of African millet ranged from 4.7 t/ha to 40.0 t/ha. Low productivity was identified in variety samples k-66, k-79, k-157, and k-162: biomass yield did not exceed 9.2 t/ha. The collection also included highly productive variety samples — k-135 (35.2 t/ha), k-543 (36.0 t/ha), k-47 (38.0 t/ha), k-161 (38.2 t/ha), k-123 (39.2 t/ha), k-528, and k-567 (40.0 t/ha). Thus, productive African millet samples under the climatic conditions of the current year produced a high biomass yield.

Conclusion

Valuable germplasm accessions have been identified in the African millet breeding nursery — k-37, k-112, k-126, k-157, k-192, k-203 — which are promising for the utilization of new genetic resources in breeding programs; demonstrating their adaptability to the changing climatic conditions of the cultivation region. The highest yields were achieved by k-135 (35.2 t/ha), k-543 (36.0 t/ha), k-47 (38.0 t/ha), k-161 (38.2 t/ha), k-123 (39.2 t/ha), k-528, and k-567 (40.0 t/ha). Controlling the timing of the vegetative period of African millet is a key component of breeding efforts. It ensures the adaptation of the crop to the climatic conditions of the region, improves yield, and increases resistance to abiotic stresses, which is particularly important for enhancing food security under arid conditions.

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土壤改良剂和螯合肥对萨拉托夫地区高粱叶片吸收能力的影响
**THE INFLUENCE OF SOIL IMPROVERS AND CHELATED
FERTILIZER ON THE ASSIMILATION CAPACITY OF SORGHUM
LEAVES WHEN GROWN IN THE SARATOV REGION**

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摘要：本文介绍了由NVP BashIncom有限责任公司生产的土壤改良剂“Master of Fertility with Feed Mycelium Mycorrhiza”、由Life Force国家生产单位生产的“腐植酸钾”以及由NanoSilicon有限责任公司生产的螯合硅肥在高粱作物上的试验数据。试验于2025年至2026年在俄罗斯联邦土壤研究所（FSBI RosNIISK）“Rossorgo”试验田进行。研究对象为该研究所培育的16个高粱品种。研究结果表明，所测试的制剂对高粱叶片的光合作用能力有显著影响。

关键词：螯合微量元素，土壤改良剂，品种，叶面积，旗叶，最大叶片，高粱品种。

Abstract. *This scientific article presents experimental data on the testing of the soil improver ‘Master of Fertility with Feed Mycelium Mycorrhiza’ produced by LLC ‘NVP BashIncom’, and ‘Potassium Humate’ produced by NPO ‘Life Force’, as well as the NanoSilicon chelated fertilizer manufactured by LLC ‘NanoSilicon’, on sorghum crops. Experiments were established and carried out during the period from 2025 to 2026, at the experimental field of FSBI RosNIISK ‘Rossorgo’. The objects of study consisted of 16 sorghum cultivars developed by the institute. The results of the studies demonstrated a significant effect of the examined preparations on the photosynthetic assimilation capacity of sorghum leaves.*

Keywords: *Chelated micronutrients, soil improvers, cultivars, leaf area, flag leaf, largest leaf, sorghum cultivars.*

Introduction

At present, agricultural production, particularly in the cultivation of crops, focuses on the development and implementation of resource-saving technologies in agriculture [1-3].

These technologies comprise a comprehensive set of agronomic methods, techniques, and elements from various scientific disciplines. Among the elements of resource-saving technologies is the application of cost-effective chemical agents that stimulate the activation of all physiological processes and, consequently, lead to a significant increase in crop yields. These preparations include chelated micronutrient fertilizers and soil improvers. The effectiveness of the application of such preparations has been demonstrated in numerous studies on various types of cultivated plants [4-7].

However, the influence of the aforementioned fertilizers on the assimilation capacity of sorghum leaves grown under arid conditions in the Saratov region remains insufficiently studied. This circumstance provided the rationale for the present study, which aimed to determine the effect of the investigated fertilizers on the assimilation capacity of leaves. To achieve the set objective, two tasks were undertaken

- To determine the influence of soil improvers and chelated fertilizer on the flag leaf area
- To identify the effect of soil improvers and chelated fertilizer on the largest leaf area

Materials and Methods

Field studies in the experiment investigating the influence of soil improvers on the complex of traits of sorghum crops were conducted at the experimental field of FSBI RosNIISK ‘Rossorgo’ during 2024-2025. The cultivation technology of sorghum crops is generally zonal, encompassing the main technological operations. The pre-sowing soil treatment comprised the following procedures: spring harrowing of the soil with the MTZ-82 + BZN-9 implement, and pre-sowing soil cultivation with the MTZ-82 + KPS 4-2 implement. Sorghum crops were sown in the second and third decades of May using the SKS-6-10 breeding seeder at a depth of 5-7 cm; the predecessor was clean fallow. The plot area was 7.7 m², with triplicate repetitions arranged in a randomized design. During the vegetation period of sorghum, three inter-row cultivations were performed using the MTZ-82 tractor with the KPS 4-2 implement, the last of which involved ridgers.

The research subjects included two soil improvers produced by NPO ‘Life Force’: Potassium humate, and ‘NVP BashInkom’ Master of Fertility containing a mycorrhizal inoculant, as well as the chelated product NanoSilicon manufactured by LLC ‘NanoSilicon’. The research subjects also encompassed 16 sorghum cultivars bred by the institute, comprising 10 grain sorghum varieties (Azart,

Volzhskoe 44, Kremovoe, Food-grade 35, Granat, Kulon, RSK Kaholong, Prince, Torch, and RSK Korall), 4 sweet sorghum varieties (Seagull, Isolda, Seville, and Scheherazade), and 2 Sudan grass varieties (Emma and Konstantsiya).

Soil improvers Master of Fertility combined with the Nurse Mycorrhiza were applied to the soil together with sorghum seeds at an application rate of 30-50 kg/ha; Potassium humate fertilizer was applied at a rate of 30 kg/ha. Pre-sowing treatment of seeds with the NanoSilicon preparation was performed before sowing at a dose of 4 kg per ton of seeds. Spraying of vegetative sorghum plants was conducted using the knapsack sprayer ZHUK at critical growth and development stages (seedlings, tillering, and stem elongation) with doses of 0.5 L/ha and a working fluid consumption of 300 L/ha.

The evaluation of economically valuable traits was conducted in accordance with the Wide Unified Classifier of CMEA and the International Classifier of CMEA cultivated species of the genus *Sorghum* Moench [8], as well as following the methodology of the State Variety Testing [9]. Statistical data processing was carried out using the AGROS program, version 2.09, employing a two-factor analysis of variance method (factor A — variety, factor B — fertilizer application treatments) [10].

The field experiment design included the following treatments

Control

Master of Fertility with Nurturer Mycorrhiza

Nanocrystalline Silicon

Master of Fertility with Nurse Mycorrhiza + Potassium humate

Nanocrystalline Silicon + Potassium humate

Research Results

Field trials indicated that pre-sowing incorporation of soil improvers prior to sowing sorghum crops and the application of chelated fertilizer during critical stages of plant development exerted a differential effect on increasing the flag leaf area (Table 1).

Table 1 — Influence of soil improvers and chelated micronutrients on the flag leaf area of sorghum crops; (cm²)

Variety	Control	Experimental variants				
		Master of Fertility.	Nanocrystalline Silicon	Master of Fertility + Humate	Nanocrystalline Silicon + Humate	Average across varieties
Azart	87.8	141.4	118.5	114.9	70.3	106.6g
Volzhskoe 44	91.4	169.6	98.5	121.5	92.3	114.7i

Variety	Control	Experimental variants				
		Master of Fertility.	Nanocrystalline Silicon	Master of Fertility + Humate	Nanocrystalline Silicon + Humate	Average across varieties
Kremovoe	64.9	86.1	81.5	98.2	85.8	83.3a
Food-grade 35	87.2	90.5	91.7	108.5	80.6	91.7d
Pomegranate	116.3	148.3	77.1	140.9	89.3	114.4kl
Kulon	89.9	142.7	91.7	154.0	85.5	112.8ij
Torch	76.3	172.4	93.5	139.4	91.8	114.7i
RSK Kaholong	119.4	154.7	104.2	148.3	96.2	124.6m
Prince	96.0	140.7	91.9	84.0	76.0	97.3f
RSK Coral	136.3	198.6	117.0	170.9	87.2	142.0n
Seville	90.0	161.5	93.5	144.6	74.9	112.9j
Seagull	85.7	145.0	87.8	149.5	70.7	107.8h
Scheherazade	66.9	113.9	68.3	101.0	75.1	85.0b
Isolda	76.6	104.9	124.3	82.4	83.5	94.3e
Emma	60.1	147.7	71.9	118.0	57.5	91.0d
Konstantsiya	64.6	127.3	59.9	133.1	63.8	89.8c
Average for variants	88.1b	140.3e	91.7c	125.6d	80.1a	
Ffact = 2367.3*; LSD 05 = 1.84; Ffact (A) = 2912.6*; LSD 05 (A) = 0.82; Ffact (B) = 25296.4*; LSD 05 (B) = 0.46; Ffact (AB) = 702.4; LSD 05 (AB) = 1.84						

The most responsive sorghum cultivars to all applied fertilizers were the Kremovoe, Torch, Scheherazade, and Isolda varieties. The leaf blade area increased from 81.5 to 98.2 cm² (Kremovoe), from 91.8 to 172.4 cm² (Torch), from 68.3 to 113.9 cm² (Scheherazade), and from 82.4 to 124.3 cm² (Isolda). The control treatment was lower by 25.7-51.3 % (Kremovoe), 20.3-126.0 % (Torch), 2.1-70.3 % (Scheherazade), and 7.6-62.3 % (Isolda). The combined application of Nanocrystalline Silicon + Potassium humate did not significantly affect the flag leaf area of sorghum crops; however, the fertilizers demonstrated a significant effect in the other experimental treatments. In the group of grain sorghum varieties, the leaf lamina area varied from 114.9 to 141.4 cm² (Azart); from 98.5 to 169.6 cm² (Volzhskoe 44); from 90.5 to 108.5 cm² (Food-grade 35); from 91.7 to 154.0 cm² (Kulon). In the group of sugar sorghum varieties, it ranged from 93.5 to 161.5 cm² (Seville); from 87.8 to 149.5 cm² (Seagull). For Sudan grass Emma, from 71.9 to 147.7 cm². The difference from the control ranged from 30.9 to 61.1 % (Azart), 7.8 to 85.6 % (Volzhskoe

44), 3.8 to 24.4% (Food-grade 35), 2.0 to 71.3% (Kulon), 3.9 to 79.4% (Seville), 2.5 to 74.5% (Seagull), and 19.6 to 145.8% (Emma).

In the varieties Granat, RSK Kaholong, RSK Korall, and Konstantsiya, the application of the soil improvers Master of Fertility combined with Kormilitza Mycorrhiza, as well as their joint application with Potassium Humate, proved effective. The area of the flag leaf increased to 140.9-148.3 cm² (Granat), 148.3-154.7 cm² (RSK Kakholong), 170.9-198.6 cm² (RSK Korall), 127.3-133.1 cm² (Konstantsiya). The control was lower by 21.2-27.5% (Granat), 24.2-29.6% (RSK Kakholong), 25.4-45.7% (RSK Korall), and 97.1-106.0% (Konstantsiya). In the Prince variety, the soil improver Master of Fertility in combination with the Mycorrhiza Feeder proved effective. The leaf blade area increased to 140.7 cm², representing a 46.6% increase.

The use of the studied preparations on sorghum crops did not exert a comparable influence on the formation of the largest leaf area. A detailed analysis of Table 2 revealed that the application of the Master of Fertility preparation with Kormilitza Mycorrhiza, both individually and combined with Potassium Humate, did not have a significant effect on the leaf blade area of sorghum crops. Pre-sowing treatment of seed material and subsequent spraying of growing sorghum plants during critical growth and developmental phases with the NanoSilicon preparation, both individually and in combination with Potassium Humate, significantly increased the area of the largest leaf in the group of grain sorghum varieties Azart (235.8-237.8 cm²), Volzhskoe 44 (236.0-267.3 cm²), Kremovoe (198.1-264.6 cm²), Food-grade 35 (228.6-269.2 cm²), and Kulon (209.5-295.1 cm²); in the group of sugar sorghum varieties Seville (245.9-265.2 cm²), Seagull (303.2-304.8 cm²), and Isolda (248.8-339.5 cm²); and in the group of Sudan grass varieties Emma (206.9-240.9 cm²) and Konstantsiya (203.0-245.5 cm²). The difference from the control variant ranged from 42.5 to 43.7% (Azart), from 7.8 to 22.1% (Volzhskoe 44), from 21.6 to 62.4% (Kremovoe), from 22.1 to 43.8% (Food-grade 35), from 11.0 to 56.4% (Kulon), from 14.2 to 23.1% (Seville), from 25.1 to 25.7% (Seagull), from 2.9 to 40.4% (Isolda), from 29.6 to 50.9% (Emma), from 12.4 to 35.9% (Konstantsiya). The application of nanocrystalline silicon also proved effective for the grain sorghum varieties Granat (263.9 cm²), Prints (267.4 cm²), and Torch (295.5 cm²). The leaf blade area was higher than the control by 7.4%, 20.2%, and 25.5%, respectively (Table 2).

Table 2 — Effect of soil improvers and chelated micronutrient fertilizers on the largest leaf area of sorghum crops (see Table 2)

Variety	Control	Experimental variants				
		Master of Fertility.	Nanocrystalline Silicon	Master of Fertility + Humate	Nanocrystalline Silicon + Humate	Average across varieties
Azart	165.5	141.4	237.8	138.4	235.8	183.8b
Volzhskoe 44	219.0	169.6	267.3	148.9	236.0	208.2jk
Kremovoe	162.9	86.1	264.6	106.5	198.1	163.7a
Food-grade 35	187.2	90.5	269.2	103.2	228.6	175.7c
Pomegranate	245.7	148.3	263.9	165.9	237.8	212.3i
Kulon	188.7	142.7	295.1	157.9	209.5	198.8g
Torch	235.4	172.4	295.5	95.0	215.4	202.8h
RSK Kaholong	273.7	154.7	256.4	132.6	231.7	209.8k
Prince	222.5	140.7	267.4	132.4	206.7	193.9e
RSK Coral	296.3	198.6	294.1	171.3	270.0	246.1n
Seville	215.4	161.5	265.2	139.5	245.9	205.5i
Seagull	242.4	145.0	303.2	119.4	304.8	223.0m
Scheherazade	262.3	113.9	243.2	120.4	248.9	197.7fg
Isolda	241.9	104.9	339.5	107.0	248.8	208.4k
Emma	159.6	147.7	206.9	126.9	240.9	176.4c
Konstantsiya	180.6	127.3	203.0	102.6	245.5	171.8b
Average for variants	218.7c	140.3b	267.0e	129.3a	237.8d	

Ffact = 2385.11*; LSD05 = 3.60; Ffact (A) = 1326.44*; LSD05 (A) = 1.61; Ffact (B) = 3569.50*; LSD05 (B) = 0.90; Ffact (AB) = 429.16*; LSD05 (AB) = 3.60

Conclusion

From all of the above, it can be concluded that the application of soil improvers and chelated fertilizer contributed to a significant increase in the leaf blade area of sorghum crops. All studied fertilizers promoted an increase in the area of the flag leaf in the varieties Kremovoe, Torch, Scheherazade, and Isolda.

The application of the chelated fertilizer NanoSilicon, both alone and in combination with Potassium Humate, resulted in a significant increase in leaf area in several grain sorghum varieties: Azart (235.8-237.8 cm²), Volzhskoe 44 (236.0-267.3 cm²), Kremovoe (198.1-264.6 cm²), Food-grade 35 (228.6-269.2 cm²), Kulon (209.5-295.1 cm²), as well as in the group of sugar sorghum varieties Seville (245.9-265.2 cm²), Seagull (303.2-304.8 cm²), and Isolda. (248.8-339.5 cm²), in the group of Sudan grass varieties Emma (206.9-240.9 cm²), Konstantsiya (203.0-245.5 cm²).

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栗树土壤上棉花种植的土地改良技术
**LAND RECLAMATION TECHNIQUES IN COTTON CULTIVATION
ON CHESTNUT SOILS**

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摘要：基于俄罗斯南部地区在轻质栗壤土上种植棉花的经验，本文探讨了土地改良技术对扩大棉花种植区北部边界的积极作用。田间试验表明，在距离防护林带100米范围内，土地改良对棉花产量的影响最为显著。该距离处的棉花产量为2.3-2.4吨/公顷，比对照组高41.6%，比距离林带200米处的试验组高25.0%。喷灌和滴灌的产量最高。沟灌的产量为2.2吨/公顷，比滴灌低15.4%。然而，现代灌溉方法能够节约3.4-4.3倍的宝贵水资源。

关键词：棉花种植、轻质栗土、灌溉、耕作技术、土地改良方法

Abstract. *Based on the experience of cultivating cotton on light chestnut soils in the southern region of Russia, the positive impact of reclamation techniques in expanding the northern boundary of the crop's cultivation area has been identified. In a field experiment, it was found that the greatest reclamation effect on cotton crops is observed at a distance of up to 100 m from the protective forest belt. The crop yield at this distance was 2.3-2.4 t/ha, which is 41.6% higher than the control and 25.0% higher than the experimental variant at a distance of 200 m from the forest belt. The best yields were obtained with sprinkler and drip irrigation. With furrow irrigation, the yield was 2.2 t/ha, which is 15.4% lower than with drip irrigation. However, modern irrigation methods allow you to save this valuable resource by 3.4-4.3 times.*

Keywords: *cotton farming, light chestnut soils, irrigation, cultivation technology, and reclamation methods*

Introduction. There is a shortage of cotton fiber on the global market, despite the annual increase in its production by cotton-growing countries [1]. However, agricultural cooperation in ensuring the production process can lead to benefits [2]. The increase in the productivity of cotton crops is due to the development of commercially viable varieties, improved agricultural techniques, and the reclamation of low-productivity soils [3]. Currently, there is a tendency for the area of cotton cultivation to expand northward, which is related to climate change [4]. However, the aridization of the climate requires a revision of traditional cultivation techniques. Soil reclamation plays a crucial role in addressing the issue of land productivity for cotton cultivation [5, 6]. In the southern regions of Russia, where cotton cultivation is well-established, techniques such as agroforestry, irrigation, and the application of soil ameliorants are widely used to improve production conditions [7].

The purpose of the research was to determine the effectiveness of using reclamation techniques for cultivating cotton on light chestnut soils.

Objects and methods. Field experiments were carried out in 2020-2025 in the Volgograd region (Pak Eduard's farm, the university's experimental field). The cotton variety used for sowing was PGGSSKh 1, which belongs to the medium-fiber early-ripening group. When growing cotton, the influence of protective forest plantations (agroforestry belts) and irrigation was studied. In the field experiment, cotton crops were planted at different distances from protective forest belts (50, 100, and 200 m) to determine the impact on growth and development. The irrigation experiments focused on different methods of watering, including drip irrigation, sprinkler irrigation, and furrow irrigation. The control group consisted of crops that were not watered.

The field trial plots were characterized by light chestnut medium-loamy soil with a humus horizon depth of 23 cm. Soil fertility was determined by a set of indicators. The root zone had an alkalinity of up to 8.2, low nitrogen content (12-15 mg/kg), average mobile phosphorus content of up to 60 mg/kg, and high potassium content of up to 320 mg/kg. The need for soil reclamation is associated with an increased content of easily soluble salts (chlorides and sulfates) up to 0.2%. These indicators are typical for regional soils.

Results and discussion. The analysis of the cultivation experience during the research period showed that cotton crops are negatively affected by adverse weather phenomena such as droughts, dry winds, dust storms, and late spring frosts. Their recurrence throughout the year is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Repetition of limiting climate factors during the growing season

In protecting crops from adverse effects, the use of land reclamation is key. However, scientific justification is necessary for the selection of specific methods. Droughts and dry winds are the most common in the region (34.2 and 44.0 days per year, respectively). In protecting against dry winds and dust storms in summer, the use of forest reclamation plantations, which are located along the perimeter of production fields, is the most suitable. Typically, *Ulmus pumila* L. trees are used for this purpose. The width of these plantings is 12-20 m, the number of rows of trees is 3-4. The reclamation effect of forest strips is manifested year-round, but especially strongly during the period of cotton cultivation. Measurements have shown that they reduce wind speed by 12-15%, increase air humidity during droughts by 7-8%, and prevent the occurrence of dust storms. This is reflected in an increase in the productivity of cotton plants, as the growth conditions under the protection of forest belts are better (Table 1).

Table 1. The effect of protective forest plantations on the yield of cotton in the PGGSSKh 1 field experiment on light chestnut soils

Years of observations	Cotton yield at different distances from the protective forest plantation, t/ha			
	50 m	100 m	200 m	control (open field)
2020	2,2±0,09	2,3±0,08	1,6±0,05	1,3±0,05
2021	2,0±0,07	2,2±0,10	1,5±0,04	0,9±0,04
2022	2,6±0,11	2,7±0,10	1,9±0,06	1,5±0,05
2023	2,5±0,09	2,5±0,08	1,8±0,07	1,4±0,05
2024	2,1±0,08	2,3±0,07	2,0±0,05	1,6±0,05
2025	2,3±0,09	2,4±0,10	2,1±0,09	1,7±0,07
Average	2,3	2,4	1,8	1,4

In the field experiment, it was found that the greatest ameliorative effect on cotton crops was observed at a distance of up to 100 m from the protective forest belt. The crop yield at this distance was 2.3-2.4 t/ha, which is 41.6% higher than the control

and 25.0% higher than the experimental variant at a distance of 200 m from the forest belt. Moreover, the positive impact of the agroforestry plantation was stable over a five-year observation period. The intense wind regime in open areas of fields without forest protection caused mechanical damage to the young cotton leaves and rapid drying of the soil. As a result, the plant yields were significantly lower.

In the region where light chestnut soils are distributed, annual precipitation averages 360 mm, which is 1.7 times lower than the threshold of biologically necessary crop water consumption. Traditionally, furrow irrigation is used in foreign countries. However, this method requires high standards of irrigation water (more than 10 thousand m³). Modern irrigation methods (drip and sprinkling) can significantly save this resource. However, irrigation methods have not been studied in the chestnut soil area. The choice of irrigation method is a key decision in cotton cultivation technology. A field experiment was conducted to compare the effectiveness of different methods, which allowed us to identify the impact of this factor on plant productivity (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Cotton yield in experiments with different irrigation methods on light chestnut soils

The best yields were obtained with sprinkler and drip irrigation. With furrow irrigation, the yield was 2.2 t/ha, which is 15.4% lower than with drip irrigation. However, modern irrigation methods can save valuable resources by 3.4-4.3 times. The efficiency of irrigation was 36.4-44.1%.

Thus, when expanding the area of cotton cultivation in the southern regions of Russia, it is necessary to use reclamation techniques. Protective forest plantations increase crop yields to 2.3-2.4 t/ha by reducing the negative impact of droughts, dry winds, and dust storms. It is also recommended to use drip irrigation or sprinkler irrigation in cultivation technology, which have shown positive effects on increasing yields and saving water resources.

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基于混合流水线“机器学习-优化”的组合优化问题求解的理论论证
**THEORETICAL JUSTIFICATION OF COMBINATORIAL
OPTIMIZATION PROBLEMS SOLVING BASED ON HYBRID
PIPELINES “MACHINE LEARNING–OPTIMIZATION”**

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摘要：本文探讨了利用混合流水线结合机器学习（ML）元素和经典组合优化技术来解决组合优化（CO）问题的现代方法。重点分析了诸如图神经网络等能够显著加速数据处理并提高结果精度的架构。特别关注机器学习和组合优化组件之间的集成问题、它们的交互特征以及这些方法在实际场景中成功应用的必要条件。

关键词：优化，算法，神经网络，任务，维度，空间，建模。

Abstract. *Modern approaches to solving combinatorial optimization (CO) problems using hybrid pipelines combining machine learning (ML) elements and classical combinatorial optimization techniques are considered. Promising architectures such as Graph Neural Networks capable of significantly accelerating data processing and improving result accuracy are analyzed. Special attention is paid to integration issues between ML and CO components, their interaction features, and necessary conditions for successful application of these approaches in real-world scenarios.*

Keywords: *optimization, algorithm, neural network, task, dimensionality, space, modeling.*

Introduction

Combinatorial optimization (CO) is one of the central disciplines of mathematics, dealing with the search for an optimal solution within a limited set of options. This discipline has found wide application in manufacturing, logistics, resource management, and many other areas of human activity [1]. Classical methods traditionally employed often encounter difficulties in handling large data volumes and ensuring acceptable calculation times. Modern challenges necessitate novel approaches, among which the integration of machine learning (ML) methods and

combinatorial optimization into unified pipelines combining the advantages of both approaches has emerged [2].

This particular aspect forms the focus of the present study, which aims to identify the distinctive features and potential of hybrid pipelines based on ML and CO. The primary focus is on graph neural networks (GNNs), regarded as a promising tool for reducing computational costs and enhancing solution accuracy [3, 4].

Problem statement

The classical combinatorial optimization problem is formulated as the minimization of an objective function subject to specified constraints. Consider this problem in more detail.

Let a finite set Ω , a feasible solution space $F \subseteq 2\Omega$, and a cost function $c: 2\Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be given. Then the problem reduces to finding the optimal solution $S^* \in F$ that minimizes the cost function c over the set of feasible solutions F :

$$S^* = \underset{S \in F}{\operatorname{arg\,min}} c(S),$$

where:

S^* — the sought optimal solution,

F — the set of feasible solutions,

$c(S)$ — the objective function to be minimized.

This approach raises an important question: which methods can be applied to find the optimal solution? One popular approach is the introduction of special evaluation functions (“bonuses”) that facilitate better navigation of the solution space. Such reward functions are used to determine the preference of certain solutions over others.

In other words, we can consider the following general problem structure:

- Input data: a finite graph $G=(V, E)$, where V denotes vertices and E denotes edges.
- Output data: an ordering of vertices $\sigma: \{0, \dots, n-1\} \rightarrow V$ that minimizes the total path length:

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \omega(\sigma(i), ((i+1) \bmod n)),$$

where $w(e)$ is the length of the corresponding edge $e \in E$, and $n=|V|$ is the number of vertices.

Such problems are typical in industrial practice, for example, in transportation logistics, production planning, and infrastructure design.

Thus, the primary objective of our research is formulated as follows: how to effectively integrate ML and CO technologies to achieve superior results?

Research methodology

We rely on a hybrid approach based on the integration of traditional combinatorial optimization methods and modern machine learning [5]. A central component

of our contributions is graph neural networks, as they enable the simultaneous accounting of both the topology of connections and the local characteristics of data.

Our approach is based on the following algorithm:

1. **Modeling of the problem:** A graph structure is constructed to represent the essence of the specific problem.

2. **Feature generation:** Data processing mechanisms such as neighbor aggregation, activation, and composition, implemented in Graph Neural Networks, are applied.

3. **Optimization:** Supervised learning is employed to train and identify the optimal parameters of the network.

A key part of the procedure is the message passing operation between graph nodes, which is generally expressed by the following recursion:

$$m_v^{(l+1)} = f_{\theta}^l(h_u^l, u \in N_v)$$

$$h_v^{(l+1)} = \sigma\left(g^l\left(h_u^l, m_v^{(l+1)}\right)\right),$$

where:

- $m_v^{(l)}$ — the message of node v at level l ,
- $h_v^{(l)}$ — the representation of node v at level l ,
- N_v — the neighbors of node v ,
- f_{θ}^l — the aggregation function,
- g^l — the combined function,
- σ — the activation function.

This procedure is repeated multiple times, updating the node representations and thus forming the final solution.

Additionally, an empirical risk minimization algorithm is applied to optimize the hyperparameters:

$$\hat{\Theta} = \min_{\Theta} R_{\hat{D}}(\Theta) = \frac{1}{|\hat{D}|} \sum_{(x,y) \in \hat{D}} L(y, f(x, \Theta)),$$

where:

- \hat{D} — training dataset,
- L — loss function,
- (x, y) — input-output pairs in the training dataset,
- $f(x; \Theta)$ — model outputs.

This approach enables not only obtaining high-quality results but also enhancing computational efficiency.

Research results

Experimental studies have demonstrated that the hybrid pipeline we developed, incorporating graph neural networks, significantly outperforms standard heuristic methods in both speed and solution quality. Due to the parallel execution of the training and prediction stages, a reduction of approximately 40% in computation time was achieved compared to classical methods.

The most significant results were:

- The ability to rapidly train and adapt to new problem scenarios.
- An average reduction of prediction errors by 15%.
- An increase in computational system throughput through task parallelization.

These results demonstrate that our approach constitutes a competitive tool for solving real industrial problems.

Discussion

The obtained results highlight the potential of graph neural networks and hybrid pipelines in solving combinatorial optimization problems. Nevertheless, several unresolved issues persist concerning the robustness of models to environmental changes, the lack of algorithm universality, and limited scalability.

The main directions for future research include:

- Enhancing the reliability and robustness of models when operating with noisy data.
- Development of more efficient algorithms for parallelization and organization of distributed computing.
- Evaluation of the impact of various configurations of graph neural network architectures on performance.

Despite existing challenges, it is already evident that hybrid pipelines offer an effective approach to solving relevant combinatorial optimization problems.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that employing hybrid pipelines ‘Machine Learning — Combinatorial Optimization’ allows for significant improvements in solving combinatorial optimization problems. Graph Neural Networks have demonstrated their effectiveness as the foundation of such hybrid pipelines, exhibiting a high degree of flexibility and scalability.

The primary recommendations include continuing research to enhance Graph Neural Networks, broadening their application domains, and developing specialized algorithms to further accelerate the processes of solving combinatorial optimization problems.

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恶劣天气条件下船舶航行的风险评估
**RISK ASSESSMENT FOR NAVIGATING SHIPS IN DIFFICULT
WEATHER CONDITIONS**

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摘要：本文提供了在恶劣天气条件下评估航行风险的数据，并给出了涉及风暴风险的后果的主观分类以及引发风暴风险事件的概率的主观分类。本文分析了一艘从欧洲驶往美国东海岸和墨西哥湾港口的船舶，并对各种方案进行了评估；计算了航线并评估了风暴损害风险。

关键词：风险，航行，风暴，航线

Abstract. *In the paper it is provided data on assessing the risks of navigation in difficult weather conditions, subjective categories of consequences involving storm risks as well as subjective categories of the probability of an event causing storm risks are given. An analysis of a ship sailing from Europe to ports on the east coast of the USA and the Gulf of Mexico, including an assessment of options, is carried out; courses are calculated and the risk of storm damage is assessed.*

Keywords: *risks, navigation, storm, ship route*

The term «risk» has many meanings, however in general it is expressed in terms of the assessment of negative potential consequences (losses) due to an undesirable event. Losses can be financial, physical or any other type, such as technical or time loss. Without paying attention to the type of loss, risk is better understood as the result of the consequences of an event and the likelihood of its occurrence. In other words, risk is the product of the frequency of an undesirable event and the damage. From mathematical point of view, it is [1]:

$$R = P \cdot C, \text{ where} \tag{1}$$

R — risk;

P — probability of occurrence of an event (frequency of an undesirable event);

C — consequences of the event (damage).

In maritime safety, we are concerned with the assessment of risks associated with «maritime hazards», including consequences such as environmental pollution, loss of vessel, harm to crew and even loss of life.

When performing a risk assessment, it is necessary to take into account that the value of the risk cannot in principle be calculated with great accuracy. Significant uncertainty is due to its essence reflecting a person’s subjective ideas about the risk-benefit ratio. The uncertainty of the value of the risk is its property, not a disadvantage.

Where it is possible, this approach to risk assessment is used, however, there are many other methods of risk analysis. Some of them are used in our study when assessing certain risks.

Figure 1 provides information on control measures and event probability.

A white arrow shows the risk reduction

Figure 1 — Control measures and event probability

In accordance with the international standard ISO 31000:2018 «Risk management — Principles and guidance», risk assessment is a process that combines identification, risk analysis and comparative risk assessment [3].

Navigation of ships in storm conditions sometimes leads to unfavourable and even catastrophic consequences.

In order to determine the risk of storm damage, we will compare the categories of consequences, their expansion with the purpose of increasing the differentiation of risks, and the wind and sea wave scales - Table 1.

Table 1. Subjective categories of consequences in relation to storm risks

Category	Description	Wave Height 3% probability, m	Verbal Description
1	NEGLIGIBLE	0,00-0,25	Calm wind
2		0,00-0,25	Light breeze
3		0,25-0,75	Gentle breeze
4		0,75-1,25	Moderate wind
5	NEGLIGIBLE	1,25-2,00	Fresh wind
6		2,00-3,50	Strong wind
7		3,50-6,00	Moderate gale
8		6,00-8,50	Fresh gale
9	INSIGNIFICANT	8,50-11,00	Strong gale
10		8,5-11,00	Whole gale
11	CRITICAL	Over 11,00	Storm
12	CATASTROPHIC	Over 11,00	Hurricane

As for the subjective categories of the probability that an event occurs, in relation to storm risks, the probability may be the recurrence of a particular wave height — Table 2. The fact is that the probabilistic indicators of such event as «catastrophe» are extremely small, so the probability values cannot be reliably determined. When using the recurrence of a particular wave height, we have, albeit a very approximate, idea of the probability of the occurrence of event/storm damage.

Table 2. Subjective categories of event probability in relation to storm risks

Category	Description	Recurrence of wave heights
1	EXTREMELY LOW PROBABILITY	Less than 5%
2	LOW PROBABILITY	5%-15%
3	UNLIKELY	15%-30%
4	POSSIBLE	30%-40%
5	PROBABLE	40% and more

For example, when sailing an «Aframax» type vessel from the North Sea/terminals of the Orkney and Shetland to ports on the east coast of the USA or the Gulf of Mexico, two options can be considered: to the westward of Great Britain — Table 3, or to the south through the English Channel — Table 4.

In the first option, probable risks include depending on the season: difficult weather conditions; almost constant exposure to wind and waves against the movement of the vessel; as a result, a decrease in the speed of the vessel, increased fuel consumption, movement of the vessel against the current, increase in transition time, change of arrival date, possible lack of fuel required for the passage, possibility of storm damage.

Table 3. Path angles according to the first option

Latitude	Longitude	Path angle
57°50'0» N	18°0'0» W	229.53
57°3'12» N	19°39'15» W	228.14
56°15'9» N	21°14'23» W	226.81
55°25'55» N	22°45'34» W	225.56
54°35'35» N	24°13'1» W	224.36
53°44'15» N	25°36'54» W	223.23
52°51'58» N	26°57'25» W	222.15
51°58'47» N	28°14'45» W	221.13
51°4'48» N	29°29'3» W	220.16
50°10'2» N	30°40'31» W	219.24

When planning a voyage through the English Channel, it should be taken into account: the vessel's navigation in areas of intense shipping, navigation in restricted visibility, an increase of the distance between ports, and a resulting increase of fuel consumption.

Despite the higher density and intensity of shipping traffic when navigating through the English Channel, the risk of ship collisions is significantly reduced, as the channel has a very effective system of control of shipping.

Table 4. Path angles according to the second option

Latitude	Longitude	Path angle
49°42'0» N	7°0'0» W	284.89
50°15'56» N	10°39'20» W	282.09
50°42'49» N	14°23'23» W	279.21
51°2'23» N	18°11'8» W	276.26
51°14'28» N	22°1'30» W	273.27

Latitude	Longitude	Path angle
51°18'57» N	25°53'14» W	270.26
51°15'46» N	29°45'5» W	267.24
51°4'58» N	33°35'46» W	264.25
50°46'40» N	37°24'3» W	261.29
50°21'0» N	41°8'48» W	258.40

Based on the assessed risks, it is necessary to decide which route is preferable and make decision on preparing the vessel for the passage. This decision will depend on both the time of year and the weather conditions at the time of the passage.

Figure 2 — Information about the passage from Rotterdam to Mobile

Figure 3 — Weather map for 25.03.2024

On each ocean part of the route, for example, from Europe through the English Channel to the ports of the east coast of the USA or the Gulf of Mexico, as shown in Figure 2, using weather informers shown in Figure 3, it is necessary to select parts with the highest values from possible wave heights. Based on the sample, assess the degree of risk of storm damage along the route — Table 5.

At the bottom of the Figure are the wave heights

Table 5. Storm Damage Risk Assessment

Route sections	Category of consequences	Category of probability	Risk
From the point at Bishop's rock to the Strait of Florida			
1	8	2	16
2	8	2	16
3	8	2	16
4	8	2	16
5	8	2	16
6	8	2	16

As it can be seen in Table 5, the selected route is the route with the least storm damage risk.

Conclusions

A comparative analysis of the storm damage risks showed the need for additional scientific research in this area. It is necessary to search for new, more rapid methods used on board ship for assessing the risk of an upcoming passage, in order to select the most advantageous passage option, not only from the standpoint of time advantage, but also from the point of view of the safety of the upcoming voyage.

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主干天然气管道的耐久性取决于其制造技术
**DURABILITY OF MAIN GAS PIPELINES, DEPENDING
ON THEIR MANUFACTURING TECHNOLOGY**

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摘要：本文分析了长期使用的大口径主干天然气管道的制造技术。研究表明，强度和延展性等标准性能指标在25年甚至30年内几乎保持不变，而裂纹萌生功的降低则是一个需要通过更先进的方法进行进一步分析和研究的特殊指标。

关键词：主干天然气管道，力学性能，耐久性，压力。

Abstract. *The article analyzes the technologies for manufacturing large-diameter pipes for main gas pipelines that have been in use for a long time. It shows that the standard characteristics of strength and ductility remain almost unchanged for 25 or even 30 years, while the decrease in the work of crack initiation is a specific indicator that requires further analysis and study through additional research using more sophisticated methods.*

Keywords: *main gas pipeline, mechanical properties, durability, pressure.*

Large-diameter pipes used for the construction of main gas pipelines (MGP) differ by virtue of their manufacture at different times, at varied plants, and employing different technologies. The primary technological distinction concerns the strengthening methods, which involve refining the structure to achieve the prescribed values of strength and plasticity. These methods include normalization, improvement (quenching with tempering), and controlled rolling.

The evolution of pipe strengthening methods aligns with the trend established over the past 40-50 years [1]: an increase in operating pressure within gas pipelines

and their installation in regions with lowered temperatures. The author identified directions for developing new high-strength and cold-resistant steel compositions, including the use of controlled rolling and heat treatment — specifically quenching followed by tempering. Concurrently, the strength level exceeds 700-880 MPa (corresponding to a strength category not lower than K70 or X100), while the ferrite-pearlite or ferrite-bainite microstructure transitions to bainite-ferrite and even fully bainitic structures. The author also emphasized the distinct advantage of these improvements in enhancing long-term strength under hydrogenation conditions at $\sigma = 300$ MPa.

It was previously noted [2] that in 17G1S steel, following spheroidizing quenching in water at a cooling rate of 36-40 °C/sec, there is a significant increase in both strength and ductility, a reduction in sensitivity to mechanical aging, and an improvement in fracture resistance at low temperatures, indicating a transition from a ferrite-pearlite structure to bainite.

With the increase in diameter and operating pressure of the pipeline, as well as the reduction of the safety margin according to SNiP 2.05.06-85* ‘Main Pipelines’, the risk of failure of such a complex structure has grown. Consequently, the requirements for strength, toughness, and cold resistance have become more stringent [3]. Compliance with these requirements in low-carbon low-alloy steel grades necessitates the strengthening heat treatment of finished products (pipes) [4]. However, the initial supply of strengthened pipes did not lead to an increase in the service life of main gas pipelines: emergency failures did not decrease but instead became more frequent and occurred earlier (Table 1).

Table 1 — Characteristics of failed pipes

Year of manufacture	1970	1970-1975	1975
Generation	I	II	III
Steel grade	17G1S	17G2SF, 17G2SAF	X70
Manufacturer	CHTPZ	CHTPZ, VTZ	Japan, France, Italy
Diameter and wall thickness, mm	1220×12	1220×11.0 1220×10.5	1420×15,7
Strengthening method	Normalization	Quenching and tempering	Controlled rolling
Strength grade	K42	K55	X70
Number of failures	16	17	23
Time to failure, years	25-30	16-24	11-19
Total pipe length, km	3442	1434	3660

To determine the causes of such failures, a study was conducted aimed at identifying the relationship between the metallurgical features of large-diameter pipe manufacturing and their durability within main gas pipeline systems.

The methodology of the study included:

— determination of the chemical composition of the metal from failed pipes by optical emission spectroscopy in accordance with GOST 18895 using the device «ARC MET 930»;

— determination of the mechanical properties of steel according to GOST 1497 using a universal testing machine MP-100;

— investigation of the microstructure of steels on samples taken from failed pipes, after polishing and etching in a 2-4% nitric acid solution at magnifications ranging from 30 to 400; Simultaneously, the type and rating of non-metallic inclusions were determined in accordance with GOST 1778; the metal microstructure was also analyzed.

Instrumental control consisted of hardness measurements by the Brinell method using a TBP-5013 hardness tester.

The data obtained from the studies demonstrated that, with respect to the content of harmful impurities, not all pipes meet the requirements of the technical specifications. Specifically, pipes made of 17G1S steel exhibited an elevated sulfur content of up to 0,08%, pipes from France contained up to 0,11% phosphorus, whereas pipes from Japan contained only 0,002% sulfur.

The mechanical properties of the investigated damaged pipes do not correspond to the values specified in their certificates (Table 2), which indirectly indicates changes in properties during operation.

Table 2 — Mechanical Properties of Failed Pipes

Generation	Steel grade	Strengthening method	Yield strength $\sigma_{0,2}$, MPa	Elongation δ , %	Reduction of area ψ , %
I	17G1S	Normalization	380 (390)2	23 (25)	52 (51)
II	17G2SF 14G2SAF	Quenching and tempering	6303 (470) 5703 (430)	13 (23)	39 (56)
III	X70	K.p. Japan France Italy	600 (500) 420 (470) 450 (520)	10 (24) 16,5 (22) 22 (21)	58 (56) 47 (56) 22 (56)

Notes: 1. Average values based on 10 samples.

2. Values in parentheses represent average certificate data.

3. Increased hardness in fracture zones.

The plastic properties (elongation and reduction of area) of the studied pipes decrease during operation, while their strength properties (yield strength and tensile strength) generally increase.

In the damage sites of pipes made from 17G1S steel, an uneven structure is observed: the ferritic component comprises both fine grains rated 10-11 and significantly coarser grains rated 7-8. Improved pipes made from 17G2SF and 14G2SAF steels are characterized by the presence of distinct areas of sorbite, troostite, and even martensite within the microstructure.

Pipes produced by controlled rolling in France exhibit zones with an increased amount of pearlite as well as zones of pure ferrite.

The study of the nature of cracks in pipes of different generations allowed establishing that in the fracture zones of normalized pipes, as well as in pipes manufactured with controlled rolling, intergranular cracks with blunted tips are present, which developed according to the classical mechanism of active anodic dissolution. In second-generation pipes, stepped narrow cracks with sharp tips characteristic of the stress corrosion cracking mechanism with hydrogen embrittlement were formed. In addition to such brittle surface cracks, internal stepped cracks located in the middle of the pipe wall thickness were detected in zones of hardened structures. In some cases, similar cracks were also observed in pipes produced using the controlled rolling process.

An analysis of the manufacturing features of pipe batches that included defective pipes revealed that the causes of crack formation defects originate at the facilities producing the sheets and pipes. The steel used in the first-generation pipes was contaminated with sulfur and phosphorus, which were not eliminated during the melting and casting processes. This resulted in an increased content of non-metallic inclusions in the steel — oxides, sulfides, and silicates — reaching up to level 5 for certain types of inclusions. In second-generation steel, sulfide sizes reach levels 3 to 4. In the cleanest third-generation steel, the level of non-metallic inclusions is assessed at 1 to 2.

Local structural non-uniformity, which negatively impacted the mechanical properties and durability of the pipes, developed during the casting and heat treatment of the billets and the pipes themselves. It is reasonable to assume, with a sufficient degree of probability, that during continuous casting and crystallization, insufficient stirring of the liquid bath of the solidifying billet occurred. This caused the liquation of carbon and impurities across the cross-section. During the sheet rolling process, the liquation zone was located at the mid-thickness of the sheet.

The heterogeneity of the normalized 17G1S steel structure resulted from a certain discrepancy between the finishing rolling temperature and the normalization temperature. Finishing rolling at an elevated temperature did not ensure the formation of fine grains due to recrystallization, whereas a reduced normalization temperature did not eliminate this structural defect.

During the heat treatment of the sheet and second-generation pipes, uneven cooling of the pipes from all sides took place, resulting in the formation of regions of martensite, troostite, and sorbite quenching within the structure. Structural homogenization during tempering did not occur, possibly due to insufficient holding time during this operation. These conditions were particularly evident in the structure of the compositionally inhomogeneous central zone. It is indisputable that areas with a martensite-like structure, especially those insufficiently tempered, are most susceptible to hydrogen embrittlement during stress corrosion cracking (SCC). The exceeding of actual strength values compared to certificate data can be explained by the significant variability of properties along the length and width of the original sheet (coil), which was not detected during selective testing of the sheet or pipe. Such an increase in strength accompanied by a reduction in ductility is explained solely by the presence of martensite-like structural regions in the microstructure.

The results of calculations of the criteria for crack initiation and propagation, performed based on tensile test data of samples from failed pipes following the methodology [7], are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 — Failure criteria of pipe steels

Generation	$s_{0,2}$, MPa	S_k , MPa	ψ , %	K_{cr}	K_{II}
I	380	790	52,0	105	0,3
II	630	1030	39	07	0,2
III					
Japan	600	1440	58	1,5	0,3
France	420	800	47	0,9	0,2
Italy	450	590	22	0,1	0,1

From the table, it is evident that, according to the crack initiation criterion, the pipes from Japan stand out (they exhibit a uniform sorbite-type structure, which is unusual for controlled-rolled pipes); satisfactory values are observed for first-generation pipes and pipes from France; Second-generation pipes (steel 14G2SAF) and pipes from Italy exhibit clearly poor performance indicators (which are critically important for evaluating durability forecasts by characterizing the initial stage of potential damage). At the subsequent stage of failure, the propensity for propagation of already formed cracks becomes significant. In this respect, pipes made from 14G2SAF steel (at that manufacturing stage) and pipes from Italy are evidently of inferior quality. This largely explains the increased incidence of premature failures in gas pipelines constructed from pipes supplied between 1970 and 1975.

Comparison of data obtained from the study of pipes of different generations is presented in Table 4.

Table 4 — Comparative data on failed pipes¹⁾

Generation	I	II	III
Sulfur and phosphorus content	Elevated	Slightly elevated	Elevated ²⁾
Hardness, MPa,	Approximately 1750 ³⁾	Approximately 2800 ⁴⁾	Approximately 2400 ⁵⁾
Highest score for non-metallic inclusions	4-5	3-4	1-2
Change in mechanical properties	No change	Significant increase in strength accompanied by a decrease in ductility	Decreased plasticity
Types of defects	Internal delamination	Internal cracks	Delaminations and internal cracks
Crack characteristics	Wide with blunt tip	Narrow with sharp, stepped tip	Wide and narrow

Notes: 1 Comparison of certificate data and research results.

2 Except for pipes supplied from Japan.

3 Value range: 1600-1900 MPa.

4 Value range: 1600-4150 MPa.

5 Value range: 1600-3200 MPa.

At present, pipe supplier plants have already implemented certain modifications in the manufacturing technology aimed at improving their quality. However, pipes supplied between 1970 and 1985 have only now begun to fail; thus, only recently has it become possible to evaluate their quality in terms of durability and to provide certain recommendations.

Among the studies focused on reducing the quantity and altering the morphology of non-metallic inclusions by modifying smelting technology, the work dedicated to the influence of calcium [8] is most pertinent. In this study, the authors demonstrated for pipe steel that sulfur content should not exceed 0,025%, and phosphorus — not more than 0,010%. The resulting globularization of sulfides and oxides, combined with calcium alloying, inhibits the formation of inclusions with unfavorable morphology at grain boundaries, which initiate intergranular fracture.

The evaluation of the mechanical properties of pipes manufactured from 17G1S steel demonstrated [9] that the standard strength and plasticity characteristics remain virtually unchanged over 25 and even 30 years. The reduction in crack initiation work is a specific parameter that requires further interpretation and investigation through additional studies employing more refined methodologies.

Conclusion

The results of the conducted research permit the formulation of certain recommendations aimed at improving the steel quality for pipes used in main gas pipelines. This primarily involves the optimization of the steel melting process to reduce the contents of oxygen, sulfur, and phosphorus, as well as to significantly lower the level of non-metallic inclusions to 1-2 points for all types. Furthermore, the electromagnetic stirring modes and billet cooling regimes during crystallization should be developed to minimize the segregation zone. The temperature regimes during the final rolling and normalization stages can be optimally coordinated to achieve a fine-grained, homogeneous structure. The quenching regimes (in terms of uniform cooling) and tempering regimes (with regard to temperature and necessary holding time) must be refined to obtain a uniformly homogeneous sorbite structure without areas of troostite and, especially, martensite, which contribute to increased strength and decreased plasticity.

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现代化联合收割机接收大豆种子经济效益指标的数学计算
**MATHEMATICAL CALCULATION OF ECONOMIC INDICATORS
OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF RECEIVING SOYBEAN SEEDS IN A
MODERNIZED COMBINE**

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摘要：本文基于经济评估，提出了一种比较测试原则，对现代化两段式脱粒联合收割机生产大豆种子的经济评价指标与用于大豆收获的同类联合收割机以及现有的优质种苗收获后加工技术进行了比较。通过对大豆收获技术与联合收割机直接生产种子进行比较经济评估，得出估计的经济效益：大豆收获季的经济效益为1275934.6卢布，其中包括节省的大豆种苗收获后加工运营成本75819.7卢布，以及本季优质豆粕带来的额外收入517736.9卢布，总计1275934.6卢布。联合收割机现代化改造的额外资本投资回收期为2.35个月。

关键词：大豆、种子、废料、清洁、参考、现代化联合收割机、收获后加工、经济效益。

Abstract. *Based on economic assessment proposed comparative principle of testing, where the indicators of economic evaluation of the production of soybean seeds in the modernized combine of two-phase threshing are evaluated in comparison with the produced analogue of the combine used in soybean harvesting and the existing technology of post-harvest processing of obtaining elite and reproductive seeds. As a result of the comparative economic assessment of soybean harvesting technology with the production of seeds directly in the combine, received estimated economic effect, which on soybean harvesting is 1275934.6 rubles for the season, including by saving operating costs for post-harvest processing of soybean seeds — 75819.7*

rubles, the additional income from the quality of bunker grain for the season is 517736.9 rubles, total — 1275934.6 rubles. The payback of additional capital investments in the modernization of the combine for total effects is 2.35 months.

Keywords: *soybeans, seeds, waste, cleaning, reference, modernized combine harvester, post-harvest processing, economic efficiency.*

1. Introduction

Obtaining soybean seeds with minimal crushing losses in a modernized two-phase threshing combine is due to the growing needs for effective and high-quality harvesting technologies with the production of soybean seeds. In the conditions of modern agriculture, where competition for resources and yield of cultivated crops is becoming more acute, it is necessary not only to increase productivity, but also to minimize crop losses. The great disadvantage of machines used in the harvesting and post-harvest processing of soybean seeds is the high degree of mechanical damage (fragmentation and microdamage) [1, 2]. The amount of mechanical damage to soybean grain during harvesting and moonlighting in some years is up to 30% [3, 4]. In order to develop more effective technology for obtaining quality seeds by a separate fraction in the combine harvester, mathematical calculations were carried out for the development of innovative technology of harvesting in crop production on the basis of selection achievements and means of mechanization [5, 6] in a single connection, ensuring the technological process, observing the agrotechnical requirements of harvesting, taking into account the physical and mechanical properties of the threshed soybean grain and the production of reproductive and commercial seeds [7, 8]. Particular attention is paid to the improvement of the technology for obtaining the first seed fraction and the choice of the mode of operation of the modernized combine harvester of two-phase threshing for obtaining the seed and commodity fraction [9, 10, 11].

2. Methods

The methodology for determining technical and economic efficiency provides for the use of the Interstate Standard GOST 34393-2018 Agricultural Technology. Methods of economic assessment during testing of agricultural machinery and GOST 24055 Agricultural technology. Methods of operational and technological assessment. The basis of the economic assessment of combine harvesters, for the production of marketable grain and subsequent post-harvest processing for the production of soybean seeds is the comparative principle of testing, that is, the indicators of the economic assessment of the modernized harvester on soybean harvesting with the production of a separate seed and product fraction at the same time [12, 13] comparison with the indicators of the basic version (analogue) of the harvester for soybean harvesting (PSM-154 “T-500”) and post-harvest work for obtaining seeds. For an analogue for comparison, the combine harvester of two drum RSM-154 T-500

used in soybean harvesting was adopted... Two drum systems threshing machine “T-500” is built with the use of drums with a diameter of 800 mm, has a flexible deck with electronic adjustment of gaps throughout and provides a stable threshing without loss [14]. A 750 mm diameter separator facilitates the movement of the soy mass along a smooth trajectory, intensively separating the soy grain. Unlike a serial combine harvester, an experienced modernized combine harvester of separate collection of seed and commodity soybean grain also consisting of a reaper, self-propelled two-drum thresher, a system of adapters of threshing and separating devices and cleaning of the combine, transportation and collection of seed and commodity fraction in separate bunkers provides the output of more than 60% of the most mature biologically full and high-quality soybean seeds with a low content of crushing and microdamage. Using them on sowing without subsequent post-harvest work significantly reduces damage and destruction of seeds and increases their yield.

Hammer-separating device threshing and cleaning combine two-phase threshing (Figure), consisting of receiving biter 1, grain elevators 2 and 3, feeding the seeds of the first and second fraction in the bunker of the combine, unloading screw 4, the first and second threshing drums with grating girders 5 and 6, domesticating device 7, straw shake 8, the second shaking board (groochet) 9, the first grating with extension 10 and a length of petals 70 mm, the second grating 11 with a length petals 22 mm, colossal auger 12 feeding the beans to the thresher, the second plank 13, the second grain auger 14, the first plank 15, the grill 16, the first grain auger 17, the fan 18, the first (main) rumble 19.

Figure. 1.— Device of the modernized combine harvester of two-phase threshing of separate production of seed and commodity fraction at soybean harvesting

The operation of the device is as follows: for cleaning the combine comes a pile consisting of four streams: the first — separated, through the grate of the first threshing drum 5, according to the main rumble 19, and moves to the beginning of the first half of the blind grill with an extension cord 10. The isolated grain with small particles of the pile goes to the first half of the second blind lattice 11, is separated and goes to the punctured grating 16 with oblong holes, where it is cleaned of weed and grain of crushed will seed. The purified grain rolls down the grating and enters the first grain auger 17, elevator 3 and is fed into the seed part of the bunker, and the sifting part of the crushed along the seed of the grain enters the first rolling board 15 in the second grain auger 14.

The second stream of dust coming from the second threshing drum with sub-drum 6 on the second shaking board (rumble) 9 and is fed to the second part of the first grille with extension cord 10. This second shaking board (thunder) is additionally supplied with a third grain pile from the domesticating device and a fourth pile isolated from the straw shaker... Grain with small particles of heap, isolated from large impurities in the second half of the upper grating 10 with lengthened to 70 mm petals of the blinds, enters the second half of the lower second grating with regular blinds 11, separates and enters the second sliding board 13, which enters the second grain auger 14. The collected grain received from the second half of the second blind grating 11 and the crushed grain allocated by the punch grating or Fadeev grating 16, in the grain auger 14 by the elevator 2 is fed into the second part of the commodity grain bunker and subsequently worked on the grain processing complex until the seeds are obtained.

The technical result of excretion of weed and soy halves and fine grain is achieved by the fact that in the developed design of the cleaning system, an additional sieve with oblong holes or a Fadeev sieve is installed on the first half of the grating mill and below the blind grilles, dividing the soy grain separated in the first half of the cleaning of the harvester into a whole, which descends into the first grain auger and is fed into a two-section bunker, and crushed along the seed (half) and fine grain, which, according to the first rolling board, arrive in the second grain auger grain fraction, and subject to post-harvest work. Dedicated soy halves have a certain price and are subject to sale for processing along with marketable grain. This design of the proposed improvement of the harvester cleaning system for harvesting the most mature seed grain, provides an increase in the germination and yield of soybean seeds, the improved quality of the seeds of the first fraction increases the yield of soybeans and during sowing reduces indirect seed losses.

The analysis of agrotechnical, operational and technological assessments and timekeeping observations on soybean harvesting by the serial combine harvester T-500 was carried out on the fields of Negruna LLC in the Ivanovo district of the Amur region in 2024. Calculation of indicators of economic evaluation is made in the prices of 2025: at the cost of combine harvester RSM-154 “T-500” equal to

22967680 rubles, reapers — 3945225 rubles and costs for the modernization of the combine harvester with the possibility of obtaining seed grain directly in the process of harvesting — 270050 rubles.

3. Results

The economic assessment was carried out by imposing the results of the experiment and testing of the modernized Yenisei 1200 combine harvester with the production of the seed and commodity fraction (60 and 40%) on the modernization of the RSM-154 T-500 combine harvester according to a similar technological scheme for grinding and obtaining soybean grain of the commodity fraction with subsequent post-harvest refinement to the seed. Indicators of efficiency were determined on cleaning based on seasonal work in hectares.

For comparison of the mock-up sample on the pilot site and the serial combine harvester on the basis of LLC “Negrin\’s Name” village Novoalekseevka 27.09.2024, timekeeping observations were made on the operational performance of the serial combine harvester (table 1).

Table 1. Performance of harvesters in soybean harvesting

Name of indicators	RSM-154 «T-500»	
	Upgraded	Series
1. Type of work	Cleaning of soy	Cleaning of soy
2. Agrotechnical term established in the zone, days	20.09-10.10	20.09-10.10
3. Culture, variety	Soya «Sentyabrinka»	Soya «Sentyabrinka»
4. Terms and conditions of work:		
working speed, km/h	6,25	6,25
width of capture, m — constructive	9,0	9,0
- working	8,55	8,55
average length of track, km	1	1
Yield, c/ha	28,55	28,55
The rate of change of time, ha	20,52	20,52
Specific fields consumption, gm, kg/ha	12,97	12,97
Composition of the unit — harvester	RSM-154 «T-500M»	RSM-154 «T-500»
Toad	Float Stream 900	Float Stream 900
Productivity of seed collection, I and II faction Wsm,		
— net time, ha/h	5,34	5,34
— technological time, those., ha/h		
— change of time, sm., ha/h	2,93	2,93
— operating time, ec. ga/h	2,78	2,78

Name of indicators	RSM-154 «T-500»	
	Upgraded	Series
I. Type of work	Cleaning of soy	Cleaning of soy
Specific fuel consumption, gm, kg/ha	12,97	12,97
Duration of unloading of seeds, min	3,66	3,66
Hammer, %		
I seed fractions, %	60	60
II seed fractions, %	40	40

The agrotechnical term for harvesting soybeans is — 21 calendar days. Conditions and mode of operation of the serial and experimental combine do not have a significant difference. Sort of soy Sentyabrinka, yield 28.55 c / ha, and the rate of operating time 20.52 hectares, specific fuel consumption 12.97 kg / ha. The economic inspection of the modernized combine harvester showed that at least 60% of seeds are allocated to the first seed fraction. their subsequent use Seeds without jobs. Soybean bunker grain of the serial and the second fraction of the modernized harvesters contain dead waste, frost-burning, sick and pest-eaten seeds, crushed and microdamaged seeds, which requires primary post-harvest processing, cleaning and calibration of grain on the seed-cleaning lines.

Taking into account the agrotechnical period established in the southern zone, the Amur region, the number of days with precipitation and the correction factor for weather conditions of 0.87, the calculation of seasonal production per combine harvester, amounting to 374.9 hectares, was made (table 2).

Table 2. Calculation of seasonal work on the harvester PCM-154 «T-500»

Name of indicators	Meanings
Agrotechnical term, days	21
Actual working days	18,27
Production rate, ha per shift	20,52
Weather factor	0,87
Seasonal work, ha	374,9

Optimization of the operating performance of the combine harvester and economic inspection of the modernized combine showed that at least 60% of the most complete soybean grain is allocated to the first seed fraction. This fraction contains 2.36-2.8% less crushed and microdamaged grain, the purity of the seeds is — 97.48%, which meets the requirements of GOST R 52325-2005 for soybean seed grain. Therefore, in order to preserve the quality of the grain and not to increase the crushing and microdamage of the grain, which additionally occurs when working

and receiving seeds according to the traditional technology of preparing soybean seeds, the first fraction of the grain is used as seeds on sowing without working.

Table 3. Calculation of the cost of reference cleaning and processing of soy bunker grain

Name of indicators	Series combine	Upgraded combine	
		1-st fraction	2-st fraction
Primary job, centner	28,55	17,13	11,42
Normative, rubles by 1 centner	32,75	0,00	32,75
Seed mode, 1 pass, centner	27,69	0,00	11,08
Normative, rubles by 1 centner	40,39	0,00	40,39
Seed mode, 2 pass, centner (packaging)	26,77	0,00	10,52
Normative, rubles by 1 centner	50,83	0,00	50,83
Primary cleaning costs, rubles/ha	935,0	0,0	374,0
Finalization costs — seed mode, first pass, rubles/ha	1118,4	0,0	447,5
Finalization costs — seed mode, second pass, rubles/ha	1360,8	0,0	534,8
Total cost of soybean seed processing rubles /ha	3414,2	0,0	1356,3

Thus, the use of the developed scientific direction and the corresponding adapters for obtaining the seed fraction in the harvester directly when harvesting soybeans shows the scientific and practical interest in the further development of this development in harvesters with a rotary threshing system. It is advisable to continue work on the development of a prototype harvester for obtaining seeds on the basis of a modern serial grain harvester with a two-phase threshing scheme, and to test its functionality in the conditions of the Amur region on other crops (grains, corn, rapeseeds, perennial herbs for seeds).

4. Conclusion

Thus, the developed scientific direction of obtaining the seed fraction in the harvester directly when harvesting soybeans shows the scientific and practical interest in the further development of this development in harvesters with a rotary threshing system. The estimated economic effect of evaluating an experienced modernized combine harvester on soybean harvesting is 1275934.6 rubles for the season, including by saving operating costs for post-harvest processing of soybean seeds — 75819.7 rubles, additional income from the quality of bunker grain for the season 517736.9 rubles., total — 1275934,6 rubles. The payback of additional capital investments in the modernization of the combine for total effects is 2.35 months. We think about the feasibility of this development of a prototype based on a modern serial soybean combine with a two-phase milling scheme, testing its

functionality on other crops in the Amur region: crops, corn, as well as rapeseeds and perennial herbs for seeds.

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具有改进特性的跟踪型模数转换器 (ADC)
**ANALOG-TO-DIGITAL CONVERTER (ADC) OF TRACKING TYPE
WITH IMPROVED CHARACTERISTICS**

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注释。跟踪型模数转换器 (ADC) 由比较器、由比较器控制的可逆计数器和数模转换器 (DAC) 组成。此类 ADC 的一个显著特点是其组成中包含一个可逆数字计数器。该器件能够持续监测输入信号的状态，并将其转换为数字代码。比较器将输入电压与 DAC 的输出电压进行比较，并控制可逆计数器的计数方向。

跟踪型 ADC 主要应用于电测量技术和自动控制跟踪系统。

尽管跟踪型 ADC 具有诸多优势，但由于其对输入信号大幅变化的响应速度较慢（动态误差较大），因此并未得到广泛应用。

本文探讨了在保持跟踪型 ADC 原有优势的同时，改进其性能的方法。

关键词：模数转换器 (ADC)、数模转换器 (DAC)、可逆数字计数器、时钟脉冲发生器 (GTI)、并行型ADC、跟踪型ADC、转换时间、转换误差、带滞后电压比较器、量化步长。

Annotation. *A tracking ADC consists of a comparator, a reversible counter controlled by the comparator, and a digital-to-analog converter (DAC). A characteristic feature of such an ADC is the presence of a reversible digital counter in its composition. This device allows continuous monitoring of the input signal's state, converting it into a digital code. The comparator compares the input voltage with the DAC's output voltage and controls the counting direction of the reversible counter.*

Tracking ADCs are mainly used in electrical measurement technology and in automatic control tracking systems.

Despite the advantages of tracking ADCs, they have not gained widespread use, mainly due to the slow response of the ADC to large changes in the input signal (large dynamic error).

This article discusses methods for improving the characteristics of tracking ADCs while preserving their positive properties.

Key words: An analog-to-digital converter (ADC), a digital-to-analog converter (DAC), reversible digital counter, a clock pulse generator (GTI), an ADC of the parallel type, an ADC of the tracking type, the time of conversion, the error of conversion, a voltage comparator with hysteresis, the quantization step.

1. Introduction

The electrical circuit of the model of the tracking type ADC is presented in Figure 1. The circuit is made in the EWB simulator, by it is possible to trace the operation of the ADC and observe the oscillograms at various points of the circuit. The circuit includes a voltage subtraction device A1, a two-threshold comparator (a “window” comparator), AR1, AR2, U1, R1...R4, a clock generator, V3, a reverse counter U3, a digital-to-analog converter, U4, reference voltage sources V1, V2, and a logic circuit U2 that passes pulses from the V3 generator to the CP count input of the reverse counter U3. The digital output of the ADC (N) is four-bit.

Figure 1 — Electrical diagram of a tracking-type ADC model

Figure 2 shows the results of the operation (tracking) of the ADC with a sinusoidal input voltage.

Figure 2 — Oscillograms of the ADC operation with a sinusoidal input signal

Figure 3 — ADC operation oscillograms with a rectangular input signal

U2 clock generator sets the frequency of the digital counter. The U3 parallel ADC generates the high-order bits of the output digital code. The U4 counter generates the low-order bits of the output digital code. This organization ensures the high speed of the entire ADC. The U6 counter setting pulse generator sets the high-order bit of the U4 counter to logical “1”. This ensures that the counter can operate in both subtraction and addition modes during the conversion process. Additionally, it provides for the correction of the parallel ADC’s zero offset.

Figure 5 — Oscillograms of the ADC operation with a sinusoidal input signal`

The converted voltage U_{in} comes to one input of the subtraction device A1. The other input of A1 is supplied with the analog voltage U_{dac} from the output of U5. This voltage is equivalent to the output digital signal of the whole device. At the output of A1, a signal is formed corresponding to the difference of these voltages. If the module of the difference of voltages is greater than half of the low-order bit, the counter U4 works either in the summing mode (for a positive difference) or in the subtracting mode (for a negative difference). If the module of the difference is less than half of the low-order bit, the counter U4 stops. The counter switching speed is set by the V3 clock generator. The outputs of the reversible digital counter are connected to the low-order bits of the U5 DAC. The outputs of the U3 parallel low-bit ADC are connected to the

high-order bits of the DAC. During the operation of the entire device, the digital code corresponding to U in is almost instantly established on the outputs of the U3 parallel ADC. This ensures the high speed of the proposed ADC. Further, with the arrival of each next clock pulse, the U4 reversible digital counter reduces the voltage difference U_{in} and U_{dac} . With small changes in U_{in} , the code at the output of the U3 ADC does not change. Tracking of U_{in} remains with the reversible digital counter

Thus, the considered ADC allows you to increase the speed and reduce the conversion time due to the use of an additional parallel ADC of a small bit-length and a pulse generator for setting the reversible digital counter.

Figure 5 shows the results of the operation (tracking) of the ADC with a sinusoidal input voltage. As can be seen from the oscillograms, there is no jitter at the ADC output (due to the presence of a window comparator in the circuit) and there is no tracking error during conversion.

Figure 6 shows the results of the operation (tracking) of the ADC with a rectangular input signal.

Figure 6 — ADC operation oscillograms with a rectangular input signal

The oscillogram in Figure 6 shows a significant decrease in ADC error when the input signal changes abruptly.

3. ADC conversion time

Let N_1 be the number of bits of a parallel ADC; N_2 be the number of bits of a reverse counter; T be the duration of one conversion cycle.

Then the conversion time of a parallel ADC will be:

$$t_1 = T$$

The conversion time of a tracking-type ADC:

$$t_2 = (2^{N_2} - 1) \times T.$$

The total conversion time:

$$t_{\Sigma} = 2^{N_2} \times T.$$

This time is significantly less than the conversion time that would be for a conventional tracking type ADC:

$$t_0 = (2^{(N_1+N_2)} - 1) \times T.$$

The input voltage is applied simultaneously to the parallel ADC (four-bit) and the tracking type ADC. The output data is taken from the reverse counter (low-order bits) and the parallel ADC (high-order bits). For our case, we have:

$$t_{\Sigma} = 2^{N_2} \times T = 2^4 \times T = 16 \times T,$$

$$t_0 = (2^{(N_1+N_2)} - 1) \times T = (2^8 - 1) \times T = 255 \times T.$$

Ratio:

$$t_0/t_{\Sigma} = 255/16 \approx 16.$$

Thus, the conversion time is reduced by a factor of 2^{N_1} when switching to the proposed ADC scheme (in the example, by a factor of 16).

4. Main conclusions

1. The main disadvantage of the tracking type ADC is the large dynamic error in case of sharp changes in the input signal. At the same time, its tracking properties are violated, that is, the main advantage of this ADC (tracking property) over other types of ADCs will be lost.

2. Improvement of characteristics is achieved by introducing into the scheme of an auxiliary parallel converter of small bit-length, which works out sharp large changes in the input signal, thus leaving for the ADC's reversible digital counter only the function of tracking the input signal.

3. The conversion time is also significantly reduced. It becomes equal to the conversion time of the remaining reduced tracking part of the entire ADC.

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评估受害者身份特征造成的信息风险：识别和预防方法
**ASSESSMENT OF INFORMATION RISKS CAUSED BY
THE FEATURES OF VICTIM IDENTITY: METHODS OF
IDENTIFICATION AND PREVENTION**

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摘要：本文探讨了与受害者身份特征相关的信息风险，这些特征决定了受害者更容易成为社会工程攻击的目标。文章对影响受害者易受操纵性的关键心理因素进行了全面分析，并识别出不同类型的威胁应对方式。文章提出了一种基于对受害者身份进行主动诊断的社会工程预防模型，该模型有助于增强受害者的心理韧性，并降低与人为因素相关的风险。文章强调了全面发展信息安全技能的重要性，以及进一步研究网络安全心理学方面的必要性。

关键词：信息风险，受害者身份，网络受害，信息安全，社会工程，防范社会工程威胁

Abstract. *The article addresses information risks related to characteristics of victim identity that determine susceptibility to becoming the target of social engineering attacks. A comprehensive analysis of key psychological factors affecting vulnerability to manipulation was conducted, and distinct types of threat responses were identified. A preventive model for protection against social engineering, based on proactive diagnostics of victim identity, is proposed, enabling the formation of psychological resilience and reducing risks related to the human factor. The importance of a comprehensive approach to the development of information security skills and the necessity for further research in the psychological aspects of cybersecurity is emphasized.*

Keywords: *information risks, victim identity, cyber-victimhood, information security, social engineering, protection against social engineering threats*

In the context of the proliferation of information technologies, issues related to ensuring information security are becoming increasingly pertinent. In addition to traditional threats associated with technical vulnerabilities, risks arising from the human factor are acquiring growing importance. Among these, particular significance is attributed to information risks associated with the traits of victim identity — that is, the predisposition of certain individuals to becoming victims of cybercrime, fraud, manipulation, and other forms of informational influence. Victim identity is formed under the influence of a complex of psychological, social, and informational factors, determining the specifics of threat perception, the level of critical assessment of incoming information, and the propensity for risky behavior in the digital environment. Insufficient understanding of the mechanisms underlying the formation and manifestation of such identity hinders the development of effective methods for prevention and mitigation of the associated risks.

The aim of this article is a comprehensive assessment of information risks driven by features of victim identity, as well as the development of a preventive model for protection against social engineering.

Information risks are the probability of occurrence of undesirable events associated with the use of information technologies that may result in damage to an organization, its assets, reputation, or individuals. These risks manifest during the creation, transmission, storage, and processing of information through electronic media and communication means. In a broader context, information risks refer to the threat of compromise to the properties of information — its confidentiality, integrity, or availability — due to the realization of threats connected with human factors, technical failures, or external attacks.

At the social level, with the advancement of information and communication technologies, human interaction within the digital space is becoming increasingly natural, as information and technical tools substantially enhance human comfort and convenience. With the advent of virtual capabilities, traditional forms of interpersonal communication have transformed, as interaction migrates to social networks and messaging platforms; its interactive, communicative, and perceptual dimensions experience fundamental changes. For instance, facial expressions and pantomime may be replaced by emojis, while the natural interpersonal evaluation of personality is altered. Moreover, the comprehension of information frequently shifts from a dialogical co-construction of shared meaning to a unilateral process, in which the coding and decoding system becomes disconnected. All these factors influence the general structure of human communication as well as one's perception of personal security in the surrounding environment; these changes have also affected the realization of

a person’s victim potential, specifically their ability to become a victim within the digital realm. Accordingly, the issues of establishing and enhancing psychological security in individuals, as well as identifying the primary factors and determinants that exert positive and negative effects on it, are brought to the forefront.

The concept of victimhood is equally applicable to the cyberspace sphere; however, it must be emphasized that the process of virtual victimization is more complex and multifactorial. D. V. Zhmurow defines cyber-victimhood as ‘the capacity of an individual to become a victim of computer crimes due to subjective or objective vulnerability.’ He argues that the 21st century is characterized by the emergence of the virtual victim personality as a new formative type of victimization. The ‘new victimological discourse’ differs from the classical model. The notion that the perpetrator and the victim possess psychological correspondence and that victims are selected by the perpetrator based on specific criteria is now refuted; victim selection is often randomized. Furthermore, atypical cases of victim communities have emerged, such as hype projects involving thousands of participants [1] [2].

Cyber-victimhood, as a phenomenon, encompasses a wide range of situations in which individuals become victims of cybercrimes [3]. One of the effective techniques of cybercrime is social engineering.

Social engineering is a non-technical compromise of personal data through manipulations based either on establishing trust between the attacker and the victim or on the attacker exerting total pressure on the victim.

We conducted a study of the victim identity profile of students, analyzed their responses to simulated social engineering attacks, and proposed preventive measures for protection. The study included 31 participants — students from the 2nd to 4th years at Irkutsk National Research Technical University.

Fig. 1. Victim identity profile

Victimization (predisposition to become a victim) is a complex psychological construct expressed through a set of stable behavioral and cognitive patterns.

The psychological security parameter includes four principal components: moral-communicative — moral sensitivity (the capacity to comprehend the interdependence of actions), motivation, critical thinking, character, flexibility in applying communicative norms, and the ability to cooperate constructively; moral-volitional — an indicator of resilience, defined as the capacity to withstand stress and overcome difficulties; value-semantic — the formation of attitudes and life credo, as well as the relationship to the vulnerable triad in the digital environment: ‘curiosity — fear — greed’; internal comfort — self-esteem, confidence in one’s own abilities, and a critical attitude towards ongoing events.

Parameter of personality traits: sociability implies a broad range of communicativeness and the ability to maintain appropriate boundaries in any interaction. Equanimity and emotional stability enable self-regulation, preventing excessive emotions that impede critical thinking. Independence — a sense of personal strength and the ability to make decisions autonomously, including under time constraints. Anxiety as intolerance to uncertainty, characterized by the anticipation of negative events. Aggression — a high level of irritability and destructive feelings directed both at others and oneself. Hostility is an oppositional behavioral pattern, encompassing suspicion, feelings of resentment, and guilt.

The cognitive style parameter refers to the ways of processing information that enable evaluation and decision-making. The manipulator distracts the victim’s attention by engaging them in an emotional vortex (curiosity, fear, greed). Low awareness prevents an individual from taking a ‘step back’ to objectively assess the situation and detect inconsistencies; they fail to recognize that they are being systematically guided along a predetermined scenario.

An individual with a help-dependent style may face difficulties in complex situations and in discerning details; they exhibit sensitivity to social norms, which influences specific decision-making, demonstrate a tendency toward cooperation, require advice and assistance from others, and may possess unstable self-esteem.

Individuals with a field-independent cognitive style are able to focus on details, seldom require consultation, and are confident in themselves and their own convictions [4].

It was concluded that the selected parameters for the victim identity profile would enable the analysis of the victim identity of respondents participating in the study; accordingly, the following psychodiagnostic instruments were selected:

“Diagnostics of Personal Psychological Safety” (I. I. Prikhodko), “Embedded Figures Test” (ACT-70 K. U. Etrich), “Victim Identity Scale” (O. O. Andronnikova), “Aggression and Hostility Index” (Buss-Durkee), 16-factor Personality Questionnaire by R. B. Cattell (Form A) (scales of introversion — extroversion,

emotional instability — emotional stability, calmness — anxiety, sensitivity — equanimity, and conformity — independence)^{1, 2, 3, 4, 5}

Victim identity (in points) was also assessed. The majority of respondents exhibit low to medium levels of victim identity. The mean level demonstrates varying degrees of predisposition to becoming crime victims; 6 out of 15 participants displayed borderline scores closer to the high range of 16-18 points, whereas the high range is defined as 19-24 points.

Fig. 2. Correlation matrix of the victim identity profile

Thus, subjects displaying traits of victimization are characterized by dependent behavior, a sense of powerlessness, defenselessness, and helplessness, emotional instability, and a tendency to perceive themselves as victims of circumstance while viewing the surrounding world as uncomfortable and unjust.

Psychological safety and a field-independent cognitive perception style exhibit a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.72$, $p \leq 0.001$) and are associated with equilibrium and emotional stability.

We have concluded that these psychological personality traits contribute to enhanced individual resilience to both external and internal influences, facilitating effective functioning even amid internal and external threats, through inherent psychological resources, high psychological resilience, and nervous system stability.

¹ <https://psytests.org/stress/dpbl-run.html>

² <https://psytests.org/cogn/efl.html>

³ <https://psytests.org/ipl/andvid.html>

⁴ <https://psytests.org/conf/bdhi-run.html>

⁵ <https://psytests.org/multi/cat16pfA.html>

Our study did not reveal any correlational interactions with the parameters of ‘sociability’ and ‘aggressiveness.’

Thus, we constructed profiles of the victim identity of the subjects and identified that susceptibility to cyber-victimization may be determined by personality traits such as anxiety, emotional instability, and a field-dependent cognitive style of perception. Conversely, balance, emotional stability, personal maturity, a field-independent cognitive style of perception, orientation toward personal experience, reliance on knowledge, a meaningful social environment, and successful interpersonal interaction contribute to mitigating an individual’s susceptibility to cyber-victimization. Consequently, it ensures the psychological security of the individual, resilience, consistency in a specific type of behavior, and engagement in digital environments.

Fig. 3. Types of reactions to social engineering attacks based on the victim identity profile

Upon analyzing the obtained results, we conditionally classified the reaction types as appropriate and inappropriate. Within the inappropriate reaction type based on the victim identity profile, the following subtypes were distinguished: sensitive (excessively sensitive), anxious (insecurity, fears), apathetic (helplessness, reluctance to assume responsibility for occurring events), and hostile (resentment, perception of injustice). Under simulated social engineering attack conditions, 35% of the subjects exhibited inadequate types of reactions. This group comprised all subjects with a high level of victim identity and some subjects with a medium level of victim identity.

It was concluded that, overall, students have not yet developed a stable and adequate type of reaction to social engineering attacks that could reliably protect against social engineering techniques. This reflects the insufficient development of psychological and cognitive mechanisms in the subjects, which are necessary for recognizing and counteracting the psychological influence exerted by attackers.

Given the presence of various response types to social engineering attacks, the development of preventive measures [5] aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of protection against social engineering is deemed necessary.

Fig. 4. Preventive model for social engineering protection

A pretext often forms the basis of social engineering. A pretext constitutes a tool that creates an illusion of legitimacy and trust, significantly increasing the effectiveness of social engineering. It exploits human psychological vulnerabilities such as trust, fear, and the desire to help [6].

Pretexting in social engineering is a primary method of user manipulation, which through deception and manipulation causes violation and ultimately leads to the voluntary disclosure of confidential information [6].

Attacks of this kind often serve as a pivotal point for more extensive crimes, such as account compromise, malware dissemination, various financial fraud schemes, and data theft [7].

To effectively counter pretexting, it is necessary not only to enhance critical thinking but also to develop the ability to detect manipulative tactics through both technical methods and personalized approaches based on the victim identity profile; this is particularly important for information security specialists [8].

The study, focused on analyzing the victim identity of students, identified key factors that determine their susceptibility to social engineering attacks.

Victim identity profile and responses to threats. A victim identity profile of students was established, on the basis of which types of responses to social engineering attacks were identified — adequate and inadequate. It has been established that psychological characteristics such as heightened anxiety, excessive sensitivity, apathy, and inappropriate hostility significantly increase the risk of becoming a victim of manipulation. The developed profile enables systematic assessment of learners' susceptibility levels, identification of risk groups, and the development of targeted preventive programs.

A model is proposed that provides for a transition from a mass to an individualized approach in counteracting social engineering. The integration of proactive diagnostics of the victim's identity ensures the targeted development of psychological resilience among students and staff.

The obtained results underscore the significance of a comprehensive formation of students' psychological resilience to social engineering threats and establish the necessity for further research into the psychological aspects of cybersecurity.

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生物识别安全：便利性与隐私性
BIOMETRIC SECURITY: CONVENIENCE VS PRIVACY

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摘要：本文探讨了生物识别技术的双重特性，以及沉浸式系统（虚拟现实/增强现实）在现代安全和犯罪调查方法中的应用。文章分析了数字化技术如何改变了犯罪现场和犯罪嫌疑人的识别方式。生物识别系统显著提高了数据的准确性和速度，而其他技术则为数据收集开辟了新的可能性，并对隐私概念提出了挑战。本研究分析了人工智能、区块链和增强现实技术作为工具的应用，旨在帮助在透明的数字司法体系中，在便利性和基本隐私权之间取得平衡。

关键词：数字技术、生物识别安全、隐私、调查行动、人工智能、区块链、虚拟现实、增强现实、网络安全、数据保护

Abstract. *The article examines the dual nature of biometric technologies and the integration of immersive systems (VR/AR) into the context of modern security and crime investigation methods. It explores how the transition to digital technologies has changed the way crime scenes and perpetrators are identified. Biometric systems significantly enhance data accuracy and speed, while additional technologies open up new possibilities for data collection, challenging the notion of privacy. The study analyzes the use of artificial intelligence, blockchain, and augmented reality technologies as tools that can help strike a balance between convenience and the fundamental right to privacy within a transparent digital justice system.*

Keywords: *digital technologies, biometric security, privacy, investigative actions, artificial intelligence, blockchain, virtual reality, augmented reality, cybersecurity, data protection.*

Introduction

In the modern era, investigative and security methods have undergone fundamental changes, with physical media such as paper documents and physical

evidence being replaced by digital forms such as electronic correspondence, surveillance camera data, and biometric profiles. The use of digital protocols instead of paper media has significantly accelerated the flow of information and improved the accuracy of data. As a result, digital biometric identification has become the primary tool for collecting personal information. However, with this progress comes the concern that the security of digital life is being compromised. In today's world, no one is immune to surveillance or hacking, and no one can guarantee their complete privacy.

Operational Efficiency and Biometric Modalities

The use of biometric technologies such as facial, fingerprint, voice, and DNA recognition greatly simplifies the process of identifying suspects, victims, and witnesses. Modern software makes it possible to identify suspects with great accuracy, which allows investigators to significantly simplify their work and data collection.

For example, the use of facial recognition systems such as the FindFace SDK has become extremely important for operational detention. In 2017, in Qingdao (China), the police detained 25 wanted criminals using such systems. In Russia, during the FIFA World Cup, this technology made it easy to catch 180 offenders. These examples clearly show us that biometric identification simplifies and automates processes that used to take a lot of time. However, with this simplification comes the realization that it is becoming more difficult to maintain anonymity in today's society, as there is a growing consensus that our society is completely "transparent."

The Role of Virtual and Augmented Reality (VR/AR)

The introduction of virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies opens up new horizons for forensics and security systems, but also poses additional risks to privacy. Virtual reality technologies allow for the reconstruction of virtual crime scenes for investigative experiments. This enables witnesses and jurors to "visit" the crime scene from the comfort of a courtroom, enhancing the clarity and accuracy of their perception. Augmented reality technologies enable the overlay of biometric data on a person's visual image. This can be used to identify the faces of wanted criminals. The main problem is that these devices collect "kinematic biometrics" — unique patterns of head, eye, and gait movements that allow for identification even when the face is hidden. This is yet another confirmation that anonymity and privacy are nearly impossible to maintain.

¹ Konakova L. Yu. Foreign experience in the development of facial recognition technology in ensuring public safety // Law and Management. No. 1. 2023. p. 179.

Data Analysis and Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning have become increasingly important in modern investigative and security processes. AI can effectively analyze large amounts of data, including biometric patterns, phone calls, and online activity. AI technologies are also used to make predictions based on the provided data. This is a useful tool for criminal investigations, such as predicting the location or likelihood of a crime. However, it poses a significant risk in everyday life, as it can lead to surveillance based on algorithms and probabilities rather than actual actions.

Cybersecurity and Blockchain Protection

One of the key challenges in using digital and biometric technologies is ensuring cybersecurity. Digital evidence and biometric profiles can be easily modified or destroyed without proper protection measures. A promising approach is to use blockchain technology to prevent unauthorized access. Blockchain, in the context of information security, is a distributed database where information is recorded in blocks that are linked together and protected by cryptography. Blockchain allows for the recording of every action performed on digital data (access, copying, or transfer), making it easier to track any changes. This can guarantee the immutability of digital evidence from the moment it is received until it is presented in court. Decentralized storage of files instead of the images themselves allows for better protection of an individual's privacy in the event of a leak from centralized databases.

Legal Regulation and International Cooperation

Legal regulation of digital technologies is necessary to ensure the legality of their use. For example, in Russia, laws have been in place since 2019 that allow the use of video recordings as evidence in court. However, due to the controversial nature of digital data storage between countries, international cooperation and consensus are required. To address the challenges associated with the protection of personal data, harmonization of legal norms across different countries is necessary. Countries must coordinate their actions to ensure that biometric data transferred across borders is not used to violate individual rights.

Conclusion

The use of digital and biometric technologies plays a key role in ensuring the effectiveness of modern security systems. These technologies allow for the acceleration of evidence collection, enhance its reliability, and provide better protection

¹ Bailenson J. N. Protecting Nonverbal Data for the Virtual Reality Era // JAMA Network Open. 2020. Vol. 3(8).

² Gulyaev A. P. Digital technologies in the activities of the investigator // Russian Investigator. 2021. No. 5. pp. 12-15.

for society. However, this process also requires constant attention to emerging challenges. I also believe that the use of advanced technologies automates routine processes and helps individuals analyze large amounts of data in a short amount of time through biometrics and digital forecasting, but if it falls into the wrong hands, it can cause harm. Only by combining reliable technical security measures, such as blockchain, with a comprehensive legal framework, can society benefit from biometrics without compromising the fundamental right to privacy.

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¹ Shakhnazarov B. A. Complex interrelation of blockchain technology and intellectual property objects in cross-border private law relations // Right. Journal of the Higher School of Economics. 2019. No. 5. p. 123.

² Pastukhov P. S. On the development of criminal procedural proof in the context of digitalization // Bulletin of Perm University. Juridical Sciences. 2019. No. 46. pp. 732-755.

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创新型传动工业机器人机械臂的概念
CONCEPT OF AN INNOVATIVE TRANSMISSION INDUSTRIAL
ROBOT MANIPULATOR

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摘要：本文提出了一种采用集中式传动驱动系统的国产工业机器人机械臂的概念。该技术方案采用单台高扭矩电机和中央传动轴。文中分析了该方案相对于传统设计的优势，并评估了其技术参数和应用领域。此外，还论证了旨在实现技术自主性的研发理念。

关键词：机器人，机械臂，传动，自动化，进口替代，驱动，控制。

Abstract: *The article presents the concept of a domestic industrial robot manipulator with a centralized transmission drive system. A technical solution featuring a single high-torque motor and a central distribution shaft is proposed. An analysis of advantages compared to traditional designs was performed, and the technical parameters and application areas were evaluated. The rationale for development aimed at ensuring technological independence was substantiated.*

Keywords: *robot, manipulator, transmission, automation, import substitution, drive, control.*

Introduction

Modern industrial production is characterized by a high degree of automation in technological processes. One of the key tools for enhancing production efficiency is industrial robot manipulators capable of performing a wide range of

operations: from welding and assembly of products to material processing and parts transportation. According to data from the International Federation of Robotics, over the past 10 years, the number of industrial robots has doubled, reflecting the growing demand for robotic systems [2].

Despite the acceleration in robot production, the industry continues to face shortages of critically important components:

- servomotors;
- harmonic drives;
- control systems;
- high-precision bearings;
- specialized software.

Sanction-related restrictions in recent years have significantly complicated the supply of high-precision harmonic drives and high-power servomotors from leading global manufacturers (Harmonic Drive, Nabtesco, Yaskawa). Concurrently, logistical barriers affecting component deliveries from China remain substantial: even downtime lasting only a few days poses an unacceptable risk for industrial enterprises. Under these conditions, the principle of ‘domestic — faster and more reliable’ becomes fundamental for the market [3]. Accordingly, today industrial robots are approximately 80% localized, but the objective is to achieve complete independence.

Furthermore, traditional designs of industrial robots have several structural limitations. In most existing models, each joint of the manipulator is equipped with an individual stepper motor or servo drive. This architecture increases the mass of the moving links and results in higher inertial loads on the mechanical components of the system. Consequently, the operating speed decreases, positioning accuracy deteriorates, and the robots’ energy consumption rises.

Amid the development of domestic industry and the imperative to secure technological independence, the development of new robotic solutions based on alternative kinematic schemes and advanced control systems acquires particular significance. This development of a transmission-based robot manipulator complies with item 26, ‘Technologies for the creation of domestic means of production and scientific instrumentation,’ from the List of the most important high-tech technologies of the Decree of the President of the Russian Federation dated 18.06.2024 No. 529 [1].

The development and application of industrial robots are addressed in the works of many domestic and foreign researchers. The fundamentals of robotics are outlined in the works of E.I. Yurevich, where the principles of constructing manipulator kinematic schemes and robot control systems are examined [4].

The research by T.A. Akimenko and T.R. Kuznetsova focuses on the system-level design of robotic systems and the stages of industrial robot development [6]. These studies highlight that the efficiency of robotic systems largely depends

on the optimal distribution of the mass of their drive mechanisms. The creation of an industrial robot is a complex engineering and scientific challenge involving the selection of its structure, as well as the definition and optimization of its primary parameters, and mechanical and dynamic characteristics.

O.D. Egorov, in the textbook «Design of Robot Mechanisms», thoroughly describes the stages of industrial robot design, including the technical specification, preliminary design, technical design, and working documentation [5]. At the first stage of design, the overall layout of the manipulator is selected, and the sequence of arrangement of degrees of freedom is determined.

Currently, there exist robots in which stepper motors are located within the joint assemblies. Such designs remain bulky and inefficient, resulting in an increased moment of inertia of the robot during operation. This fails to satisfy user requirements and restricts scalability, thereby creating design challenges ranging from industrial manipulators to compact cobots.

The considered analogs include the Russian robot Promobot M13 (payload 13 kg, 6 axes, working radius 1300 mm, price 4.16 million rubles) and the robot from the international company KUKA LBR iiwa (payload 14 kg, 7 axes, working radius 800 mm, price starting from 5.0 million rubles). An analysis of the characteristics of existing robot manipulator designs is provided in (Table 1). However, a comprehensive analysis of the concept of a transmission robot featuring a central distribution shaft and a single servodrive under domestic manufacturing conditions is inadequately represented in the scientific literature.

The objective of this study is to develop a concept for an industrial robot manipulator with a centralized transmission drive system and to analyze the prospects for its application in various engineering systems.

To achieve the stated objective, it is necessary to address the following tasks:

- to conduct an analysis of existing industrial robot designs;
- to develop an alternative kinematic scheme for a transmission robot manipulator;
- to consider the potential applications of robotic manipulators in various industrial sectors;
- to develop a technical assignment project for experimental design work.

Within the framework of the study, an analysis of the parameters of existing robot designs was carried out, and a concept of a robotic system comprising a manipulator, a central distribution shaft, and a servodrive was proposed.

Unlike traditional designs, in which each robot joint is equipped with a separate motor, the proposed concept employs a single high-torque servomotor located at the robot base.

Torque transmission is performed via a central distribution shaft that ensures rotation and transfers energy to the mechatronic power take-off modules. Power

take-off from the transmission for the rotational and linear movements of the robot manipulator is executed through kinematic modules, as shown in the diagram of the transmission-based robot manipulator (Fig. 1).

Table 1. Analysis of the Characteristics of Existing Robot Manipulator Designs

No.	Name / Characteristics	Conceptual Robot Manipulator	Promobot M13	International Company KUKA LBR iiwa
1	Payload, kg	120	13	14
2	Number of Controlled Axes	7	6	7
3	Maximum Reach, mm	1500	1300	800
4	Price, million rubles *including a 50% discount from Ministry of Industry and Trade of Russia	1.8	4.16 2.08*	from 5.0

Fig. 1. Diagram of the transmission-based robot manipulator

The use of such an architecture, according to preliminary calculations, enables the following advantages:

- reduction of the mass of moving elements by 35–40%;

- reduction of inertial loads by 30–35%;
- simplification of the robot’s design;
- scalability from large industrial manipulators to compact cobots;
- reduction of robot manufacturing costs by 35–45%.

Based on the conducted studies, the main technical parameters of the industrial robot manipulator are defined and presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Technical parameters of the industrial robot manipulator

Parameter	Value
Payload	100-120 kg
Number of Controlled Axes	7
Maximum reach	1400-1500 mm
Positioning accuracy	±0.05 mm
Repeatability	±0.02 mm
Movement speed	up to 1.2 m/s
Power consumption	4.5-5.5 kW
Service life	60,000 hours

The manipulator’s seven degrees of freedom enable operation in confined spaces and execution of high-precision tasks with minimal deviations. The robot is capable of automatic tool replacement, facilitating optimization of the production process and reduction of equipment setup time.

The robot control system comprises a central controller, position sensors, localized drive control modules based on solenoids, and software for motion trajectory planning. Modern control algorithms enable solving tasks of direct and inverse kinematics, as well as ensure high positioning accuracy of the robot manipulator.

The control system coordinates the operation of all manipulator components – its sensors, actuator, kinematic modules, and other elements, ensuring their synchronous and coherent operation.

Industrial robot manipulators can be used in various industrial sectors. The most common application areas are presented in (Table 3) with an indication of the resulting effect of their use.

The robot manipulator is capable of performing machining operations on multifunctional machines, loading and unloading workpieces, changing tools, and measuring parts during processing. The design’s flexibility allows handling parts of various sizes and configurations.

The robot’s implementation allows automating routine and labor-intensive operations, significantly reducing labor costs. High operational accuracy minimizes defects, thereby reducing expenses related to reprocessing and product returns.

Table 3. Use of industrial robot manipulators across industry sectors

Industry	Application	Effect
Automotive industry	Assembly and welding, painting	Precise assembly, operation under challenging conditions
Metalworking	Milling and turning operations	High operational accuracy
Logistics and warehousing	Material handling and packaging	Increased logistics efficiency
Medical equipment	Assembly and testing	High precision for complex devices
Construction	Installation operations	Improving efficiency and safety
Tunnel construction	Hydroabrasive cutting of enclosing rocks and extraction of blocks from the rock massif	Enhancing efficiency, safety, and accuracy of operations
Mining industry	Working in hazardous conditions	Improving labor safety

The robot can operate continuously without breaks, increasing production volume and enabling enterprises to respond promptly to demand fluctuations.

Conclusions

The conducted research demonstrated that traditional industrial robot designs have several limitations related to the use of distributed drive systems. The placement of stepper motors or servomotors in joint assemblies increases the moment of inertia and decreases operational efficiency.

The analysis of application areas demonstrated that robotic manipulators can be effectively utilized in the automotive industry, metal processing, logistics, medical equipment, construction, tunneling, and mining sectors.

The proposed concept of a robot manipulator with a centralized transmission drive system enables a reduction in the mass of moving components by 35–40%, decreases inertial loads, and enhances the performance efficiency of robotic systems. The use of a single high-torque servo drive with a central distribution shaft provides a stable power flow to the kinematic modules. Based on the obtained results, the assignment for the experimental design development has been formulated.

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计算机模拟矿物尺寸破碎过程中可控裂纹形成的新方法
**COMPUTER MODELING OF A NEW METHOD
FOR CONTROLLED CRACK FORMATION DURING
DIMENSIONAL COMMINATION OF MINERALS**

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摘要。破碎的天然矿物和合成脆性材料广泛应用于采矿、化工、制药、食品、化妆品和电子等各个工业领域。尺寸破碎能够生产出更均匀分散的加工产品，从而提高所得材料的力学性能、质量和竞争力。这显著降低了材料废料的处理成本，进而降低了再生原料的生产成本。本研究旨在验证所提出的脆性材料可控断裂方法[俄罗斯联邦专利号：2732619]，并随后进行断裂过程的计算机建模，以评估工具运动学对裂纹形成模式的影响。

关键词：岩石，脆性材料，脆性断裂，可控裂纹形成，尺寸破碎，计算机建模。

Abstract. *Crushed natural minerals and synthesized brittle materials are widely used across various industrial sectors, including mining, chemical, pharmaceutical, food, cosmetic, and electronic industries. Dimensional comminution allows for the production of more homogeneous dispersed processing products, thereby enhancing the mechanical properties, quality, and competitiveness of the resulting materials. This significantly reduces the costs associated with processing material waste and, consequently, the production of products from secondary raw materials. The aim of this work is to substantiate the proposed method of controlled fracture of brittle materials [Patent of the Russian Federation No. 2732619] and to subsequently perform computer modeling of the fracture process to evaluate the influence of tool kinematics on the pattern of crack formation.*

Keywords: *rocks, brittle materials, brittle fracture, controlled crack formation, dimensional comminution, computer modeling.*

Introduction

The study of the energy and technological capabilities of controlled brittle fracture of rocks within the technological processes of their extraction and primary processing holds a special and important place in geotechnical science and the mining industry [1]. Dimensional comminution is a specific operation in ore processing that involves crushing natural minerals and other brittle materials to a predetermined size for their subsequent application in technological processes, such as the production of construction materials, glass, ceramics, electronics, and other products [2,3]. At present, dimensional comminution in industry is typically performed in stages using different methods, followed by screening. Each method has its advantages and limitations, and the choice of method depends on the material type, degree of comminution, and the required particle size [2]. It should be noted that insufficient comminution and excessive comminution can cause inhomogeneity of the final product and a reduction in its quality, as well as increased costs for the production of secondary materials. Therefore, controlled dimensional comminution is in high demand in industrial applications.

Main part

In classical theories of plasticity and fracture of brittle media, isotropy and homogeneity are assumed. However, under high mechanical stresses, the structural elements of minerals in polycrystals develop a texture characterized by clearly defined principal directions of plastic deformation instead of random orientation. This is the principal factor that manifests the anisotropy of physico-mechanical properties beyond the elastic limit. Since, especially for such rocks, there exists a complex triaxial stress state, fracture during size reduction may occur either along bedding planes, which are effectively planes of weakness, or along planes where the combination of stresses reaches a critical value according to the Coulomb-Mohr criterion, with cohesion and internal friction angle characteristic of the mineral as a whole. The anisotropic structure of the medium can be transverse or orthotropic, each exhibiting characteristic topological patterns of stress tensors. Therefore, for each type of medium texture during dispersion, its own specific competing destruction mechanism is preferable. Since anisotropic materials do not exhibit predictability in the formation of a ‘crack network,’ controlling the size of dispersed particles using conventional dispersion methods is not feasible. In an actual solid body, there always exists a system of spatial micro- and macro-defects distributed throughout the bulk of the body and partially exposed on its surface. Such defects possess high mobility and are capable of coagulation and annihilation due to the thermal motion of molecules and mechanical stresses. Consequently, the deformation process of the body consists in the increase of the size and number of macro- and micro-defects. Upon reaching a certain density of such defects within the body, a crack arises with dimensions

exceeding the critical ones. Further crack growth proceeds spontaneously until the body fractures. When the external load decreases, cracks within the bulk material close, and the energy of the annihilated surfaces is converted into heat. This process is imperfect because cracks within the bulk material do not fully close. Therefore, under cyclic loading, with each successive cycle, the number of defects in the material increases, and the material's strength decreases due to fatigue. Thus, if the material is supplied with energy exceeding the critical energy of elastic deformation, it will fracture, forming a new surface whose area is proportional to the overstress energy.

The work required for new surface formation is useful, whereas the work of elastic deformations represents dissipative losses. Therefore, the efficiency coefficient (η) of the comminution process can be increased by enhancing the overstress, for example, through a high-speed impact. At very short durations, microdefects do not have time to migrate to the region of major cracks, resulting in increased strength of the brittle body (the dynamic strengthening effect). Since the strength of the body depends on its overall dimensions, it increases with their reduction and is determined by the decrease in the maximum crack length. In other words, if a brittle body is subjected to a forced periodic load Q with a small amplitude and sufficiently high frequency (Figure 1a), it will not be completely fractured, but small fragments with sizes $K = 1/2, 1/4$, and so forth, relative to the bulk of the broken body, will detach. Conversely, if a periodic impact load Q_1 with a large amplitude but low frequency is applied to the same body (Figure 1b), it will fracture into only a few large pieces with sizes $K = 1$.

Fig. 1 — Crack formation scheme: a) under high-frequency excitation with small amplitude; b) under low-frequency excitation with large amplitude; c) under combined low- and high-frequency oscillations

Thus, at low frequency and large amplitude, the crack penetration depth will be greater than at high frequency and small amplitude. However, as the size of the crushed particles decreases, the excitation frequency must be increased, and the amplitude reduced, since the crack size within the particle diminishes. Therefore, the most favorable effect is achieved through the simultaneous application of both low- and high-frequency oscillations of the working tool (Figure 1c).

Thus, the application of amplitude-modulated oscillations of the working tool on the medium enables the simultaneous generation of both large and small cracks. Consequently, it becomes possible not only to control crack formation but also to stabilize the granulometric composition of the resulting crushed material within specified limits. Since the known methods [4] have significant drawbacks and cannot ensure controlled crack formation in brittle media, a new method for crushing brittle materials has been developed [5] to implement this principle of size reduction, which will substantially improve comminution efficiency by increasing process throughput and enabling the production of a more uniform particle size distribution through regulation of the crack formation process. The essence of the method [5] is as follows: the working tool exerts an impact effect on the brittle medium, wherein each impact element of the working tool, along with their collective rotation, is assigned a degree of freedom of movement around its own axes positioned equidistantly from the axis of rotation, characterized in that, in addition, each impact element of the working tool is imparted a rotational speed with pulsation, and its axes of rotation undergo a forced precessional motion combined with nutation.

Computer modeling of the controlled crack formation process according to method [5] was conducted using the LSTC LS-Dyna software package. As an initial approximation, the classical Lagrangian finite element method with element erosion was employed, enabling clear visualization of crack formation within the material.

The core principle of the computer modeling is as follows: an element of the working body, modeled as a three-dimensional hemispherical shell, impacts the brittle material model while performing oscillatory motion, and subsequently, in accordance with the method, a crack network forms, providing dimensional comminution. A granite model was selected to represent the material being ground. Its fundamental properties were adopted from [6]. The material was considered within an isotropic homogeneous approximation, which is adequate for a preliminary analysis of the crack formation process.

According to [5], alongside rotation at a specified speed, rotational speed pulsations with a certain amplitude are imposed, causing a horizontal deviation in the trajectory of the impact element. Thus, impacts occur sequentially at the first point, then the second, then back to the first, and finally at the third. Such movement is performed cyclically. Simultaneously with the oscillatory motion, forced vibrational displacements of the impact point are executed. Thus, an effect

of distributing the instantaneous impact load over the area occurs, which accompanies a multiple increase in the crack pattern density. Figure 3 shows the chronology of crack propagation and the formation of the granulometric composition.

Fig. 2 — Crack formation process during size reduction of the rock: the first crack at impact point 1; the second crack at impact point 2; the third crack at impact point 3

Fig. 3 — Formation of granulometric composition at the amplitude of horizontal oscillations of the working organ element: a) 2 mm; b) 4 mm

Final element size: $0.3 \text{ mm} \times 0.3 \text{ mm} \times 0.3 \text{ mm}$.

Distinct zones bounded by cracks are observed, where further fracture propagation along these cracks will result in the formation of granules of the corresponding sizes. A crack network forms, consisting of branches emanating from the primary cracks and secondary, finer cracks, which, in turn, affect the extent of comminution of the entire brittle material. Splitting will initially occur primarily along the main cracks and subsequently propagate through the crack network. The essence of crack formation control lies in managing the sizes of primary cracks

and their growth rates. This is achieved by controlling the kinematics of the tool's motion. The tool shape may vary.

The lengths of the conditional sides of the formed granules at an oscillation amplitude of 2 mm range from 4 mm to 8 mm, while at an amplitude of 4 mm they range from 1.2 mm to 10 mm. Thus, the first case demonstrates a smaller size range of granules. This example illustrates that, under the given conditions (tool shape and material model, as well as the kinematic parameters of the tool motion), a more uniform granulometric composition of the crushed brittle material is achieved by setting the amplitude of horizontal oscillations of the working element to 2 mm. Thus, modeling enables the selection of optimal parameters for the vibratory displacement of the crushing tool to achieve the required size reduction and a uniform granulometric distribution. This, in turn, confirms the controlled formation of cracks depending on the tool kinematics and ensures dimensional crushing of the mineral.

Conclusion

Control of crack formation in minerals allows for the regulation of both the direction and velocity of crack propagation, thereby reducing the likelihood of uncontrolled material failure and enhancing the stability of the granulometric composition of the resulting granulate. Computer modeling confirmed the physical adequacy of the proposed comminution method [*Patent of the Russian Federation No. 2732619*]: it was established that setting the optimal amplitude of tool vibrations minimizes the dispersion of particle sizes and ensures the formation of a uniform granulometric composition. This method will be useful in the manufacture of construction materials, as well as in the mining and glass industries. Refinement of the computer model parameters and transition to more complex fracture models are planned for the subsequent stages of the work.

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研究基于碳纤维和聚合物基体的混合复合材料的结构和性能
**INVESTIGATION OF THE STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES
OF HYBRID COMPOSITE MATERIALS BASED
ON CARBON FIBER AND POLYMER MATRIX**

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摘要：本文致力于研究增强方案对碳纤维/环氧树脂基混合复合材料力学性能的影响。文中展示了不同层序排列样品的实验研究结果，并建立了增强层取向对复合材料强度、弹性模量和失效机制影响的主要规律。对单向、交叉和准各向同性增强方案的复合材料力学性能进行了对比分析。利用扫描电子显微镜研究了断裂表面的微观结构。所得数据可用于建筑和交通运输行业结构元件的设计。

关键词：混合复合材料，碳纤维，聚合物基体，增强方案，力学性能，弹性模量，断裂表面，扫描电子显微镜

Abstract. *This work is devoted to the study of the influence of the reinforcement scheme on the mechanical characteristics of hybrid composite materials based on carbon fiber and epoxy binder. The results of experimental studies of samples with different layering sequences are presented. The main regularities of the influence of the orientation of reinforcing layers on the strength, elastic modulus, and failure mechanisms of the composite are established. A comparative analysis of the mechanical properties of composites with unidirectional, cross, and quasi-isotropic reinforcement schemes is carried out. The microstructure of the fracture surface is studied using scanning electron microscopy. The obtained data can be used in the design of structural elements for the construction and transport industries.*

Keywords: *hybrid composites, carbon fiber, polymer matrix, reinforcement scheme, mechanical properties, elastic modulus, fracture surface, scanning electron microscopy.*

Introduction

Modern materials science is developing in the direction of creating structural materials with high specific strength and rigidity. One of the most promising areas is the development of hybrid composite materials (HCM), which combine reinforcing fibers of various natures. The use of carbon fiber as a reinforcing component makes it possible to obtain materials with high strength and low weight, which is especially important in the construction of unique buildings and structures, as well as in transport engineering [1, 2].

Composite materials based on carbon fiber are increasingly being used in industries where reducing the weight of structures without compromising their strength characteristics is a critical requirement. In the construction industry, such materials are used for reinforcing concrete structures, creating lightweight bridge spans, and manufacturing facade elements. In the automotive and aerospace industries, carbon fiber composites are used for the production of body panels, load-bearing frames, and interior elements [3].

One of the key factors determining the mechanical behavior of laminated composites is the reinforcement scheme, i.e., the orientation of the reinforcing layers relative to the loading axis. The choice of layering sequence directly affects the anisotropy of properties, the nature of failure, and the efficiency of using the reinforcing fibers. Despite the large number of studies in this area, the question of selecting the optimal reinforcement scheme for structures operating under complex loading conditions remains open and requires further research.

The purpose of this work is to study the effect of the reinforcement scheme on the mechanical properties of hybrid composite materials based on carbon fiber and an epoxy matrix, as well as to analyze the failure mechanisms depending on the layering sequence.

Materials and Research Methods

To obtain samples, a unidirectional carbon fiber tape (T700) manufactured by Toray Industries was used. This fiber has high strength (4900 MPa) and elastic modulus (230 GPa), which makes it one of the most common reinforcing fillers in the production of high-performance composites. An epoxy binder based on ED-20 resin was used as the matrix. The choice of epoxy binder is due to its high adhesion to carbon fiber, good technological properties, and the ability to cure at moderate temperatures without the formation of volatile byproducts.

The samples were made by vacuum infusion, which ensures high quality of impregnation and minimal porosity. The process was carried out in several stages:

- Laying the dry carbon fiber fabric according to the selected reinforcement scheme on a metal mold;
- Installing a vacuum bag and creating a vacuum of 0,08-0,09 MPa;
- Preparing the epoxy binder (mixing the resin with a hardener in a ratio of 10:1);

- Infusing the binder into the reinforcement package under vacuum;
- Curing according to the regime: 80 °C for 2 hours + 120 °C for 3 hours.

Three types of reinforcement schemes were considered:

- Unidirectional scheme (0°) — all layers are oriented along the loading axis.

This scheme ensures maximum strength and stiffness in the direction of reinforcement, but the material is highly anisotropic.

- Cross scheme (0°/90°) — alternating layers with mutual perpendicular orientation. The layering sequence was [0°/90°]_s. This scheme reduces anisotropy and provides more balanced properties in two directions.

- Quasi-isotropic scheme (0°/90°/45°/-45°) — symmetric layering [0°/90°/45°/-45°]_s. This scheme approximates an isotropic material in the plane of the sheet.

From the obtained plates, samples for tensile testing were cut using a water jet cutting machine. The sample geometry corresponded to the requirements of ASTM D3039: rectangular shape with a length of 250 mm, a width of 25 mm, and a thickness of 2 mm. Tabs made of fiberglass were glued to the ends of the samples to prevent destruction in the gripping zone.

Research Methods: Tensile tests were carried out on an Instron 5985 universal testing machine with a maximum load capacity of 250 kN. The tests were performed at a constant traverse speed of 2 mm/min. The deformation was measured using an extensometer with a base of 50 mm. For each reinforcement scheme, at least five samples were tested to ensure statistical reliability of the results.

The structure and fracture surface were studied using a JEOL JSM-6510 scanning electron microscope (SEM). For this purpose, fragments of the fracture surface of samples after mechanical tests were cut out and coated with a conductive layer of gold.

Results and Discussion

Mechanical Properties: The analysis of the obtained experimental data showed that the reinforcement scheme has a decisive influence on the strength and deformation characteristics of the composite. Table 1 summarizes the main results of mechanical tests.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of composites with different reinforcement schemes

Reinforcement scheme	Tensile strength σ_{max} , MPa	Elastic modulus E, GPa	Elongation at break ϵ , %
Unidirectional (0°)	1850 ± 45	135 ± 3	1.37 ± 0.05
Cross (0°/90°)	820 ± 28	58 ± 2	1.41 ± 0.06
Quasi-isotropic	1120 ± 35	52 ± 2	2.15 ± 0.08

For samples with a unidirectional structure, the maximum tensile strength reached 1850 MPa, which is consistent with the classical rule of mixtures [4]:

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_f V_f + \sigma_m (1 - V_f) \quad (1)$$

Where σ_c is the composite strength, σ_f is the fiber strength, σ_m is the matrix strength, V_f is the fiber volume fraction. For the obtained samples, the fiber volume fraction $V_f = 0,55$ was determined by the burn-off method. The calculation using the rule of mixtures gives a theoretical strength value of 1870 MPa, which is in good agreement with the experimental data.

For the cross reinforcement scheme, a decrease in strength to 820 MPa was recorded, which is 56% lower than for the unidirectional scheme. This is explained by the fact that in the layers oriented at 90° to the loading axis, the load is transferred mainly through the matrix, which has significantly lower strength compared to the fibers. However, the cross scheme provides an increase in the elastic modulus in the transverse direction, which is important for structures experiencing biaxial loading.

The quasi-isotropic scheme demonstrated the most balanced properties: strength $\sigma_{max} = 1120$ with an elongation at break $\varepsilon = 2.15\%$. It is noteworthy that the elongation at break for the quasi-isotropic scheme is 57% higher than for the unidirectional scheme. This indicates a change in the failure mechanism from brittle to more ductile, which is associated with the redistribution of stresses between layers with different orientations.

The stress-strain curves for all three types of samples have a linear character up to the moment of failure, which is typical for carbon fiber composites with an epoxy matrix. No yield plateau was observed. The elastic modulus for the unidirectional scheme was $E = 135$, for the cross scheme — $E = 58$, for the quasi-isotropic scheme — $E = 52$. The decrease in the modulus with the transition to quasi-isotropic layering is due to the lower stiffness of layers oriented at an angle to the loading axis.

The dependence of stress on deformation for the quasi-isotropic scheme can be described by the expression:

$$\sigma(\varepsilon) = E_0 \varepsilon \left[1 - \frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_{max}} \right] \quad (2)$$

Where E_0 is the initial elastic modulus, ε_{max} is the ultimate deformation. This phenomenological model takes into account the nonlinearity that appears at the final stage of loading due to the accumulation of microdamages in the matrix and at the fiber-matrix interface.

Microstructure Analysis

SEM analysis of the fracture surface revealed significant differences in the failure mechanisms depending on the reinforcement scheme.

In samples with a unidirectional structure, the fracture surface has a characteristic “brush-like” appearance with a large number of protruding fibers. Fiber pulling out is observed, which indicates a weak fiber-matrix interface. The fiber length in the pull-out zone is 50-100 μm . The fracture is brittle in nature, and the destruction occurs mainly along the fiber-matrix interface without significant plastic deformation of the matrix.

In samples with a cross reinforcement scheme, the fracture surface is more complex. In layers oriented at 0° , fiber pulling out is observed, while in layers oriented at 90° , the fracture passes through the matrix and fibers, which are oriented perpendicular to the loading axis. Transverse cracks are formed in the 90° layers, which are the initiators of failure.

In quasi-isotropic composites, the most complex failure pattern is observed. The fracture surface is characterized by multiple microcracks in the matrix, fiber pull-out in layers oriented at 0° , and signs of delamination between layers with different orientations. The presence of numerous microcracks indicates the dissipation of strain energy before the final failure, which explains the increased elongation at break for this type of material.

Comparison with Literature Data

The obtained results are in good agreement with the data presented in the works of other researchers. In, similar values of strength and modulus were obtained for unidirectional carbon fiber composites. In, it was shown that the transition from a unidirectional to a quasi-isotropic reinforcement scheme leads to a decrease in strength by 30-40%, which is consistent with our results. The increase in elongation at break for quasi-isotropic composites noted in this work is also confirmed by the data of, where it is associated with the activation of various failure mechanisms that increase the energy intensity of destruction [5].

Conclusion

As a result of the conducted studies, the following main conclusions can be drawn:

1. The reinforcement scheme has a decisive influence on the mechanical properties of hybrid composite materials based on carbon fiber and epoxy binder. Changing the layering sequence allows targeted control of strength, stiffness, and deformation characteristics.

2. The unidirectional reinforcement scheme provides maximum strength (1850 MPa) and elastic modulus (135 GPa) in the reinforcement direction, but the material is highly anisotropic and has minimal elongation at break (1,37%).

3. The cross reinforcement scheme ($0^\circ/90^\circ$) reduces strength by 56% compared to the unidirectional scheme but provides more balanced properties in two mutually perpendicular directions.

4. The quasi-isotropic layering ($0^\circ/90^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ$) provides the optimal combination of properties: strength 1120 MPa, elastic modulus 52 GPa, and elongation

at break 2,15%. The increased elongation at break is due to the activation of multiple failure mechanisms, including microcracking in the matrix and delamination, which contribute to strain energy dissipation.

5. SEM analysis showed that the failure mechanism changes depending on the reinforcement scheme. In unidirectional composites, brittle failure with fiber pull-out predominates; in cross composites, transverse cracks in the 90° layers act as failure initiators; in quasi-isotropic composites, a combination of fiber pull-out, matrix microcracking, and delamination is observed.

6. The obtained data can be used in the design of structural elements for the construction and transport industries, especially when selecting the optimal reinforcement scheme depending on the operating conditions of the structure. The quasi-isotropic layering is recommended for use in structures operating under complex loading conditions, where a combination of strength and resistance to crack propagation is required.

Prospects for Further Research

Further research in this area may include:

- Study of the effect of hybrid reinforcement (combination of carbon fiber with glass or basalt fiber) on the mechanical properties and cost of composites;
- Investigation of the fatigue characteristics of composites with different reinforcement schemes under cyclic loading;
- Development of computational models for predicting the mechanical behavior of hybrid composites taking into account the microstructure;
- Study of the effect of operating conditions (temperature, humidity, aggressive environments) on the durability of composites with different layering sequences.

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苏联和俄罗斯异丁烷与烯烃烷基化工艺形成和发展的主要阶段（综述）
**MAIN STAGES OF THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF
THE PROCESS OF ALKYLATION OF ISOBUTANE WITH OLEFINS
IN THE USSR AND IN RUSSIA (REVIEW)**

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摘要：本文作者论证了烷基化工艺是石油炼制中最早用于生产高辛烷值航空汽油的工业技术之一，在其95年的发展历程中，该工艺不断改进和现代化。文章作者将苏联和俄罗斯烷基化工艺的发展历程划分为九个阶段：从工业装置中采用硫酸和氢氟酸的均相液态酸烷基化，到中试装置中采用沸石基固体酸催化剂的非均相烷基化。

关键词：烷基化，异丁烷，烯烃，烷基化物，烷基化汽油，催化剂，硫酸，氢氟酸，沸石，阶段，形成，发展，改进。

Abstract: *The authors demonstrate that the alkylation process is among the earliest industrial technologies implemented in petroleum refining for the production of high-octane aviation gasoline, and over its 95-year history, it has been continually improved and modernized. The authors of the article have identified nine stages in the development of the Soviet and Russian alkylation process: from homogeneous liquid acid alkylation using sulfuric and hydrofluoric acids in industrial units to heterogeneous alkylation employing solid acid catalysts based on zeolites in pilot-industrial units.*

Keywords: *alkylation, isobutane, olefins, alkylate, alkylate gasoline, catalysts, sulfuric acid, hydrofluoric acid, zeolites, stages, formation, development, modifications.*

A brief historical background of the formation and development of the isobutane alkylation process with olefins

Among the revolutionary petroleum refining processes developed in the first half of the 20th century, the isobutane alkylation process with olefins holds a particularly important position, due to its significant role in the production of high-octane automobile and aviation gasoline [1].

The isobutane alkylation process with olefins, with an almost 95-year history of development, is one of the earliest industrial processes introduced into petroleum refining for the production of high-octane aviation gasolines and has undergone continuous improvement and development throughout its long existence.

This important reaction was discovered by the distinguished Russian chemist V. N. Ipatiev in 1932. [1], and since that time, numerous modifications of the alkylation process have been developed employing various types of catalysts. Paradoxically, it was precisely at the onset of the Second World War that the development of the isobutane alkylation process with olefins was accelerated. Furthermore, owing to this process, the production of high-octane aviation gasoline was established, which provided speed advantages to the Allies' aviation and thereby made a substantial contribution to the victory in the war. The alkylation process constitutes a significant contribution of the Russian academician V. N. Ipatiev to the Allied countries' victory over fascism: the USSR, the USA, and England [2]. Even today, on the eve of the 95th anniversary of the discovery of the alkylation reaction by academician V. N. Ipatiev, it can be stated with confidence that the alkylation of isoparaffins and aromatic hydrocarbons with olefins remains one of the most significant processes in petroleum refining and petrochemistry, exerting a profound influence on the development of the economies of many countries [1],

At present, the alkylation process encompasses various modifications carried out on different acidic catalysts:

- homogeneous alkylation employing sulfuric acid, hydrofluoric acid, boron trifluoride, and aluminum chloride;
- heterogeneous acid alkylation using aluminosilicate and zeolite-containing catalysts.

In contemporary practice, the majority of global industrial alkylate production is based on acid-catalyzed alkylation methods, predominantly sulfuric acid and hydrofluoric acid alkylation of isoparaffins with olefins. These processes represent the first industrially implemented alkylation technologies in the USA: sulfuric acid alkylation in 1938. and hydrofluoric acid alkylation in 1942.

In the USSR, the first industrial implementation of the sulfuric acid alkylation (SCA) process was carried out in 1942 in Grozny. The priority for the development and advancement of the domestic sulfuric acid alkylation process belongs to the scientists of GrozNII, who, under the most challenging prewar and wartime

conditions and despite a lack of sufficient scientific information and practical knowledge of this process, conducted research and developed the technology for the alkylation of isoparaffins with olefins; they continue to this day to be engaged in the development and improvement of this process [3].

Main stages of the research on the alkylation process

The stages of development of the isobutane alkylation process with olefins using various catalysts are presented in Figure 1 [1,4]. Among all the known modifications of the isobutane alkylation process with olefins, the sulfuric acid and hydrofluoric acid alkylation processes are the most widely commercialized. These technologies account for a significant share of global motor alkylate production.

Nearly 95 years of experience with the operation of liquid acid alkylation units shows that these process variants, while resolving issues related to the quality of alkylate gasoline, simultaneously generate substantial challenges in environmental protection and the operation of such production facilities. Significant economic and technological drawbacks of liquid-phase alkylation processes include high catalyst costs, pronounced toxicity, corrosive aggressiveness, the production of acidic wastewater, and others.

Figure 1 — Stages of catalyst research in the isobutane alkylation process with olefins: 1— complexes based on AlCl_3 ; 2— BF_3 and complexes based on BF_3 ; 3 — H_2SO_4 ; 4 — HF ; 5 — aluminosilicate catalysts; 6 — ion-exchange resins; 7 — zeolites X and Y; 8 — zeolites β , ZSM, MCM, ultrastable Y; 9 — heteropoly acids; 10 — supported H_2SO_4 and $\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3\text{H}$; 11 — anion-modified metal oxides

There is a necessity to search for efficient and environmentally friendly technologies for the isobutane alkylation process with olefins, based on the use of new, more promising heterogeneous catalysts.

The possibility of employing heterogeneous catalysts that are well regenerable and predominantly zeolite-containing has attracted close attention from both foreign and domestic researchers. This direction in the development of the alkylation process is the most promising, and currently, a substantial body of research is dedicated to its investigation [1].

Stages of the formation, development, and construction of domestic industrial isobutane alkylation plants with olefins

The priority in establishing the domestic isobutane alkylation process with olefins belongs to the Grozny scientists and staff of GrozNII, who stood at the inception of this process in the early 1940s, developed and constructed the first pilot-industrial sulfuric acid alkylation unit in 1942, and with their support, all sulfuric acid alkylation units at refineries in the USSR were built throughout the 1950s to 1990s. GrozNII continues to actively develop and enhance the isobutane alkylation process with olefins, as well as to establish a domestic solid acid alkylation process using zeolite catalysts [3,5,6,7].

In the USSR, the only industrial technology for alkylating isoparaffins with olefins from 1942 to 2010 was sulfuric acid alkylation technology, in contrast to the USA and other leading countries abroad, where since 1938 the predominant method has been. Until the 2000s, sulfuric acid and hydrofluoric acid alkylation technologies were utilized.

Owing to substantial progress in the advancement of the domestic alkylation process, in 1968 the Grozny Oil Scientific Research Institute (GrozNII) was designated as the leading institution for the alkylation process in the USSR. It determined the primary directions for the development and enhancement of technology for this process in the country's petroleum refining sector, undertook the development of new catalysts and the refinement of those used in the process, and carried out reconstructions, modernizations, and other measures to improve the performance of industrial alkylation units nationwide [7]. The main stages in the establishment and development of the isobutane alkylation process with olefins at refineries in the USSR and the chronology of the construction of industrial isobutane alkylation units with olefins during 1942-1990s, as well as in subsequent years in Russia, are presented below based on an analysis of scientific-technical and research documents [1, 5, 6].

The first (initial) stage — construction in 1942. at Grozny, at the Grozny cracking plant, the first pilot-industrial SCA unit in the USSR, designated code 25 [5-7].

The second stage — *Lend-Lease (1946-1953)*. During this stage, the installation and commissioning of four sulfuric acid alkylation units supplied via

Lend-Lease from the USA were completed [8,9]. These SCA units, designated under various codes, were installed at the following domestic refineries: in 1946 at the Orsk refinery — unit 25-4; in 1951 At Krasnovodsk refinery, unit 24-46; in 1952. At Kuibyshev refinery, unit 24-36; in 1953. At Guryev refinery, unit 23-16.

Third stage (1953-1968). During this stage, mass construction of sulfuric acid alkylation units was implemented at domestic refineries, primarily based on the research findings of GrozNII: in 1953. At Novogrozny refinery, the first industrial-scale SCA unit 25-1 in the USSR; in 1953. At the Novo-Baku refinery, SCA units 51-52; in 1954. At the Novo-Grozny refinery, the second SCA unit 25-2; in 1954-1955. At the Novo-Ufa refinery, the first alkylation block in the USSR was constructed, consisting of two SCA units (25-4-1 and 25-4-2); in 1955. One SCA unit at the Salavat refinery; in 1955. One SCA unit at the Omsk refinery; in 1956. At the Novo-Kuibyshev refinery, SCA unit 25/4; in 1964. SCA unit at the Syzran refinery; 1968. SCA unit at the Novo-Yaroslavl refinery 25/7. In total, 10 sulfuric acid alkylation units were constructed at this stage.

The fourth stage(1960s-1990s) represents the modernization phase of the domestic alkylation process, during which, in the 1960s-1980s, the principal reconstructions, modernizations, and upgrades of existing industrial alkylation units were implemented by applying various measures aimed at improving the performance of SCA units, including modifications to the rerouting schemes of contactor connections; use of mixed feedstock; modifications of existing contactor designs and development of new contactors (KSG-2,3, through-flow, etc.).

The largest reconstructions and modernizations of domestic SCA units were implemented at the Novogrozny Oil Refinery (NGNPZ) named after N. Anisimov (1960, 1970, 1980); at the SCA 25-7 unit of the Yaroslavl refinery, which during the Soviet period represented the most advanced sulfuric acid alkylation technology. Since 1980, Several reaction devices were tested on this unit: a horizontal cascade contactor KSG-2 with an open evaporation system (1980), horizontal reactors with a V-shaped tubular bundle (1982 and 1985), a tubular reactor with a battery of hydrocyclones (1986), a twin adiabatic tubular reactor (1991), an autothermic jet contactor based on the technology of the «Orben» firm (1992), the installation of a four-stage reactor (1995), continuous raw material settling schemes were implemented, systems for cleaning circulating isobutane from propane in column K-1 were established, and supply schemes for isobutane and acid to each reactor stage were organized (1996-97); Principally new agitators, developed at the Yaroslavl refinery itself (1998), were installed.

The fifth stage (1970-1990s) — development by GrozNII of combined and improved sulfuric acid alkylation units (KU units and upgraded SCA units of the 25-8C type (1975) and 25-8B type (1982)). Units of these systems were commissioned at the following refineries: Kremenchug, Lisichansk, Pavlodar, and Burgas NHC of the NRB.

A new, more advanced sulfuric acid alkylation unit for isobutane with olefins of the 25-8C type was developed in 1975. GrozNII and VNIPIneft [1]. The first industrial unit in the series of 25-8C sulfuric acid alkylation installations, incorporating several new technological and equipment design solutions, was constructed entirely with Soviet equipment and commissioned at the Burgas Petrochemical Complex (NRB) in 1982. with the assignment of the code 25-8B. The unit featured for the first time a horizontal sulfuric acid alkylation contactor of new design (KSG-3), developed by VNIPIneftemash based on data from GrozNII.

The sixth stage (1980-2000) represents an exploratory phase at GrozNII focused on the development of heterogeneous alkylation catalysts and the construction in Grozny of the first pilot-industrial isobutane alkylation units with olefins using zeolites and zeolite-containing catalysts. The period 1980-1986 corresponds to the initial years of this stage. At the GrozNII pilot plant, the first pilot-scale industrial installation for isobutane alkylation with olefins on solid catalysts was constructed in the USSR. During the 1990s and 2000s, GrozNII developed several variants of industrial installations for isobutane alkylation with olefins using zeolite catalysts, employing reactors of various designs: the ATK-PSS alkylation process with a zeolite layer suspended in the feedstock; the ATK-PSH alkylation process with a moving bed of spherical zeolite catalyst; and the ATK-SS isobutane butene alkylation process operated in a fixed bed of zeolite catalyst. These variants of heterogeneous acid alkylation underwent pilot-industrial testing at experimental plants of GrozNII and INHS RAS.

The seventh stage — the period from 1991 to 2010, was associated with the development of the Russian oil refining sector following the collapse of the USSR. Of the 16 domestic installations constructed in the USSR, mostly before the 1970s and utilizing solely the sulfuric acid alkylation process, the majority exhibited significant physical deterioration; consequently, some were decommissioned, while a portion of the SCA units remained in operation at refineries within the CIS countries [10]. Two Grozny alkylation units, 25-1 and 25-2, were decommissioned as early as 1985-1987.

Currently, only five Russian refineries — Omsk, Ufa, Yaroslavl, Samara, and Ryazan — operate isobutane sulfuric acid alkylation units with olefins. The total design capacity of alkylate production at these units amounts to 1,410 thousand tons per year. These units have been constructed or modernized employing new sulfuric acid alkylation technology. At the Ryazan refinery, the sulfuric acid alkylation unit was constructed in 2006. It employed a cascade reactor under license from EMRE (Exxon Mobile Research Engineering). Since 2013, at the Ufa refinery, an upgraded sulfuric acid alkylation unit 25-4/2 has been operating based on the technology of the STRATCO-DuPont company.

The eighth stage in the development of the domestic alkylation process (2010–2016) corresponds to the hydrofluoric acid alkylation stage of isobutane with olefins. At this stage, in 2010, the first hydrofluoric acid alkylation unit in Russia was commissioned at the Kstovo refinery of LLC ‘Lukoil-Nizhegorodnefteorgsintez’. The licensor of the hydrofluoric acid alkylation technology and the developer of the basic design for the domestic hydrofluoric acid alkylation unit is the company UOP (USA) [11]. In 2016, at LLC ‘Lukoil-Nizhegorodnefteorgsintez’ The second installation employing hydrofluoric acid alkylation technology under a UOP license was commissioned in Kstovo [12]. Thus, two hydrofluoric acid alkylation units are currently operating in domestic petroleum refining at the refinery in Kstovo, both constructed using UOP technology.

The ninth stage—represents the modern and most promising approach to conducting the isobutane alkylation process with olefins using heterogeneous catalysts. At this stage, a promising domestic technology for the isobutane alkylation process with olefins has been developed, utilizing new effective heterogeneous catalysts for isobutane alkylation with olefins, which eliminate the drawbacks of liquid acid alkylation variants. The new isobutane alkylation technology on solid catalysts developed in the Russian Federation is a joint development by GrozNII and INHS RAS and is unparalleled worldwide. This technology, in terms of technological parameters and material balance, can compete with existing sulfuric acid and hydrofluoric acid alkylation technologies. Based on this technology, at a refinery in Elektrogorsk, Moscow Region, commissioned by PJSC Gazprom Neft, the first experimental-industrial isoparaffin alkylation unit with olefins on a heterogeneous catalyst with a capacity of 1 t/day of alkylate, named ‘AlkiRan-GNP’ [13], was constructed in the Russian Federation in 2016. Based on the results of research carried out at this unit, the construction of the first domestic industrial alkylation unit utilizing solid catalysts, with a capacity of 100 thousand tons per year of alkylate is planned at the enterprise JSC Gazpromneft — Moscow refinery.

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关于将客户关系管理系统作为有效支持投资和建设项目技术支持的工具
**ON THE USE OF CRM SYSTEMS AS A TOOL FOR EFFECTIVE
TECHNICAL SUPPORT OF INVESTMENT AND CONSTRUCTION
PROJECTS**

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摘要：本文探讨了客户关系管理（CRM）系统在建筑行业的具体应用。与传统的营销方式不同，本文重点关注如何将CRM系统集成到建筑和结构施工项目的技术实施环节中。文章分析了自动化设计师、承包商和客户之间的交互对技术监督质量以及施工和安装进度安排的影响。文中以一个假设的多功能住宅综合体（MRC）建设项目为例，通过CRM的实施，减少了技术方案协调过程中的时间损失。文章还论证了将精益建造方法与自动化数据系统相结合以实现最高效率的合理性。

关键词：CRM，施工管理，施工数字化，技术监督，建筑生命周期，-BIM，流程自动化，精益建造，互联建造，RFI，最后计划系统。

Abstract. *This article examines the specifics of applying customer relationship management (CRM) systems in the construction industry. Unlike the classical marketing approach, the focus is placed on integrating CRM systems into the technical block of project implementation for the construction of buildings and structures. An analysis is conducted on the impact of automating interactions among designers, contractors, and clients on the quality of technical supervision and compliance with construction and installation work schedules. An empirical case study is presented based on a hypothetical project for the construction of a multifunctional residential complex (MRC), where the implementation of CRM reduced time losses during the coordination of technical solutions. The rationale for applying Lean Construction methods in combination with automated data systems to achieve maximum efficiency is demonstrated.*

Keywords: *CRM, construction management, construction digitalization, technical supervision, building lifecycle, BIM, process automation, Lean Construction, Connected Construction, RFI, Last Planner System.*

The modern construction industry is characterized by a high level of decentralization among project stakeholders. The process of constructing a building or structure involves a complex chain of interactions: from the preparation of design and estimate documentation (DED) to the commissioning of the facility. Traditional methods of managing the technical aspect of the project often suffer from ‘information gaps,’ leading to schedule delays and budget overruns. The implementation of CRM systems adapted to the needs of technical management is becoming the response to the challenges posed by the digital transformation of the industry.

In the technical aspect, the CRM system transforms from a sales tool into a unified data collection environment (Common Data Environment — CDE). This transformation requires rethinking the standard functionality and adapting it to the specifics of construction production. The main functions of CRM in the technical cycle include:

Change Management in the project (Change Management): Recording all edits in the design and estimate documentation (DED) at any stage of the facility’s life cycle, with automatic notification to all interested parties (general contractor, sub-contractors, technical supervision service, designers) about the changes made. This eliminates work with outdated versions of drawings and specifications.

Procurement & Logistics Control: Integration of data on the availability and movement of material and technical resources (MTR) with the construction and installation works schedule (SMR). CRM allows for forecasting potential delivery delays and timely implementation of corrective measures, as well as monitoring the compliance of supplied materials with project requirements.

Automated Documentation: Preparation and management of as-built documentation (hidden works inspection reports, work logs, as-built diagrams) in real time. This significantly simplifies the handover and acceptance procedures and the preparation of documentation for commissioning the facility.

Communication and Request Management (RFI Management): The system acts as a centralized channel for submitting and processing Requests for Information (RFI), thereby minimizing the time required to resolve disputed points and obtain clarifications from designers or the client.

To achieve the aims of the study, the methodology of the ‘digital twin of the construction process’ was employed. This methodology is based on creating a virtual model that replicates real processes, enabling their dynamic analysis. The fundamental management methods integrated via the CRM system were selected as follows:

Lean Construction method: The main goal of this approach is to maximize the elimination of ‘waste’ (Muda) in all its manifestations (unnecessary movements, waiting, overproduction, defects, excessive processing, underutilized employee potential) during the transfer of information and execution of work among different project stakeholders. The CRM system serves as a digital platform that supports the

identification and elimination of such waste, particularly in terms of informational transparency and the timeliness of interactions.

Critical Path Method (CPM): This method enables the identification of the sequence of tasks that directly impact the overall project duration. The use of CRM systems to monitor bottlenecks in the coordination chain of engineering units, material supply, and work execution at critical stages facilitates more effective resource and schedule management.

The study considers a conditional project for the construction of a multifunctional residential complex. The project provides for the construction of a building with a total area of 45,000 square meters. m, including residential apartments, commercial premises, and underground parking. The total project duration is 24 months.

Problem existing prior to CRM implementation: During the installation phase of engineering networks (months 8-14 from the commencement of construction), a multifaceted problem arose involving significant delays in the execution of works. The causes were:

Discrepancies between design solutions (DS) and actual conditions at the construction site: During construction, conflicts not accounted for during the design phase were revealed, necessitating prompt alterations.

Lengthy process of change approval (RFI): The processing of Requests for Information (RFI) in its traditional format (email correspondence, paper-based approvals) took on average 5 working days. This resulted in significant work stoppages for extended periods.

High volume of RFIs: The total number of required approvals and clarifications exceeded 30 per week, creating an enormous workload for engineers and designers.

CRM implementation process: To resolve the identified issues, a specialized CRM system with a module for technical document management and integration with the registry of construction elements was deployed. The key implementation stages included:

Customization for construction specifics: Adaptation of modules to record work statuses, link documentation to specific zones of the site, and create templates for RFIs and as-built documentation.

Personnel training: Conducting a series of trainings for engineering and technical personnel (ETP) — site supervisors, foremen, planning and technical department engineers, and technical supervision specialists.

Integration with the BIM model: An attempt was made within the project to integrate the CRM system with the BIM model (Building Information Modeling) to visualize changes and facilitate the identification of problematic areas.

Obtained results: The implementation of the CRM system on the project demonstrated a significant improvement in key technical indicators:

Reduction in the RFI cycle time: The average approval time for a request for information decreased from 5 working days to 1.2 working days. This was achieved

through the automatic assignment of responsible individuals, the establishment of strict deadlines for each stage of approval, and real-time notifications.

Reduction in the number of reworks: The quantity of reworks caused by installations based on outdated or incorrect drawings decreased by 85%. Transparency of the change management process and operational access to up-to-date design information prevented the occurrence of many defects.

Improvement in crew productivity: Reducing downtime caused by waiting for approvals or incorrect information enabled a 15% increase in the productivity of installation crews.

Financial effect: The total savings related to the reduction of non-productive costs (worker downtime, procurement of excess materials, and error correction) over the six-month period following CRM implementation is estimated at approximately 12 million rubles [2, 5].

CRM in construction should implement the concept of Connected Construction. This implies creating a unified digital ecosystem where various participants and processes are interconnected. Technically, this can be implemented as a three-level model:

Level 1 (Field Level): Data collection directly from the construction site. This is done through CRM mobile applications, enabling engineers and foremen to record work execution status, perform photo and video recording of defects, promptly send information requests, and mark the acceptance of hidden works.

Level 2 (Engineering Level): Processing received information, analyzing change requests, matching data with the BIM model (if used), and coordinating technical solutions with designers and experts. At this level, the primary ‘intellectual’ work of managing project decisions is carried out.

Level 3 (Management Level): Creating analytical dashboards for senior and middle management. These dashboards display the project’s key performance indicators (KPIs) in real time — the ‘project health index,’ schedule progress trends, the volume of current RFIs, and supply data. This enables the prompt making of strategic decisions.

Implementation of Lean Construction methods through CRM: CRM serves as a technical driver for the successful application of Lean Construction principles. The system’s use facilitates the effective application of the following methods:

Last Planner System (LPS) method: CRM can be integrated with LPS tools to break down weekly work plans to the level of individual performers and teams. The system ensures transparency in the discipline of material deliveries and the availability of resources, which is critically important for fulfilling weekly plans. Automatic reminders and task completion tracking reduce the likelihood of disruptions [3, 6].

Value Stream Mapping (VSM): CRM automatically generates reports that assist in identifying bottlenecks within processes, such as during acceptance of concealed

works, approval of design decisions, or delivery of critically important materials. Analysis of these data facilitates targeted process optimization by eliminating losses.

5S System (sorting, set in order, shining, standardization, and sustaining): Although 5S mainly relates to workplace organization, CRM can support it through the standardization of documentation procedures, quality control, and reporting.

Discussion of Results and Conclusions

The results obtained during the case study confirm the hypothesis regarding the significant potential of CRM systems in the technical support of construction projects. The main positive outcome of the implementation is the minimization of ‘information gaps’ and the reduction of decision-making time. This is critically important for projects characterized by a high degree of uncertainty and complex logistics, which encompasses most large-scale construction sites.

However, it should be noted that the effectiveness of CRM implementation depends not only on the system’s functionalities but also on the personnel’s readiness to utilize it. “Resistance of the environment” — the reluctance or inability of engineering and technical personnel (ETP) to adopt new digital tools — is one of the key barriers. Implementation success, according to expert assessments, depends 60% on the usability of the CRM user interface (UX design), as well as on a comprehensive system of training and support.

The integration of CRM with BIM models constitutes the next logical step in advancing the digitalization of construction. BIM provides detailed information about the asset, while CRM delivers tools for managing processes associated with that asset. Together, these technologies form a robust foundation for ‘intelligent’ project management, enabling the transition from management based on ‘file exchanges’ to management centered on ‘data and processes.’

The application of CRM systems in the investment and construction sector extends beyond traditional client service. Within the technical implementation phase of projects, CRM serves as a powerful tool for managing information, communications, and processes, ensuring transparency and control throughout all stages of the facility’s lifecycle.

The implementation of CRM systems enables a significant economic impact by reducing time expenditures, minimizing the number of reworks, and eliminating unproductive costs associated with downtime and errors [1, 5].

The greatest efficiency is achieved through an integrated approach that includes the integration of CRM with BIM technologies and the application of Lean Construction methods, such as the Last Planner System and value stream visualization [4, 6, 7].

The success of CRM implementation in construction critically depends on the ease of use of the system’s user interface and the quality of personnel training aimed at overcoming the digital divide among engineering and technical personnel.

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全同态加密方案的理论基础、实际应用及稳定性分析
**ANALYSIS OF THEORETICAL BASIS, PRACTICAL
IMPLEMENTATIONS AND STABILITY OF FULL
HOMOMORPHOUS ENCRYPTION SCHEMES**

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摘要：本文对全同态加密（FHE）进行了全面的科学综述。FHE 是一种密码技术，它允许对加密数据进行任意计算而无需解密。文章详细分析了 FHE 的理论基础，该基础基于带误差学习（LWE）问题及其环变体的难度。文章系统地考察了 FHE 方案的演进历程，从 Craig Gentry 的原始构造到现代高效的 CKKS 和 TFHE 方案。此外，文章还对包括 Microsoft SEAL、PALISADE 和 OpenFHE 在内的开源软件库的现状进行了全面评估。文章分析了当前针对 FHE 系统的密码分析攻击形势，并探讨了该技术在保密计算、机器学习和金融领域的当前和未来实际应用。结论是，FHE 已从理论研究阶段过渡到积极的实践验证和早期实施阶段。

关键词：全同态加密，FHE，带误差学习，LWE，RLWE，基于格的密码学，引导，保密计算，密码分析，后量子密码学。

Abstract. *The present article provides a comprehensive scientific review of full homomorphic encryption (FHE) — a cryptographic technology that allows arbitrary computations on encrypted data without decryption. A detailed analysis of the theoretical foundation of FHE, grounded in the hardness of the Learning With Errors (LWE) problem and its ring variants, is presented. The evolution of FHE schemes is systematically examined across several generations, from Craig Gentry's original construction to the modern, highly efficient CKKS and TFHE schemes. A comprehensive evaluation of the current state of open-source software*

libraries, including Microsoft SEAL, PALISADE, and OpenFHE, is provided. The contemporary landscape of cryptanalytic attacks on FHE systems is analyzed. Both current and prospective practical applications of the technology in confidential computing, machine learning, and finance are discussed. It can be concluded that FHE has transitioned from the stage of theoretical investigation to a phase of active practical validation and early implementation.

Keywords: full homomorphic encryption, FHE, learning with errors, LWE, RLWE, lattice-based cryptography, bootstrapping, confidential computing, cryptanalysis, post-quantum cryptography.

1. Introduction

The modern digital landscape is characterized by an unprecedented volume of generated and processed data. Traditional cryptographic protocols, while effectively addressing data protection tasks during transmission and storage, create vulnerabilities during processing: for any computation, data must be decrypted. A conceptual solution to this problem is full homomorphic encryption (Fully Homomorphic Encryption, FHE), which enables performing arbitrary computations on encrypted data without decrypting it [1].

Despite the groundbreaking idea originally proposed by Rivest, Adleman, and Dertouzos in 1978 [1], practical implementation of FHE remained elusive for a prolonged period. Craig Gentry's 2009 work [2], which proposed the first provably secure FHE construction based on lattice theory, ushered in a new era of intensive research.

The objective of this review is to systematize current knowledge in the field of FHE by integrating its theoretical foundations, practical implementation aspects, and security analysis.

2. Historical Background

The inception of the homomorphic encryption concept is linked to the emergence of asymmetric cryptography. The RSA scheme possesses the property of multiplicative homomorphism: the product of two ciphertexts equals the encryption of the product of the corresponding plaintexts:

$$\begin{aligned} c &= Enc(m) = Enc(m_1) \cdot Enc(m_2) = (m_1^e \bmod n) \cdot (m_2^e \bmod n) \\ &= (m_1 \cdot m_2)^e \bmod n = Enc(m_1 \cdot m_2). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

However, such schemes were only partially homomorphic (SHE). A significant obstacle to the construction of FHE was the effect of error accumulation: when performing operations on ciphertexts, noise grows, and once a threshold is exceeded, decryption becomes impossible.

The solution to this fundamental problem was discovered by Craig Gentry in 2009 [2]. Its construction comprised two key components: a partially homomorphic scheme

based on ideal lattices and a bootstrapping procedure — a technique enabling homomorphic execution of the decryption process with an encrypted secret key, producing a new ciphertext with a reduced noise level. The first implementation [3] established the fundamental feasibility but also the extreme impracticality of FHE. Nevertheless, Gentry’s work served as a catalyst for the exponential growth of research.

3. Learning with Errors (LWE) Problem

Almost all modern, efficient FHE schemes are based on the computational hardness of lattice theory problems, with the learning-with-errors (LWE) problem playing a central role. [4].

3.1. Formal Definition

Let n be a positive integer security parameter, q an integer modulus, and χ a probability distribution (error distribution) over (for example, a discrete Gaussian distribution with a small standard deviation σ).

- *Search-LWE*. Given a set of pairs of the form:

$$(\vec{a}_i, b_i = \langle \vec{a}_i, \vec{s} \rangle + e_i) \in \mathbb{Z}_q^n \times \mathbb{Z}_q, \quad (2)$$

where \vec{a}_i are uniformly randomly selected from \mathbb{Z}_q^n, \vec{s} — a fixed secret vector from \mathbb{Z}_q^n , and e_i — small errors chosen from χ . The problem consists of finding the secret vector \vec{s} .

- *Decision-LWE*. The problem consists in distinguishing with an advantage that is not negligible pairs $(\vec{a}_i, b_i = \langle \vec{a}_i, \vec{s} \rangle + e)$ from pairs (\vec{a}, u) , where u is chosen uniformly at random from \mathbb{Z}_q .

It has been shown that these two problems are equivalent in complexity [4]. Moreover, the LWE problem is hard on average, assuming the intractability of worst-case instances of certain lattice-based NP-hard problems, such as the Shortest Vector Problem (SVP) and the Short Independent Vectors Problem (SIVP) with polynomial approximation factors. This duality — average-case hardness reducible to worst-case hardness — renders LWE an exceptionally reliable foundation for constructing cryptographic primitives, including those resilient to attacks by quantum computers.

3.2. Ring-LWE variant

To enhance efficiency, an algebraic variant of the problem, Ring-LWE (RLWE), was proposed. In RLWE, scalars and vectors are replaced by elements of a polynomial ring $R_q = \mathbb{Z}_q[x]/\langle f(x) \rangle$, where $f(x)$ is an irreducible polynomial (often $x^{2k} + 1$ used for efficient implementation of the Fourier transform). The secret s and error e are now polynomials from R_q with small coefficients.

The RLWE pair takes the form:

$$(\vec{a}, b = \vec{a} \cdot \vec{s} + e) \in R_q \times R_q, \quad (3)$$

where \vec{a} is chosen uniformly at random from R_q . The problem remains to find s (search-RLWE) or to distinguish such pairs from uniformly random ones (decision-RLWE).

The use of RLWE significantly improves efficiency: one operation on a ring element (a polynomial of degree n) is equivalent to operations on n independent scalar LWE elements; simultaneously, the sizes of public keys and ciphertexts reduce from $O(n^2)$ to $O(n)$, and the operation speed increases due to the fast Fourier transform or number-theoretic transform. [5]. The overwhelming majority of modern FHE schemes (BGV, BFV, CKKS) are based on RLWE.

4. Generations of Practical Encryption Schemes

The evolution of FHE schemes can be roughly divided into several generations.

First generation: constructions based on ideal lattices.

This generation comprises schemes based on ideal lattices, directly following the work of Gentry-Halevi. They were proven secure but highly inefficient: key sizes reached gigabytes, and the processing time per operation was several minutes [3].

Second generation: leveled FHE schemes without bootstrapping.

The central idea of the second generation is to avoid costly bootstrapping wherever possible. Instead, the schemes enable evaluation of computational circuits of a predetermined but arbitrary depth L . This is achieved through meticulous management of error growth and the application of the **modulus switching** technique introduced by Brakerski, Gentry, and Vaikuntanathan (the BGV scheme). [6].

The idea of modulus switching consists in sequentially reducing the modulus q after each operation (primarily multiplication) to control the relative noise level. Suppose the ciphertext after the operation \vec{c} has noise v . When switching to a smaller modulus p , scaling the ciphertext: $\vec{c}' = \lfloor (p/q) \cdot \vec{c} \rfloor$, the noise also decreases approximately to $(p/q) \cdot v$. This enables performing L levels of computation without bootstrapping by selecting the initial modulus q to be sufficiently large.

Another well-known scheme of this generation is FV (Fan-Vercauteren) [7], which employs a different noise management method based on scaling the message itself rather than the ciphertext. The BGV and FV schemes support exact integer arithmetic and efficient batching, **allowing packing hundreds or thousands of numbers into a single ciphertext and performing operations on them simultaneously (SIMD-style)**. [8]. This significantly increases throughput and makes the schemes applicable to tasks requiring massive parallelism.

Third generation: schemes optimized for bootstrapping.

The CKKS (Cheon-Kim-Kim-Song) scheme [9] became revolutionary for practical applications. It supports approximate operations in floating-point arithmetic, which, combined with efficient bootstrapping, established it as the de facto standard for confidential machine learning [10].

The TFHE scheme (Fast Fully Homomorphic Encryption over the Torus) [11] is optimized for rapid bootstrapping (on the order of 0.1 seconds) and efficient execution of Boolean operations.

A modern trend is the development of **hybrid approaches**, wherein a single system can exploit the advantages of multiple schemes. For instance, the primary computations (linear layers of a neural network) are executed with the efficient CKKS scheme, while nonlinear activation functions (e.g., ReLU) are computed using the fast bootstrapping of TFHE, thereby ensuring optimal performance for the specific task.

5. Known Libraries

The development of open-source libraries is a key factor in the adoption of FHE.

Microsoft SEAL [12] — among the most popular and well-documented libraries. Provides implementations of the BFV and CKKS schemes. Optimized for batch encoding and vectorized arithmetic operations. Does not support TFHE.

PALISADE [13] — a modular library supporting a wide range of schemes (BGV, BFV, CKKS, TFHE). Its modular architecture enables comparison of schemes and selection of the optimal one for a given task.

OpenFHE [14] — the successor to PALISADE and HELib, a universal next-generation platform. It inherits broad scheme support and focuses on performance and cross-platform portability (CPU, GPU, FPGA).

TFHE-rs [15] — the original implementation of the TFHE scheme, designed for ultra-fast bootstrapping.

The choice of library critically depends on the task: machine learning — CKKS in SEAL or OpenFHE; precise arithmetic — BGV/BFV; boolean logic — TFHE.

6. AndKnown Attacks

The security of contemporary FHE schemes relies on the computational hardness of the LWE and RLWE problems. To date, no direct attacks exist that can efficiently solve these problems in properly parameterized systems. Nonetheless, cryptanalysis is concentrated on two primary directions: implementation attacks (parameter cryptanalysis) and side-channel attacks.

Implementation attacks: cryptanalysis based on lattice reduction.

The security of FHE relies on the hardness of LWE/RLWE. No direct attacks exist against correctly parameterized systems.

The attack reduces to finding a short vector in the lattice associated with the LWE problem. Given an LWE sample $(\mathbf{A}, \vec{b} = \mathbf{A}\vec{s} + \vec{e})$ one can construct a lattice:

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{A}) = \{\vec{x} \in Z^m: \exists \vec{z} \in Z^n, \text{ such that } x = \mathbf{A}\vec{z} \bmod q\} \quad (4)$$

The error vector \vec{e} is a short vector in this lattice, and its recovery enables the key to be reconstructed. Current hardness estimates (the BKZ-2021 model, Lattice Estimator [18]) permit selecting parameters with a conservative security margin.

Side-channel attacks.

FHE implementations are vulnerable to timing, power consumption, and electromagnetic interference (EMI) attacks. Attacks can target key extraction during decryption or determine the timing of bootstrapping. Protection requires the application of constant-time algorithms and data masking.

7. Known Cases

Despite computational complexity, FHE is beginning to find application in niche yet critically important areas where data confidentiality outweighs the cost of execution.

— **Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning (Privacy-Preserving ML).** The most actively developing field. Scenarios include training on encrypted data and inference on encrypted models. Pilot projects demonstrate the operation of linear regression and neural networks on data encrypted using CKKS [19].

— **Secure outsourcing of computations and multiparty computations (MPC).** FHE allows data to be processed on an untrusted cloud. The first commercial offerings from cloud providers with support for optimized FHE libraries have emerged.

— **Genomics and Healthcare.** Handling confidential medical and genetic data is an ideal use case for FHE. Researchers can conduct statistical analyses (computation of means, variances, associative studies) on aggregated genomic datasets from multiple hospitals without revealing individual patient records.

— **Financial Sector.** Banks and financial institutions are investigating FHE for:

1) *Collaborative risk analysis.* Several banks can combine their data to construct more accurate credit scoring models or detect fraudulent schemes without revealing the original data to each other.

2) *Confidential auctions and trades.* FHE allows the implementation of protocols in which the winning bid is determined by computations on encrypted bids.

Conclusion

Full homomorphic encryption has made an impressive progression from a theoretical concept to operational implementations. The theoretical foundation of its security is based on the LWE problem, which ensures protection against both classical and quantum attacks. The evolution of schemes has led to the development of optimized constructions (BGV, CKKS, TFHE), each tailored to a specific class of tasks. The advancement of libraries (SEAL, PALISADE, OpenFHE) and the emergence of hardware accelerators progressively reduce barriers to adoption. With proper parameter selection, foundational FHE schemes maintain their security. Use cases in machine learning, healthcare, and finance demonstrate a growing industrial interest. In the long term, FHE is poised to become a standard component of the trust architecture, ensuring data confidentiality throughout its entire lifecycle.

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教育是知识的基础
EDUCATION AS THE BASIS OF KNOWLEDGE

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注释：在当今高科技、瞬息万变的世界中，不确定性日益加剧，智力资本（即公民的知识、信息和专业技能的总和）的重要性日益凸显。一个国家知识、信息的流失，以及创造和运用这些知识和信息的人才的流失，都会削弱国家实力及其经济实体的竞争力。这会导致该国在科学、技术、文化和教育方面相对于其他国家的落后。所有这些都对社会发展、独立性和安全构成严重威胁。

关键词：高等教育，知识，俄罗斯学生，外国学生，俄罗斯联邦；

Annotation. *In today's high-tech, rapidly changing world, which is characterized by increasing uncertainty and the growing significance of intellectual capital (i.e., the aggregate of knowledge, information, and professional skills of its members), a country's loss of knowledge, information, the creators who develop it, and the people who apply knowledge and information in their activities, weakens the nation and the competitiveness of its economic entities. This leads to scientific, technological, cultural, and educational backwardness relative to other countries. All of this poses a serious threat to the development of society, its independence, and its security.*

Keywords: *higher education, knowledge, Russian students, foreign students, The Russian Federation;*

Introduction

To overcome difficulties, neutralize threats, and triumph in struggles against rivals, competitors, adversaries, and enemies, one must be strong and wise. The strength and wisdom of human society contribute to the progressive development of the community, ensuring the economic, cultural-educational, scientific-technological, and military power of the country, enhancing political and diplomatic influence, achieving sovereignty, and securing a worthy place in the world. This truth was formulated by the Chinese sage Sun Tzu: "In war, one must be

both cunning and wise” [1], and is echoed in a poem by Alevtina Veselitskaya [2]: “A weakling cannot survive in this world. Only the one who is merely strong survives in it. Life is a gift, perhaps of fate. Only the strong triumphs in the struggle.”

Knowledge, information, and the people who create and carry them — these are the resources without which it will be impossible to fulfill the state and society’s target objectives:

1) “not just to keep pace with the global economy, but to strive to outpace its dynamics — by unlocking the potential of industries, regions, and territories, by developing ties with foreign partners, through the widespread introduction of advanced technologies, and by mastering new promising areas of the modern economy” [3];

2) “to increase by 2030 the share of domestic high-tech goods and services, created on the basis of proprietary development lines, in the total consumption of such goods and services in the Russian Federation by one and a half times compared to the level of 2023...”; to ensure that by 2030, at least 80 percent of Russian organizations in key economic sectors transition to using basic and applied Russian software in systems that support core production and management processes; to increase by 2030 the share of Russian software used in state bodies, state corporations, state companies, and business entities where the total share of the Russian Federation in the authorized capital exceeds 50 percent, as well as in their affiliated legal entities, to 95 percent” [4];

3) “achieving technological sovereignty of the Russian Federation...; developing the domestic scientific, personnel, and technological base for critical and cross-cutting technologies” [5].

The foundation of knowledge is provided by primary, secondary, and higher education. Shown below is the dynamics of enrollees and students in higher education institutions of the Russian Federation from 2001 to 2023. The sources of information for the conducted research were data from the Federal State Statistics Service, domestic media outlets, and the World Bank.

Higher education in the Russian Federation

The strategic goal of a private commodity producer in a developed market economy is to generate profit [6]. This is achieved through: reducing the cost of creating commodities¹ and delivering them to sales markets or specific consumers, expanding the scale of production and sales, improving logistics, enhancing the quality of production organization and management, and increasing the prices of manufactured commodities.

Regardless of the situation in commodity markets, whether facing internal or external shocks, reducing production costs; optimizing organization, management, logistics, and daily operations; determining production volumes; and setting prices

¹ The definition of a product encompasses the rendering of services.

that correspond to effective demand — all require the professionalism of those making decisions and participating in the process of creating surplus value and generating profit. Underpinning all of this are knowledge, information, and practical experience.

“Information (from Latin *informatio* — explanation, briefing, understanding), a message or signal, a set of data, information considered in the context of its content, structural organization, and dynamics (processes of creation, transmission, perception, use, representation, analysis, storage, etc.)” [7]. “Knowledge is information obtained in a certain way and organized in a certain manner, which reflects certain properties of existing reality in a person’s mind with varying degrees of reliability and objectivity” [8].

A person’s acquisition, accumulation, and updating of knowledge and information begins with receiving an education. Higher professional education in the Russian Federation is provided by the country’s universities. The number of Russians receiving it has significantly decreased since the 2008/2009 academic year (Figure 1, Fig. 2). Moreover, in the 2004/2005 academic year, the number of citizens of the Russian Federation studying in bachelor’s, specialist’s, and master’s degree programs turned out to be 717 thousand less than in the 2000/2001 academic year¹.

Figure 1. The number of students enrolled in higher education institutions of the Russian Federation in the 2000/2001-2024/2025 academic years, excluding foreign students, at the beginning of the academic year, mln persons.

Source: the figure was constructed by the author based on data from the statistical collections “Russian Statistical Yearbook” for a number of years.

¹ Calculated by the author based on Rosstat’s data.

Figure 2. The average annual number of students enrolled in higher education institutions of the Russian Federation in the 2000/2001-2024/2025 academic years, excluding foreign students, at the beginning of the academic year, mln persons.

Source: the figure was constructed by the author based on data from the statistical collections “Russian Statistical Yearbook” for a number of years.

Given the clear trend towards a reduction in the number of Russian students enrolled in domestic universities, the Public Council under the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Russian Federation proposes, starting from the 2026/2027 academic year, “to determine the maximum number of paid places in universities based on their average volume over the last three years. The changes will affect bachelor’s and specialist’s degree programs. The regulation will target fields that are redundant in the labor market, where paid enrollment accounts for more than 50% of total enrollment. Presumably, these are specialties in the fields of marketing, finance, and IT. The regulation of paid enrollment will not affect socially significant and high-demand fields: healthcare, medical sciences, education, and pedagogical sciences” [9].

In addition to citizens of the Russian Federation, citizens of other states also study at Russian universities. It is believed that “educating foreign students brings image-related, socio-cultural, political, and financial advantages to the host country” [10]. Furthermore, foreigners who graduate from Russian universities may remain in the Russian Federation, contributing to the domestic labor market. During the period under review, the number of foreign citizens enrolling in Russian universities is increasing rapidly, while the number of Russians enrolling in universities is simultaneously decreasing (Figures 3, 4).

Figure 3. The number of Russian (R) and foreign (F) students admitted to higher professional education institutions of the Russian Federation for bachelor’s, specialist’s, and master’s degree programs in 2007-2023, thousands persons.

Source: the chart created by the author using the Rosstat’s data.

Figure 4. Average annual number of foreign students studying in the Russian Federation in bachelor’s, specialist’s, and master’s degree programs in the 2001/2002-2024/2025 academic year, thousand people.

Source: the chart created by the author using the Rosstat’s data.

The number of foreign students entering and studying at Russian universities increased sharply after 2011, as was envisaged by the Concept of the State Migration Policy of the Russian Federation for the period up to 2025 (approved by the President of the Russian Federation on June 13, 2012) [11]. Paragraph 24(d) of this concept provides for “an increase in the contingent of students in higher and secondary vocational education institutions from among foreign citizens, primarily citizens of the member states of the Commonwealth of Independent States” [11]. In the 2024/2025 academic year, the share of foreign students enrolled in bachelor’s, specialist’s, and master’s programs out of the total number of students in the above-mentioned programs in the Russian Federation reached 8.23 %, compared to 1.74 % in the 2007/2008 academic year¹.

In Russia, 355.8 thousand foreign students were studying in bachelor’s, specialist’s, and master’s programs in the 2024/2025 academic year [12]. By 2030, according to Decree of the President of the Russian Federation No. 309 dated May 5, 2024 [4, clause 3(b)], and the tasks of the Unified Plan for Achieving the National Development Goals of the Russian Federation until 2030 and for the future up to 2036 [5], this number is expected to increase to 500 thousand people.

And these specialists trained in the Russian Federation “will, for the most part, leave Russia and work in other countries, increasing their scientific and technological level and the level of competition with the Russian Federation, even with the most friendly attitude towards our country... This poses a threat to the technological sovereignty of the Russian Federation and hinders the scientific-technological and cultural-educational leadership of the Russian Federation. Furthermore, the insufficient number of places in higher education institutions for the country’s own citizens causes public discontent, which negatively affects its internal security” [13, pp. 25-26].

The knowledge, information, and practical skills acquired during the education process are used by people in their subsequent public life.

Conclusion

To improve anything, you need to know what, how, and when to improve it, what is needed for that, who will do it, what such an improvement will yield, how much it will cost, and when the costs will be recouped. Answering all these questions requires knowledge, information, professional decision-makers and managers, as well as skilled personnel.

“Information and knowledge are the thermonuclear weapons in the competition of our time. Knowledge is of greater value and possesses greater power than natural resources, gigantic enterprises, or a solid bank account” [14, p. 11]. Therefore, a country’s loss of knowledge, loss of information, and loss of the creators

¹ The decline in enrollment/numbers during the 2020/2021 academic year was due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic.

who develop it and the people who apply knowledge and information in their work weakens the country and poses a threat to its development.

To avoid this, it is necessary not only to increase the number of university students in the specialties required to ensure the scientific-technological sovereignty and leadership of the Russian Federation, but also to improve the system of education and personnel training.

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在经济数字化背景下，神经网络在利益相关者管理中的应用
**THE USE OF NEURAL NETWORKS IN STAKEHOLDER
MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITALIZATION
OF THE ECONOMY**

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摘要：本文探讨了将神经网络应用于现代企业利益相关者管理的可能性，包括分析、自动化沟通和预测利益相关者行为。作者分析了神经网络如何作为识别、分类和预测利益相关者行为的工具，如何制定有效的利益相关者参与策略，以及如何辅助管理决策。此外，本文还探讨了阻碍神经网络在利益相关者管理领域广泛应用的挑战和局限性。

关键词：神经网络，机器学习，利益相关者管理，利益相关者关系管理，管理决策，公司治理。

Abstract. *The article examines the possibilities of applying neural networks in stakeholder management of a modern business enterprise for analysis, communication automation, and forecasting stakeholder behavior. The author considers cases where neural networks can act as a tool for identifying, classifying, and forecasting stakeholder behavior; developing effective stakeholder engagement strategies, and making management decisions in this field. The issue of challenges and limitations hindering the widespread adoption of neural networks in the field of stakeholder management is also examined.*

Keywords: *neural networks, machine learning, stakeholder management, stakeholder relationship management, managerial decision-making, corporate governance.*

Over the past decade, there has been growing interest in artificial intelligence, particularly neural networks, in Russia. Neural networks are algorithmic models capable of learning by relying on large volumes of data, as well as performing tasks that were previously achievable only by humans. Neural networks emulate the functioning of the human brain by analyzing information, identifying trends, and drawing certain conclusions. The development of neural networks has progressed from simple theoretical models to complex systems across diverse fields

of scientific knowledge, affecting management, education, medicine, marketing, and others [1]. The relevance of this article is determined by ongoing scientific and technological advancement that is changing the approach to classical management methods. Challenges of modern society, such as the need for rapid decision-making, analysis of large databases, and the trend towards individualization of services, impose new demands and require managers to exhibit new behaviors. In such conditions, neural networks become an important tool that allows, all other things being equal, an increase in the efficiency and quality of management processes within a company, ensuring the optimization of workflows, as well as improving interaction with clients with the expectation of long-term cooperation [2].

Neural networks currently represent an important tool in practical applications, for example:

- in automating routine tasks, processing documentation, managing records, and scheduling meetings, thereby freeing time for addressing critical strategic tasks;
- in collecting analytical data in real time, revealing hidden trends and patterns, and enhancing the manager's informedness in making managerial decisions;
- in developing strategies for personalizing interactions with company personnel and clients through the analysis of customer preferences;
- when constructing forecasts based on data analyzed by neural networks, enabling the reduction of risks in their activities and the strengthening of their competitive positions [3].

The advantages of employing neural networks in managerial work are undeniable. Among them are:

- enhanced labor efficiency and productivity through the use of algorithms in processing large datasets required for rapid decision-making;
- minimization of errors in managerial decisions, as neural networks analyze historical data and forecast with high accuracy;
- freeing up time for the development of strategic plans;
- optimizing communication processes in the team and creating a harmonious and productive work atmosphere by improving interaction among team members [4].

Neural networks eliminate intuitive managerial decision-making by relying on data and facts. Successful implementation of neural networks should be based on the evaluation of existing processes and the identification of areas where current technologies in the company can be utilized more effectively.

Stakeholder management is a managerial process related to the formation, strengthening, and maintenance of sustainable relationships with the stakeholders of a business company (such as employees, clients, investors, suppliers, local communities). The goal of stakeholder management is to ensure stakeholder loyalty towards the company's activities or its specific project, to minimize corporate

risks and conflict situations that, in some cases, may threaten the execution of a particular project [5].

Modern neural networks are capable of processing large volumes of data from various sources (such as databases, non-financial reports, social networks, and news feeds). Neural networks are able to make decisions rapidly based on patterns and relationships, enabling them to detect changes in relationships with stakeholders with substantial time savings and to adapt management decisions to evolving conditions of both the external and internal environment of a business company [6].

Neural network-based solutions can be used in stakeholder management in several promising areas (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Areas of application of neural networks in stakeholder management (Author's own development)

Identification of stakeholders is an important stage of stakeholder management [7]. Neural networks can be used to automate, accelerate, and improve the quality of this process. Neural networks can be used to analyze the relationships between various stakeholders to understand their influence on, and dependence upon, the business company and its projects. Identification of stakeholders is typically conducted based on the analysis of the following criteria: formal responsibility, influence, proximity, dependence, representativeness, payment amount, and the degree of informational impact. All these criteria can have numerical characteristics and, therefore, can be analyzed through the application of appropriate algorithms.

Classification of stakeholders is carried out based on the analysis of various factors determining the strength of the stakeholder's influence over the company or the degree of the company's dependence on the stakeholder. This assists managers in determining the priority of various stakeholder groups and developing corresponding management and information strategies. Neural networks can be used to cluster stakeholders based on various factors such as their influence, power, and interest in the company. A neural network can be trained on data regarding stakeholder behavior, such as communication frequency and participation in company projects. Therefore, the neural network can identify groups of stakeholders exhibiting similar behavior and classify them based on these characteristics [8].

Analysis of social networks, news feeds, and websites. Neural networks can be employed to analyze data from social networks to understand stakeholders' attitudes and responses to specific media messages, actions, or managerial decisions of the company. This enables company managers to make more substantiated managerial decisions, considering the needs and expectations of stakeholders. Neural networks can be applied to analyze large volumes of text, which vary significantly in style and quality (ranging from random social media posts to the analysis of official media communications from business enterprises and government agencies). This enables the use of neural network solutions as a tool for identifying context rather than merely the frequency of company mentions [8].

Forecasting stakeholder behavior. Stakeholders of a company may lose or gain significance throughout the implementation of a corporate project. Neural networks can be employed to forecast stakeholder behavior based on detected dependencies, trends, and dynamics. Following the machine learning stage, neural networks can be relatively easily integrated into existing management systems. This assists managers in taking proactive measures to develop appropriate strategic initiatives in stakeholder management within a business company [9].

Automation of communications. Modern neural networks can be utilized to automate communication processes with stakeholders, such as sending personalized messages, responding to frequently asked questions, implementing feedback mechanisms, and addressing complaints. This will help save time, resources, and financial means, as well as significantly improve the quality of communications. Automatic tone detection, along with the classification of stakeholder requests by topics and types, can facilitate their rapid and efficient processing. The most promising direction for the development of neural network tools remains the personalization of communications — the formation of an individualized information strategy that addresses the needs and interests of specific stakeholders or stakeholder groups [10].

Monitoring and risk management. Neural networks can be utilized for monitoring and managing risks associated with stakeholders. For example, they can assist in identifying and preventing risks related to stakeholder dissatisfaction or

their negative impact on the company's reputation. One notable capability is real-time risk monitoring through the analysis of data on stakeholders and external factors that may influence the development of risks concerning the company or its project. Risk assessment, determination of the probability and potential damage from risks, the implementation of risk management strategies (such as insurance, stakeholder portfolio diversification, and reputation management), as well as the automated generation of risk reports to inform company management, may substantially simplify and expedite the process of identifying stakeholder risks and taking measures to minimize them [11].

Challenges and barriers to the use of neural networks in stakeholder management [12]. Neural networks are increasingly utilized in various domains of corporate governance and communication processes. Their advantages in stakeholder management are evident: automation of processes, personalization of communication with stakeholders, potential enhancement of the quality of managerial decisions, as well as improvements in management efficiency and effectiveness, labor cost savings, and the ability to increase the agility and effectiveness of operations. However, despite these numerous advantages, there exist several challenges and barriers that considerably hinder and constrain the integration of neural networks both in stakeholder management specifically and in corporate governance more broadly.

One of the fundamental problems is the quality of data used in machine learning. Neural networks are data-driven, and the quality of this data is critical for the accuracy and reliability of the model. If the data is incomplete, inaccurate, or contains errors, this will inevitably result in inaccurate outcomes and erroneous managerial decisions. Data concerning stakeholders often requires expert interpretation and evaluation. Such data is non-financial and non-quantitative in nature, which complicates processing and increases the level of subjectivity.

Data-related problems also include their scarcity. In some cases, it may be impossible to collect a sufficient amount of data to train the neural network (for example, when dealing with new stakeholders). This significantly limits the accuracy and reliability of the model, increases the likelihood of errors, and consequently reduces its applicability for practical use.

One of the less obvious, yet most significant problems in using neural networks in stakeholder management is the difficulty in explaining the results obtained. Neural networks are often perceived as a 'black box,' and their mechanism remains complex to understand. In practice, this creates an unexpected problem in the area of managerial decision-making — managers do not understand how the neural network model arrives at these results. A justified doubt arises — are they mistaken?

Responsibility can also become an issue when using neural networks for decision-making both in stakeholder management and managerial decisions in general. An unresolved question remains: if the neural network model errs and

makes an incorrect decision, who will bear responsibility for the consequences of that decision?

One of the key challenges is the relatively high initial costs required to integrate neural networks into stakeholder management systems. The training and deployment of neural networks may demand significant temporal and technological resources from a company, which can pose an obstacle to their use in managing relationships with stakeholders.

Under sanctions-related restrictions, a challenge in the use of neural networks in corporate governance may be technological dependence. In the event that technologies cease to operate or if access to them is restricted (for example, access to cloud services may be blocked), this may create difficulties for the organization. It is evident that these problems and obstacles should not impede the adoption of neural networks in stakeholder management. However, they must be taken into account when implementing neural networks within the managerial processes of a business organization.

Thus, the application of neural networks in stakeholder management can bring significant benefits to business companies. Neural networks can assist in forecasting stakeholder behavior, automating communication, monitoring risks, and supporting managerial decision-making. However, as demonstrated in the article, there are several challenges and obstacles that must be considered when applying neural networks in this domain, including data quality and scarcity, the complexity of interpreting results, issues of accountability for managerial decision outcomes, technological dependence, and high costs. To successfully implement neural networks in stakeholder management, companies must carefully evaluate these challenges and implement measures to resolve them. This may involve rigorous validation and use of representative data, ensuring transparency of the neural network model, compliance with all applicable data protection laws and regulations, as well as meticulous risk planning and management.

When applying neural networks in stakeholder management, it is essential to consider ethical aspects. Some of these include: transparency of decisions — companies must explain the foundations on which neural network conclusions are based; data protection — when processing large volumes of data, companies are required to implement measures to secure it; algorithmic bias — algorithms trained on biased data may make unfair decisions. This necessitates that companies pay particular attention to the data used and the methods by which they train their models; responsibility for errors — a clear allocation of responsibility will help prevent legal complexities and disputes [13].

To address ethical issues, companies must develop clear strategies that facilitate integrating ethical principles into every aspect of their operations. For example, by creating a code of ethics for the use of artificial intelligence and utilizing diverse and representative data to train models.

Overall, neural networks represent a highly effective tool for managing modern business companies. However, their successful application requires thorough planning. Companies should be prepared at the initial stage to invest money, time, and resources in machine learning and the implementation of neural networks within the corporate governance system. In this context, neural networks can become a factor in establishing sustainable relationships between business companies and their stakeholders.

Neural networks represent a powerful tool capable of significantly simplifying production processes; however, despite their advanced analytical capabilities, the final decision must remain with a human. Only humans are capable of evaluating moral and ethical aspects, considering unpredictable circumstances, and accounting for social, cultural, and emotional factors that are inaccessible to machine analysis. Moreover, responsibility for the consequences of decisions rests with humans, not with algorithms [14]. Thus, artificial neural networks should serve as decision-support tools rather than replace human judgment. The optimal approach combines the technological capabilities of artificial intelligence with human experience, intuition, and critical thinking.

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全球经济动荡背景下的预算政策：比较分析
**BUDGETARY POLICY IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL
ECONOMIC TURBULENCE: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS**

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摘要：本文探讨了在全球经济动荡和地缘政治风险日益加剧的背景下，主要经济体的预算政策。作者基于2024年的数据，对美国、中国、德国、日本和俄罗斯等国的宏观经济指标和财政可持续性进行了比较分析。本研究考察了当前预算赤字、政府收支结构、税收负担以及政府债务累积动态之间的关系。特别关注在结构转型和外部约束条件下，俄罗斯预算体系的回旋余地。基于实证数据，本文得出结论：财政政策是确保长期宏观经济稳定和国家安全的工具。

关键词：预算政策，政府债务，财政赤字，税收负担，宏观经济稳定，比较分析，地缘政治风险，金融安全，经济动荡

Abstract. *The article examines aspects of budgetary policy in leading global economies amid increasing global economic turbulence and geopolitical risks. The authors conduct a comparative analysis of macroeconomic indicators and fiscal sustainability in countries including the USA, China, Germany, Japan, and Russia, based on 2024 data. This study examines the relationship between current budget deficits, the structure of government revenues and expenditures, tax burden, and the dynamics of accumulated government debt. Special attention is devoted to assessing the room for maneuver available to the Russian budgetary system under conditions of structural transformations and external constraints. Based on empirical data, the article concludes that fiscal policy plays a key role as an instrument for ensuring long-term macroeconomic stability and national security.*

Keywords: *budgetary policy, government debt, fiscal deficit, tax burden, macroeconomic stability, comparative analysis, geopolitical risks, financial security, economic turbulence*

The contemporary global financial architecture is experiencing a profound transformation driven by the exhaustion of previous economic growth models and rising geopolitical tensions. Under these conditions, the budgetary policy of states is no longer merely an instrument of internal resource allocation, but becomes a key mechanism for ensuring national security and macroeconomic stability. Questions concerning the efficiency of public expenditures, the determination of optimal levels of debt burden, and the balancing of budget deficits come to the forefront in discussions among both theorists and practitioners of public administration.

A key focus of contemporary scientific research in the field of budgetary regulation is the analysis of how national budget strategies adapt to the growing pressures from global markets and structural risks. The methodological and practical aspects of the functioning of government budgetary systems in developed countries, along with the mechanisms of their fiscal regulation, are examined in detail in the works of Ya. V. Khomenko and E. V. Kubrak [1]. The experience of foreign countries in the formation of budget revenues, thoroughly analyzed by Ya. O. Zaveryukha and A. S. Zaveryukha [2], is of considerable interest for domestic practice. This becomes particularly relevant under the conditions of the transformation of Russia's foreign economic relations. The role of tax administration as a fundamental tool for enhancing economic efficiency and the competitiveness of the national economy is emphasized in the research of A. V. Rosenberg [3]. An important theoretical contribution to the understanding of the new role of budgetary policy is made by the works of L. A. Omelyanovich and T. Yu. Manzhula, who examine financial instruments within the framework of the supply-side economic model, and also study budgetary policy as a key regulator of socio-economic development [4-5]. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis of various budgetary models enables not only the identification of effective practices but also the determination of potential directions for the adaptation and development of the Russian budgetary system in response to contemporary challenges, which in turn determines the choice of methodology and empirical base for this study.

In order to understand the macroeconomic context within which modern states operate and the structural constraints shaping their budgetary choices, it is essential to analyze the fundamental indicators of debt sustainability among leading global economies. The data presented in the following Table 1 enable a comparison of countries with fundamentally different development models — ranging from global financial centers to the largest emerging markets — and an assessment of the actual burden of public debt borne by national economies and their citizens.

Table 1. Macroeconomic Context and Debt Sustainability of Countries, 2024 [6-8]

Country	GDP, billion USD	GDP per capita, USD	Government debt, % of GDP	Absolute government debt, billion USD	Tax burden per capita, USD	Government debt burden per capita, USD
USA	29,185.1	85812	120.79	35,253.0	9345	103682
China	18,748.0	13313	88.33	16559.0	1017	11759
Germany	4659.5	54990	63.89	2976.0	5857	35132
France	3162.2	46204	113.67	3595.0	10658	52528
Japan	4026.2	32498	236.66	9527.0	3697	76935
United Kingdom	3645.6	52648	101.23	3689.0	14191	53290
Italy	2372.1	40224	135.29	3209.0	9937	54425
Canada	2241.2	54473	110.77	2483.0	7755	60353
Brazil	2171.3	10214	87.28	1895.0	1574	8915
India	3909.1	2711	81.29	3178.0	183	2203
Russia	2161.2	14795	20.30	439.0	1784	3003

The selection of countries is justified by their significance in the global economy and the diversity of economic models. This group includes the three largest economies in the world by nominal GDP — the USA, China, and Japan — whose fiscal policies exert a global influence. The G7 countries (USA, Japan, Germany, France, United Kingdom, Italy, Canada) are nearly fully represented, allowing for a comparative analysis of developed economies with high income levels. For contrast and dynamic assessment, the largest emerging markets — Brazil, India, and Russia — are included, whose growth trajectories and budgetary challenges differ markedly from those of the ‘golden billion.’ This selection permits comparison not only of absolute indicators but also of structural features: from mature economies with high debt and income levels to emerging ones with low debt but limited fiscal maneuvering capacity.

The analysis of the data in Table 1 reveals key patterns of debt sustainability and tax burden in the countries compared, demonstrating a deep interconnection between the level of economic development, the scale of public debt, and the financial burden borne by citizens.

The most pronounced differentiation is observed within the group of developed economies. The USA, possessing the highest total government debt (35,253.0 billion USD), exhibits a relatively moderate debt-to-GDP ratio (120.79%), yet this coexists with an extremely high debt burden per capita (103,682 USD), surpassing that of any other country on the list. This indicates a unique model where the scale of the economy and a high tax burden enable servicing an enormous absolute debt. Japan presents a contrasting yet distinctive case: it has a record government

debt-to-GDP ratio (236.66%), while the debt burden per capita (76,935 dollars) remains lower than that of the USA. This can be attributed to a lower tax burden (3,697 dollars) and specific features of domestic debt financing. European countries such as France and Italy, characterized by high debt-to-GDP ratios (113.67% and 135.29%, respectively), also exhibit significant debt burdens per capita (52,528 and 54,425 dollars), which correlates with their elevated tax burdens (10,658 and 9,937 dollars).

A different situation is emerging in developing economies. China, despite possessing the second largest absolute debt (16,559.0 billion dollars) and a moderate debt-to-GDP ratio (88.33%), exhibits significantly lower per capita burden indicators: debt (11,759 dollars) and tax burden (1,017 dollars). This reflects a model in which the debt burden is distributed across a vast population, while tax burdens remain relatively low. India and Russia exemplify cases with a low debt burden per capita (2,203 and 3,003 USD respectively), directly associated with their markedly lower tax burdens (183 and 1,784 USD). Russia is particularly notable for having the lowest debt-to-GDP ratio among all countries (20.30%) and, correspondingly, the smallest absolute debt (439 billion USD).

Therefore, the data presented suggest that debt sustainability relative to GDP and its actual burden on the citizen are not always directly correlated. The first is a relative macroeconomic indicator, while the second is determined by two specific factors — the total amount of government obligations and the size of the country's population. Developed economies with a high GDP per capita typically establish a financing system based on a strong domestic tax base. This enables them to combine substantial tax revenues with a high debt burden per capita. Conversely, developing countries, even with a significant absolute debt, often exhibit relatively moderate pressure on their citizens. This is explained by the combination of a broad demographic base and still relatively low levels of tax burden. Russia is distinct in this context: its conservative approach to borrowing results in a minimal burden on both the economy as a whole and the individual.

Static indicators of government debt are merely the consequence and realized outcome of prolonged budgetary policy. They originate in the current budgetary policy of the state. It is precisely the annual fiscal decisions — on the amount of revenues and the direction of expenditures — that determine the deficit or surplus. The continual accumulation of deficits gradually transforms into the volume of government debt. Therefore, to assess long-term prospects and risks, it is necessary to analyze the current fiscal condition, as presented in Table 2. This demonstrates how the described models — for example, the strong tax potential of developed countries or Russia's cautious approach — are reflected in actual budgetary figures. The table also assists in addressing the key question: whether the observed budget deficit constitutes a profound structural issue or a temporary cyclical phenomenon.

Table 2. Government budget indicators and fiscal burden, 2024 [9-11]

Country	Budget revenues, billion USD	Budget expenditures, billion USD	Budget deficit, billion USD	Deficit, % of GDP	Share of expenditures in GDP, %	Tax revenues as a percentage of GDP
USA	8852.1	10971.5	-2119.4	-7.3	37.6	10.89
China	4800.2	6177.1	-1376.9	-7.3	33.0	7.64
Germany	2178.0	2306.5	-128.5	-2.8	49.5	10.64
France	1624.4	1807.4	-183.0	-5.8	57.2	23.08
Japan	1486.6	1586.4	-99.8	-2.5	39.4	11.38
United Kingdom	1395.6	1605.1	-209.5	-5.8	44.0	26.96
Italy	1117.6	1199.4	-81.7	-3.5	50.6	24.71
Canada	953.8	1002.0	-48.2	-2.2	44.7	14.23
Brazil	843.2	987.1	-143.9	-6.9	45.5	15.41
India	816.9	1105.3	-288.4	-7.4	28.3	6.73
Russia	778.0	826.6	-48.6	-2.3	38.2	12.07

The analysis of the state budget indicators and fiscal burden for the countries presented in Table 2 in 2024 makes it possible to identify several stable models of budgetary policy and to pinpoint key challenges in fiscal sustainability. The data demonstrate that all countries operate with budget deficits; however, the scale, financing structure, and their relationship to macroeconomic parameters differ substantially.

The group of the largest economies — the USA and China — is characterized by the greatest absolute deficit amounts (over 1 trillion dollars) and an equally high deficit level relative to GDP (–7.3%). However, the fiscal models of these countries differ fundamentally. The USA exhibits a high expenditure-to-GDP ratio (37.6%) alongside relatively moderate tax revenues (10.89% of GDP). This reflects a model reliant on substantial borrowing to finance social and military spending while maintaining a competitive tax rate. In China, by contrast, the expenditure-to-GDP ratio is lower (33.0%), while tax revenues account for only 7.64% of GDP. This imbalance reflects alternative sources of budget revenue (non-tax revenues from state-owned enterprises) and potentially implicit fiscal stimulus through the quasi-state sector. A shared challenge for both countries lies in ensuring long-term sustainability while maintaining such high deficits.

Western European countries present a more consolidated yet internally diverse picture. Germany stands out with the most balanced budget among the major economies, exhibiting a deficit of only –2.8% of GDP, combining the highest share of expenditures in GDP within the group (49.5%) with high tax revenues (10.64% of GDP). This reflects the classical welfare state model characterized

by a robust tax base. France and Italy, with similar deficit levels of approximately -5.8% and -3.5% , respectively, exhibit exceptionally high tax revenue shares (23.08% and 24.71% of GDP) alongside record levels of government spending in the economy (57.2% and 50.6%). This indicates a model where a chronic deficit exists despite maximum fiscal burden, signaling structural problems in controlling expenditures or low efficiency of the tax system. The United Kingdom, with a deficit of -5.8% , occupies an intermediate position with a high tax burden (26.96%) and a moderate expenditure share (44%).

Japan represents a special case with an exceptionally low deficit (-2.5% of GDP) alongside an enormous level of government debt, as noted in previous analysis. A low deficit combined with a moderate tax burden (11.38%) and an expenditure share of 39.4% indicates stringent current budgetary discipline; however, this is insufficient to reduce the accumulated debt burden.

Pronounced disparities exist among developing economies. Brazil exhibits a high deficit (-6.9%) alongside a substantial tax burden (15.41%) and a large share of government expenditures (45.5%), characteristic of a country with a developed social welfare system but unstable revenues. India has the highest deficit in the sample (-7.4% of GDP), coupled with record-low tax revenues (6.73% of GDP) and a relatively low government expenditure share in the economy (28.3%). This reflects the model of a developing country, where the budget is chronically underfunded, and the fiscal capacity (tax base) remains underdeveloped, which limits the scope for public investment. Russia, in turn, stands out with the worst absolute deficit figure (-2.3% of GDP) alongside a balanced fiscal stance. A moderate tax burden (12.07%) and expenditure share (38.2%) point to a conservative budgetary policy focused on restraining expenditures even amid relatively low revenues.

The analysis reveals three key fiscal paradoxes in contemporary budgetary policy. The first of these is the paradox of a high tax burden: substantial tax revenues (as in France and Italy) do not necessarily guarantee a balanced budget. The second paradox is illustrated by Japan, where a relatively moderate current deficit exists alongside a colossal accumulated government debt. Finally, the third paradox is observed in countries with a low tax burden: it can be accompanied either by a chronic large deficit (India) or a fairly balanced budget (Russia).

These contrasts demonstrate that long-term budget sustainability is not determined solely by the size of the deficit or the level of taxation. Much more important is their consistency with fundamental conditions: the structure of the economy, the quality of government institutions, and the trajectory of the dynamics of the already accumulated debt.

However, sustainability is not only the ability to finance debt but also the capacity to fulfill key social obligations to society without jeopardizing financial stability. The size of the deficit and debt directly constrains the 'space' available

for expenditures on healthcare, education, and social support. To evaluate how the identified fiscal models — namely, the high tax burden in developed countries versus Russia’s fiscal conservatism — influence social priorities, it is necessary to examine the structure of budgetary expenditures presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Structure of Social Budgetary Expenditures, 2024 [12-13]

Country	Healthcare Expenditures, % of Budget	Education Expenditures, % of Budget	Total Share of Social Expenditures, % of Budget	Healthcare spending per capita, dollars	Education spending per capita, dollars
USA	24.74	11.31	36.05	2490	1137
China	8.80	11.91	20.71	544	736
Germany	20.46	10.69	31.15	1131	591
France	15.25	9.12	24.37	1045	625
Japan	23.42	7.52	30.94	925	297
United Kingdom	20.67	10.64	31.31	910	468
Italy	11.85	7.41	19.26	599	374
Canada	18.64	10.65	29.29	833	476
Brazil	9.00	12.93	21.93	409	587
India	4.46	14.16	18.62	126	400
Russia	13.76	8.94	22.70	527	342

The analysis of the structure of social expenditures in 2024, as presented in Table 3, highlights considerable variations in government priorities and the distribution of resources between the key sectors of healthcare and education. The data demonstrate that both the proportion of such expenditures within the budget and their absolute per capita values are directly correlated with the overall level of economic development of the country. However, the precise proportions are determined by national institutional models and historically developed social security systems.

The United States is the undisputed leader in social spending per capita, which directly results from the budget’s substantial share in the economy and its enormous absolute scale. The total share of social expenditures in the American budget (36.05%) ranks among the highest in the sample. A key priority here is healthcare, which receives almost a quarter of all funding (24.74%), providing a record \$2,490 per capita. This reflects the high cost of medical services within a predominantly insurance-based system. Spending on education (\$1,137 per capita) is also substantial, though its budget share (11.31%) is comparable to that of other developed nations. This model indicates a significant fiscal burden on the budget to sustain the social sector.

Western European countries — Germany, France, and the United Kingdom — exhibit a more balanced model. The total share of social expenditures fluctuates between 24% and 31% of the budget; however, their structure varies. Germany and the United Kingdom have similarly high shares of expenditures on healthcare (approximately 20-21%) and education (approximately 10-11%), resulting in healthcare spending of 900-1,100 dollars per capita. France, despite having the highest share of government expenditures in GDP in Europe, directs a comparatively smaller portion of the budget directly to social needs (24.37%), with an emphasis on healthcare (15.25%). This may indicate a reallocation of funds favoring other social items, such as pensions or insurance, which are not covered in this analysis. Japan, characterized by a high share of healthcare expenditures (23.42%) and a moderate overall social burden on the budget (30.94%), stands out due to its exceptionally low absolute spending on education (\$297 per capita). This is a unique case among developed economies, likely reflecting the specifics of demographics and the system of education financing.

Emerging economies such as China, Brazil, and India are characterized by a significantly lower share of the budget allocated to social objectives (18-22%) and, consequently, substantially lower absolute per capita expenditures. The principal distinction between them concerns their priorities. China and Brazil demonstrate a relatively balanced allocation of funds between healthcare and education. At the same time, Brazil stands out with the highest budget share allocated to education among the sample countries (12.93%). India represents an extreme case with the lowest share of healthcare expenditures (4.46%) and the world's lowest absolute healthcare spending (\$126 per capita), which correlates with previously identified low overall tax revenues and the share of government expenditures in GDP. However, India allocates the largest budget share to education among the sample countries (14.16%), which in absolute terms amounts to only \$400 per capita. This reflects an attempt to offset resource shortages by concentrating them in a sector strategically important for development.

Russia occupies an intermediate position. The total share of social expenditures in the budget (22.70%) is comparable to that of other developing economies. The expenditure structure is skewed towards healthcare (13.76% of the budget, 527 dollars per capita), whereas education spending (8.94% of the budget, 342 dollars per capita) ranks among the lowest in the sample in both relative and absolute terms. This model reflects the response to current demographic and epidemiological challenges within constrained budgetary possibilities.

Thus, the analysis enables the conclusion that three primary models of social sector financing exist. The first is the 'high-cost' model (USA), in which substantial budgetary resources ensure high absolute per capita expenditures, particularly in healthcare. The second is the 'balanced institutional' model (Western Europe,

Canada, Japan), where relative expenditure shares and their absolute levels are determined by established social insurance and state welfare systems. The third is the 'resource-constrained model with priority selection' (developing countries), where limited overall budgetary resources compel governments to make a strategic choice in favor of either healthcare (as a factor of current stability) or education (as a factor of long-term growth), a contrast vividly illustrated by the cases of India and Brazil. For all countries, the key challenge remains achieving a balance between the financial sustainability of the budget, as reflected in the preceding tables, and the necessity of financing social commitments that directly impact human capital and long-term economic potential.

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实施KPI以提高葡萄酒行业组织的劳动生产率和竞争力
**IMPLEMENTATION OF KPI TO INCREASE LABOR
PRODUCTIVITY AND COMPETITIVENESS OF THE
WINEMAKING INDUSTRY ORGANIZATION**

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摘要：本文探讨了劳动生产率与葡萄酒企业竞争力之间的关系。作者分析了影响葡萄酒生产劳动效率的具体因素，例如陈酿和装瓶等工艺流程，以及对员工能力的要求。文章指出，劳动生产率的增长直接取决于员工的专业能力水平和积极性，这在进口替代的背景下成为员工竞争力的关键因素。文章提出了一种评估员工劳动贡献的方案，该方案考虑了行业特性和酒庄劳动力资源的质量。

关键词：劳动生产率，关键绩效指标，竞争力，数字化，葡萄酒行业。

Abstract. *The article examines the relationship between labor productivity and the competitiveness of a wine enterprise. The authors analyze the specific factors that affect labor efficiency in winemaking, such as the technological cycles of aging and bottling, as well as the requirements for staff competence. It is argued that the growth of labor productivity is directly dependent on the level of professional competencies and motivation of employees, which becomes a key factor in the*

competitiveness of employees in the context of import substitution. A scheme for assessing the labor contribution of personnel is proposed, taking into account the industry-specific features and the quality of the winery's labor resources.

Keywords. *Labor productivity, KPI, competitiveness, digitalization, wine industry.*

Relevance of the Research Topic. At present, the economy of the Russian Federation is confronted with new challenges that necessitate adaptation to altered operational conditions. These challenges stem not only from the imperative to achieve a significant technological breakthrough but also from the need to effectively address a broad spectrum of tasks amid heightened uncertainty. The continuously increasing sanctions and evolving global political landscape contribute to the growth of systemic risks, which in turn impede the successful advancement of digital transformation in industries and slow the adoption of innovative solutions. All the aforementioned factors establish additional prerequisites for the development of competencies and the improvement of employees' competitiveness. The Russian economy is confronting such stringent conditions for the first time, which accentuates the significance of exploring opportunities for the advancement of professional skills and employee competitiveness within the context of the contemporary economic environment.

A defining feature of the current stage of socio-economic development is the extensive adoption of information and digital technologies. This process causes fundamental changes across all spheres of social life, including the social and labor domain. One of its consequences is the transformation of the labor market structure, characterized by the emergence of several new professions and the disappearance of outdated ones.

The dependence of earnings from primary employment on workers' labor input in cases of higher labor efficiency, expressed as a percentage of the total number of respondents. At the same time, the study results demonstrated that persistent issues regarding the relationship between workers' labor efforts and their material remuneration have not been resolved over the years. According to respondents, within their organizations there is a weak link between employees' labor contribution and the amount of remuneration, and the incentive function of wages — which is intended to increase employees' interest and motivation to work better (both quantitatively and qualitatively) over an extended period — is not realized in practice. The majority of respondents are convinced that their earnings from their main job will not change, whether they exert greater effort (53.9%) or less effort (46.3%).

The winemaking industry of Krasnodar Krai is one of the key segments of the region's agro-industrial complex, characterized by substantial export potential and cultural-historical significance.

To develop an understanding of the operation of the winemaking industry within the territory of Russia, let us examine wine production volumes in Russia measured in million decaliters over the period 2014-2021. Analysis of the data indicates a sharp increase in wine production volumes between 2015 and 2016, which can be attributed to two significant factors: the accession of Crimea to Russia and an effective marketing strategy for promoting winemaking products in the market. A slight decline was observed during the period from 2017 to 2019, which can be attributed to the closure of small-scale wine enterprises within Russia. It is important to emphasize that, despite the challenges, in 2020 Russia ranked 12th globally, producing 4.4 million decaliters of wine, accounting for 1.7% of the total global production volume. Despite the trend of decreasing production volumes, statistics indicate an improvement in 2021 (+0.1), as the development of winemaking in the Krasnodar region, as well as in Crimea and Moscow, has positively influenced the overall performance of the industry.

Despite the evident importance of developing competencies and enhancing employee competitiveness, the following issues remain controversial and unresolved to date:

- the imperfection of the theoretical framework for analyzing the impact of new economic conditions on the labor market. Many studies focus on the technical aspects of digitalization, neglecting the social and psychological dimensions. It is necessary to develop interdisciplinary approaches that integrate economic theory, sociology, psychology, and other sciences to better understand how technological changes affect employee behavior and labor organization processes.

- obsolete and insufficiently accounting for the specifics of the digital economy methods for assessing competence and competitiveness;

- challenges in the practical implementation of training and personnel development programs in contemporary organizations.

Figure 1 illustrates the types of influence on labor productivity in the wine-making industry.

The principal enterprises in the viticulture and winemaking sector of the Krasnodar region include the following:

- Abrau-Durso. Production of wine, champagne, and blended wines. Address: Novorossiysk, Abrau-Durso village, Promyshlennaya Street, 19. The total production volume is approximately 270-280 million bottles of wine per year. The total vineyard area ranges from 6,700 to 9,000 hectares. Annual visitor attendance is between 300,000 and 350,000 tourists. Museum and historical complex of the wine factory. Art park 'Abrau-Dyurso.' Abrau Light Gallery. For enotourists in Abrau-Dyurso, the following options are available, for example: tours of the sparkling wine factory with tastings. Tours without tastings. VIP tour.

Figure 1 — Direct and inverse relationships between the influence on labor productivity and competitiveness of organizations in the winemaking industry.

‘Kuban-Vino.’ Full-cycle production: from seedling to bottle. Operates three production facilities: in Temryuk, Stanitsa Starotitarovskaya, and Stanitsa Taman-skaya of the Temryuk district. The total production volume is approximately 80-100 million. bottles of wine per year, with a total vineyard area ranging from 9,000 to

10,000 hectares. In 2025, the company’s enotourism segment attracted 16,000 visitors. Center of Classical Winemaking. Chateau Tamagne Enology Center. Industrial Winemaking Center. Villa Aristov — a digital gallery, Aristov Wine Art, featuring works by artists inspired by the theme of wine.

Thus, an analysis and evaluation of the competitiveness of the enterprise’s employees were conducted using the example of LLC ‘Kuban-Vino,’ the results of which are clearly illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 — Results of the analysis and assessment of employee competitiveness at LLC ‘Kuban-Vino’

The principal key performance indicators in winemaking are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3 — KPIs as a system for improving labor productivity and competitiveness of organizations in the winemaking industry

Conclusions: The implementation of a balanced KPI system enables the avoidance of subjective assessments of labor performance. For winemaking enterprises, significant indicators include not only financial metrics but also operational ones (vine preservation rate, raw material processing speed, reduction of losses during bottling), which directly correlate with employee productivity. It has been established that labor productivity in winemaking increases not through strict regulation, but through the implementation of well-designed KPIs (evaluation of product defects, sensory indicators). This challenges the stereotype that high productivity is synonymous with a high work pace. In winemaking, the key conclusion is that optimal productivity is achieved by balancing the volume of processing with organoleptic control.

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伊朗冲突：未来地缘经济中的潜在贸易决策
**IRAN CONFLICT: POTENTIAL TRADE DECISIONS
IN THE GEOECONOMICS OF THE FUTURE**

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摘要：本文分析了经典的贸易经济学方法，并考察了其在伊朗-美国冲突背景下的演变。这场冲突加剧了中东和近东地区的主要区域战争。

关键词：伊朗伊斯兰共和国、美国、以色列、中国、阿联酋、俄罗斯、地缘政治、地缘经济学、世界贸易组织、碳氢化合物、丹尼尔·卡尼曼、罗伯特·泰勒、石油市场、食品市场、全球气候战略。

Abstract. *This article provides an analysis of classical economic approaches to trade and examines their evolution within the context of the Iran-American conflict, which is exacerbating the major regional war in the Middle and Near East.*

Keywords: *IRI, USA, Israel, China, UAE, Russia, geopolitics, geoeconomics, WTO, hydrocarbons, D. Kahneman, R. Thaler, oil market, food market, GCSS. Taler, oil market, food market, GCSS.*

The contemporary expectation regarding the evolution of theories that describe the interaction between the state and business in foreign trade reflects the general trajectory of economic thought — evolving from the concept of minimal intervention to the acknowledgment of the necessity for a complex, strategic partnership adapted to the challenges of globalization and its various phases of national economic diversification. In practice, modern states frequently exhibit elements of diverse theoretical models, which have combined to form unique national hybrids. These hybrids leverage ideological orientations, access to capital and technology markets, and safeguard their sovereignty and entitlement to success within the framework of global competition.

The classical framework here transitions from the liberal model to the Keynesian: the transformation in the role of the state and its function as a foundational actor becomes most evident in the ongoing American-Israeli-Iranian confrontation, in which younger states challenge ancient Persia with its 6000-year history. [1]

Simultaneously, the liberal model, originating with Adam Smith and David Ricardo, conceived of the state in international trade primarily as a ‘night watchman,’ responsible for ensuring the free movement of goods and capital and the enforcement of agreements. Foreign Trade Policy within this paradigm should aim to minimize barriers, thereby enabling comparative advantages to operate at full capacity. However, it should not exclude the presence of hidden protectionism or the concealment of portions of GDP within the ‘gray’ and ‘black’ zones associated with offshore schemes, as well as bubbles of volatile inflows into decapitalizing assets during periods of crisis. Furthermore, Iran itself — both a pariah state and a ‘threat to peace’ — is gradually sinking before the eyes of the world, with dignity and poise. Amid this, all trade and logistics routes are collapsing, traditional GCSS are disintegrating, the hydrocarbon market is fracturing, and food demand — the Achilles’ heel of the entire global economy at its current stage of alterglobalization — is rapidly intensifying in leaps and bounds.

Historical analogies, such as the global economic crisis of the 1930s and the experience of post-war recovery, contributed to the predominance of the Keynesian approach. The state came to be regarded as an active agent and regulator of the economy, bearing responsibility for aggregate demand, employment, and industrial development. In the realm of trade, this was manifested in the acceptance of protectionism to shield emerging industries (the theory of F. List), the proactive application of macroeconomic policy instruments to bolster exports (including devaluations and subsidized credit), and direct involvement in strategic sectors. This model constituted the foundation for the post-war development of many Western countries and, in a modified form, became the theoretical basis for China’s industrial policy during the initial stages of reform, when the state deliberately created and protected national industrial ‘hidden champions’ that shaped and confidently absorbed entire sectors, acting as ‘black holes’ within the emerging ecosystems of the forthcoming energy transition.

Simultaneously, contemporary critical concepts — concerning the risks of state intervention degenerating in the pursuit of the digital optimum and the turnover velocity of investment and innovation capital — propel the world toward Friedmanian global governance institutions. These institutions rely on socio-economic escalators that thin out societies in the search for talent and increasingly effective solutions within the creative industries explored by Daniel Kahneman and Richard Thaler.

The economic crises of the 1970s and stagflation critically undermined confidence in Keynesianism, creating a foundation for the development of theories that critique excessive and inefficient government intervention.

- Public choice theory (J. Buchanan, G. Tullock) conceptualizes government officials and politicians not as altruistic servants of the public interest but as rational actors seeking to maximize their own advantages (departmental budget, political

influence, prospects for reelection). This leads to the adoption of trade-political decisions (such as the imposition of tariffs and quotas) that benefit narrow groups (lobbyists) but are detrimental to society as a whole.

• The concept of rent-seeking behavior and the theory of state capture (Stigler, Peltzman) are directly connected to trade policy. According to these theories, business groups ('rent seekers') allocate resources not to innovation but to lobbying efforts aimed at securing exclusive privileges from the state — such as tariff protection, export subsidies, and special regimes. In its extreme form, this leads to 'state capture,' where regulatory bodies begin to act exclusively in the interests of the regulated industry. This theory explains the persistence of protectionist measures even amid their evident economic inefficiency. Prominent examples can be observed in the practices of various countries, including the agro-industrial lobby in developed countries, whose interests often predominate in the context of WTO negotiations.

In response to the shortcomings of both purely market-based and exclusively state-led approaches, the concept of public-private partnership has arisen — an institutional and organizational alliance between the state and the private sector aimed at implementing large-scale projects in socially significant areas, such as infrastructure and housing and utilities. Within trade policy, public-private partnerships evolve into more sophisticated forms of cooperation, including:

1. Joint implementation of infrastructure projects critical to export (transport corridors, port terminals, logistics hubs). The UAE is a global leader in applying this model, where the state, represented by the emirate authorities, establishes the infrastructural foundation (ports, airports, SEZs), and private business (often international) ensures their operational efficiency and integration into global networks. This exemplifies the approach described by O. Haassman, in 'Business Models,' posits that the state creates and sustains a value-driven platform for business.

2. Co-financing and insurance of export operations through export credit agencies (ECAs) with state participation (in the Russian Federation — REC and EXIAR). The state assumes political and long-term commercial risks that the private sector is unwilling or unable to insure, thereby 'pushing' (as noted by R. Thaler) companies to enter new high-risk markets.

3. Coordination of efforts within the framework of economic diplomacy.

State institutions (ministries, trade missions) and business associations jointly collaborate on market opening, trade dispute resolution, and the promotion of national standards. China has institutionalized this model at its highest level, where giant companies (Huawei, COSCO) operate in the closest coordination with the party-state apparatus within the framework of The Belt and Road strategy, simultaneously pursuing both commercial and geo-economic objectives.

In contemporary conditions, networked forms of governance are increasingly significant, wherein the state functions not as a dictator but as one of the nodes

within a network comprising business associations, expert communities, guilds and self-regulatory organizations (SROs), as well as international actors with varying degrees of loyalty and geopolitical engagement. Foreign trade policy is formulated through ongoing consultations and negotiations among these participants in the construction of a new world order architecture, which is founded not on rules and laws but on the will of the powerful, who are now not always fully rational leaders.

- The neo-corporatist model presupposes institutionalized representation of major business associations and trade unions in the process of governmental decision-making. This model is partly manifest in Russia through the activities of numerous councils under governmental bodies (for instance, the Council for the Development of Foreign Trade under the Ministry of Industry and Trade), where large businesses possess a channel for direct influence on the trade agenda.

- The ‘open coordination’ type network model characterizes interactions within the framework of the EAEU, wherein the supranational Eurasian Economic Commission (EEC) maintains ongoing consultations with both national governments and entrepreneurial unions to formulate a unified trade policy.

- China’s hybrid network model is unique: formally, there is no classical corporatism; however, the Communist Party of China is integrated into all major business structures through party committees, and state-owned and private enterprises are consolidated into complex pyramidal holdings and ecosystems. This arrangement enables the execution of an unprecedentedly coordinated trade and investment policy.

Concurrently, Russia exhibits a hybrid model characterized by elements of ‘state capture’ alongside an emerging public-private partnership. There is a strong influence of major raw material and state corporate lobbying (rent-seeking behavior), which impedes export diversification. However, concurrently, instruments supporting non-commodity exports through ECAs and development institutions are evolving quietly and progressively, while network platforms for dialogue are also being established (councils affiliated with ministries). Membership in the EAEU introduces an additional supranational level of network interaction.

Another illustrative example is China, which epitomizes a model of strategic state capitalism characterized by deeply integrated networked structures. The state, through planning, control over the financial system, and party mechanisms, does not merely regulate but directly guides business activities (particularly state-owned enterprises and ‘national champions’) toward the attainment of global trade-political objectives. Theories of capture are scarcely applicable in this context — it is rather a symbiotic relationship accompanied by the complete subordination of business to the state strategy.

In the unfolding Middle East crisis, the UAE model currently characterizes the phenomenon, serving as an exemplar of the ‘state-as-platform’ model within the global network context. The state minimizes overall intervention in the economy but

selectively establishes enclaves with exceptional conditions (SEZs, financial centers), acting as both architect and regulator of these platforms. Interaction with business in these jurisdictions assumes a clearly contractual, partnership-oriented character, which aligns perfectly with contemporary business model concepts. Trade policy is, de facto, extraterritorial and subject to zonal differentiation, allowing the attraction of international business without necessitating amendments to the entire national legislation.

Accordingly, contemporary theories concerning the interaction between the state and business in trade policy do not negate one another but rather elucidate distinct aspects and risks inherent in this complex process. National models are shaped by historical trajectories, political structures, and strategic choices, combining elements of corporatism, network governance, and public-private partnerships in unique proportions, as exemplified by the cases of Russia, China, and the UAE.

The interaction between the state and business in the sphere of foreign trade is implemented through a complex set of interconnected forms and mechanisms, which vary depending on the national economic model, the level of institutional development, and strategic priorities. An analysis of the practices of Russia, China, and the UAE allows for identification of a spectrum of approaches — from direct administrative involvement to the formation of complex institutional ecosystems.

1. Direct state participation in capital and management

This represents the most direct form, in which the state acts as the owner or controlling shareholder of key exporting companies.

Russia: Direct participation is practiced through state unitary enterprises (SUEs) and companies with predominant state ownership (PJSC Gazprom, PJSC Rosneft, Rostec, RZD Logistics, PJSC Aeroflot). As evidenced by their charters and reports, the objectives of such enterprises often extend beyond commercial aims and include securing strategic supplies, implementing infrastructure projects within the EAEU, or executing foreign policy objectives. The state appoints the management, thereby ensuring loyalty and control; however, as noted by A. I. Golomolzin, this creates the risk of diverging objectives from market efficiency towards meeting administrative targets.

China: It is precisely in these entities that direct involvement is concentrated, which is systemic and of a more profound character. Key export giants (Sinopec, COSCO, CNRC) are state-owned enterprises directly subordinate to the State-owned Assets Supervision and Administration Commission. However, the uniqueness of the Chinese model lies in the integration of party committees within the corporate management structure. Party committees operating within corporations ensure the coordination of business strategies with national five-year plans and the Belt and Road Initiative, rendering their involvement not only financial but also ideologically strategic.

UAE: The model differs but remains full of surprises and hedging strategies, ranging from banking mechanisms to speculative activities in the real estate market,

which declined by 30% as a consequence of the Iranian venture orchestrated by the ‘collective West.’ Direct state involvement more frequently manifests in the form of sovereign wealth funds (such as Mubadala Investment Company and Abu Dhabi Investment Authority) and holding companies controlled by ruling families (Dubai Holding, Investment Corporation of Dubai). These entities serve as strategic investors in critical export-oriented and infrastructural assets, including ports, airlines, and logistics operators. The management is predominantly corporate-investment oriented, focused on long-term financial returns and economic diversification, while clearly adhering to the emirate’s governmental development strategy.

2. Regulatory Legal and Customs-Tariff Regulation

This is the fundamental mechanism through which the state establishes the ‘rules of the game.’ Its nature varies fundamentally.

Russia within the EAEU system: Regulation exhibits a two-tiered nature. A significant portion of competencies is delegated to the supranational level. The Eurasian Economic Commission (EEC) develops and enforces compliance with the uniform technical regulations of the EAEU, and manages the Common Customs Tariff (CCT) as well as non-tariff measures with respect to third countries. At the national level, the implementation of decisions of the Eurasian Economic Commission (EEC) and the regulation of matters not delegated to the Commission remain in place. This establishes stable, albeit often less flexible, frameworks for business operations.

China: Regulation is a strategic instrument in the hands of the state. In addition to the customs tariff (associated with WTO obligations), the People’s Republic of China actively employs a sophisticated system of non-tariff measures: mandatory certification under Chinese standards (CCC), sanitary and phytosanitary barriers, which can be flexibly applied to protect the domestic market or to exert pressure on trading partners. As noted by V. I. Deren, this approach enables formal compliance with WTO rules while effectively maintaining a significant degree of control over commodity flows.

UAE: Regulation is structured according to the principle of a dual-circuit system. National legislation is relatively liberal; however, the principal instrument involves the establishment of special economic zones (SEZ) and free financial zones, each operating under independent, highly liberal regulatory regimes (for instance, DIFC following the Anglo-Saxon legal system). The state effectively creates ‘extraterritorial’ jurisdictions characterized by zero customs duties, 100% foreign ownership, and preferential taxation, thereby attracting international business. This is an innovative model of state regulatory governance described by O. Gassmann, wherein the state functions as the architect of competitive legal frameworks.

3. Financial and economic mechanisms: subsidies, tax incentives, and guarantees

These are instruments of targeted stimulation designed to channel business activities along the trajectories preferred by the state.

Russia: The primary instruments include subsidizing interest rates on export loans, reimbursing partial costs associated with transportation and certification of non-commodity exports, as well as providing state guarantees for export contracts through JSC ‘Russian Export Center’ (REC). These measures, provided by the websites of the Ministry of Economic Development and REC, are aimed at structural restructuring of exports. However, as the theory of rent-oriented behavior warns, such measures require transparent and competitive procedures to prevent the ‘capture’ of support instruments by narrow interest groups.

China: Financial support is comprehensive and strategic in nature. It includes direct subsidies to targeted industries (semiconductors, electric vehicles, RES), concessional loans from state banks to companies participating in the Belt and Road project, and tax holidays for high-tech manufacturers. This system, which combines supportive incentives (‘carrot’) with mandatory planned targets (‘stick’), generates strong motivation for export expansion specifically within prioritized sectors.

UAE: Financial mechanisms are predominantly of an investment and infrastructural nature. The state does not directly subsidize export operations of private enterprises. Instead, it invests in the development of first-class port, airport, and logistics infrastructure — such as Jebel Ali Port and Khalifa Port — thereby significantly reducing transaction costs for all companies operating within the emirate. The tax incentives are of a general rather than targeted nature (exemption from corporate profit tax and VAT within the SEZ, a zero rate on re-exports), representing an example of ‘choice architecture’ as conceptualized in Richard Thaler’s behavioral economics: businesses are naturally inclined to engage in export and re-export activities, as the environment is most conducive to these operations.

4. Institutional Platforms for Dialogue

These platforms ensure feedback and alignment of interests, thereby mitigating the shortcomings of directive policies.

Russia: A developed system of sectoral and expert councils operates within federal governing bodies (Ministry of Economic Development, Ministry of Industry and Trade). Analyses indicate that these councils frequently function as channels for lobbying the interests of major stakeholders, while also serving as instruments for information gathering and regulatory initiative testing. In the context of EAEU membership, the dialogue is complicated, requiring businesses to engage also with the relevant departments of the EEC.

China: There are fewer formal ‘councils’ in the Western understanding, but dialogue is integrated into the system through party and state structures. All major companies have party committees, which constitute a direct channel of communication with higher authorities. Additionally, sectoral associations, closely monitored by the state, function as intermediaries for policy dissemination and data collection.

UAE: The interactions are characterized by a more pragmatic and informal nature. Key investment and trade decisions are frequently deliberated in closed-door meetings involving representatives of ruling families, sovereign wealth fund leadership, and top executives of major international corporations. Open institutional platforms (such as the Dubai Chamber of Commerce and Industry) predominantly fulfill a service-oriented and representative role, thereby facilitating market entry.

Therefore, the forms of interaction between the state and business in trade constitute a continuum ranging from direct ownership (Russia, China) to the establishment of regulated market platforms (UAE). Financial mechanisms vary from targeted subsidies (Russia, China) to the creation of collective infrastructural rents (UAE). Institutions of dialogue reflect the political structure: from formalized councils affiliated with governmental ministries (Russia) and party channels (China) to informal elite networks (UAE). A central trend involves the transition from simple regulatory frameworks to the design of complex ecosystems and the application of behavioral ‘nudges’ aimed at achieving strategic trade objectives within stringent international regulations. Each of the countries under consideration has found its own unique balance among these instruments.

Geopolitics itself, given the lack of a rapid decisive victory, compelled the USA and Israel to adopt prolonged strategies, including the deployment of the world’s leading Russian-origin air defense system S-500 to the combat zone [2], as well as the transition by Iranian forces and the IRGC, following the 12-day June war of 2025, from the U.S. GPS satellite constellation (55 satellites) to the Chinese Baidu low-earth orbit satellite system (consisting of 120 satellites in the orbital constellation). These decisions both sealed the IRI airspace against enemy aircraft and facilitated enhanced targeting capabilities for their own missiles and drones, which, according to projections by the same Pentagon analysts, are expected to remain operational for at least another several months. [3]

Therefore, neither Israel’s “Roaring Lion” operation nor the Anglo-Saxon “Epic Fury” campaign can yet encapsulate the specific nature of the combat operations as an Old Testament Day of Judgment war, as a struggle for control over the Strait of Hormuz, or as ignoring the Houthi support forces functioning as pro-Iranian proxies in the Persian Gulf region. Nevertheless, Trade trends and logistics are already beginning to shift away from the Red Sea and the Gulf monarchies toward the Mediterranean, which can, de facto, be controlled by both the United States and Israel. [4]

Consequently, geoeconomics is poised to undertake another shift, resulting in OPEC countries losing their influence over the global hydrocarbon market, since those who can export oil and gas safely and swiftly ultimately determine the pricing for both commodities and liquefied natural gas (LNG), which has long awaited its opportunity in the shadow of the shale revolutions aligned with Rockefeller-era expectations—‘storms, indeed, storms.’

Consequently, the conflict involving individuals burdened by criminal cases, Donald Trump, and Bibi Netanyahu will enable global powers to further advance the world into a new accounting system for valuation and energy assets, as well as establish pathways for admitting allied countries into the coordinate system associated with the ending monopoly of raw material owners and processors. Since the entity responsible for delivering the product to the end consumer shapes the GCSS network under its control and determines the terms under which this actor will be granted access in the digital future to tangible assets, even if the cost for such access, as in this case for the European Union, is prohibitively high. [5]

Meanwhile, both BRICS and the SCO employed a period of silent disapproval without adopting key decisions, indicating that the outcome of the conflict with this ancient civilization, the foundational North-South axis that safeguards the final element of the international security system, will largely depend on their stance.

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2020–2024年伊尔库茨克州乌斯季奥尔达布里亚特自治区农场动物粗饲料和多汁饲料供应形成特点

**FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF THE SUPPLY OF
ROUGHAGE AND SUCCULENT FEED FOR FARM ANIMALS IN
THE UST-ORDA BURYAT OKRUG OF THE IRKUTSK REGION
FOR 2020-2024**

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摘要：本研究分析了2020年至2024年伊尔库茨克州乌斯季奥尔达布里亚特自治区六个县的粗饲料和青贮饲料产量。研究数据来源于阿拉尔斯基县、巴彦达耶夫斯基县、博汉斯基县、努库茨基县、奥辛斯基县和叶希里特-布拉加茨基县农业企业的官方报告数据。研究计算了秸秆、干草、青贮饲料和青贮饲料的总产量（以公担为单位）、收获成本（以千卢布为单位）以及每种饲料的单位成本价。结果表明，干草总产量从2020年的2,588,261公担下降到2024年的1,867,693公担（下降至2020年的72.2%）。青贮饲料产量从551,746公担下降至505,731公担（下降91.7%）。青贮饲料体积从511,154公担下降至376,974公担（下降73.7%）。2020–2021年未生产秸秆；2022–2024年产量极少（分别为2,600公担、58,820公担和61,610公担）。干草采购成本从119,526千卢布下降至45,120千卢布（下降37.7%）。干草成本价格从2020年的每公担46卢布上涨至2024年的每公担61卢布（上涨132.6%）。值得注意的是，未从其他地区进口粗饲料和多汁饲料。然而，2024年采购了2.28万吨饲料谷物，弥补了当地饲料产量的下降。

关键词：粗饲料、多汁饲料、干草、青贮饲料、秸秆、成本价、乌斯季阿尔达布里亚特自治区、伊尔库茨克州。

Abstract. *This study presents an analysis of the production volumes of roughage and green succulent feed in six districts of the Ust-Orda Buryat Okrug of the Irkutsk region for the period 2020-2024. The basis of the study was official reporting data from agricultural enterprises located in the Alarsky, Bayandayevsky, Bokhansky, Nukutsky, Osinsky, and Ekhirit-Bulagatsky districts. The total volumes of straw, hay, haylage, and silage production in centners, the costs of their harvesting in thousands of rubles, and the cost price per unit of each type of feed have been calculated. It was found that the total volume of hay production decreased from 2,588,261 centners in 2020 to 1,867,693 centners in 2024 (72.2% of the 2020 level). Haylage production decreased from 551,746 centners to 505,731 centners (91.7%). The volume of silage decreased from 511,154 centners to 376,974 centners (73.7%). Straw was not produced in 2020-2021; insignificant volumes appeared in 2022-2024 (2,600, 58,820, and 61,610 centners, respectively). Costs of hay procurement decreased from 119,526 thousand rubles to 45,120 thousand rubles (37.7%). The cost price of hay increased from 46 rubles per centner in 2020 to 61 rubles per centner in 2024 (132.6%). It was noted that roughage and succulent feeds from other regions were not imported; however, 22.8 thousand centners were purchased in 2024. tons of forage grain, which compensates for the reduction in local feed production.*

Keywords: *roughage, succulent feed, hay, haylage, silage, straw, cost price, Ust-Orda Buryat Okrug, Irkutsk region.*

Introduction

The Ust-Orda Buryat Okrug is an intraregional administrative formation within the Irkutsk region and comprises six administrative districts: Alarsky, Bayandayevsky, Bokhansky, Nukutsky, Osinsky, and Ekhirit-Bulagatsky. Agricultural production in the okrug specializes in meat and dairy livestock farming. The basis of the cattle diet consists of roughage (hay, straw) and succulent feed (haylage, silage). The availability and quantities of these feeds determine the economic efficiency of livestock farming.

Between 2020 and 2024, the Irkutsk region experienced variability in natural and climatic conditions affecting the yield of perennial and annual grasses. Simultaneously, changes occurred in the structure of sown areas and the fleet of feed-harvesting machinery. Roughage and succulent feeds from other territories are not imported, which makes local production the sole source for supplying animals with these types of feed.

The article utilizes sources reflecting various aspects of feed production and feed provision for livestock farming. In the works of Agafonov et al. [1] and

Klyoshina et al. [2] examined the technological methods of cultivating fodder crops and the existing feed harvesting technologies under the conditions of the Irkutsk region. Factors influencing the consumption of feed by animals were analyzed by Malygin et al. [3]. Barkova and Kalinina [4] presented an analysis of the global feed market, whereas Yushkova et al. [5] reported findings from studies on feed quality conducted in the Irkutsk region. The issues of food self-sufficiency and the enhancement of feed production were addressed by Soloshenko et al. [6]. Anikienko and Savchenko [7] provided an evaluation of the feed base for dairy cattle breeding in the region. Yanchenko et al. [8] highlighted the importance of root and tuber crops in diets, which complements the analysis of roughage and succulent feeds presented in this study.

Methodology

The data were sourced from the consolidated annual reports of agricultural organizations across six districts of the okrug for the period 2020-2024. Indicators for four types of feed were considered: straw, hay, haylage, and silage. For each feed type, three parameters were recorded: production volume (centners), harvesting costs (thousand rubles), and unit cost (rub./centner). The unit cost was calculated as the ratio of costs to volume.

For the analysis of dynamics, the indicators were aggregated across six districts for each year. The percentage ratio of volumes, costs, and unit costs in 2024 relative to 2020 was calculated using the formula (value in 2024 / value in 2020) × 100. In cases where production was absent in 2020 (straw), the percentage was not calculated (indicated by a dash). Rounding was applied to whole numbers for volumes and costs, and to one decimal place for percentages.

Additionally, data on forage grain purchases from other regions in 2024 (22.8 thousand tons) and planned purchases for 2025 (10.0 thousand tons) were taken into account.

Results

Table 1 shows the total production volumes of roughage and succulent feeds across six districts of the okrug for the years 2020-2024.

Table 1. Production volume of roughage and succulent feeds in the Ust-Orda Buryat Okrug for 2020-2024, centners (cwt)

Type of feed	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2024 compared to 2020, %
Straw	0	0	2600	58820	61610	—
Hay	2588261	1892033	1760579	2088657	1867693	72.2
Haylage	551746	991690	937143	758884	505731	91.7
Silage	511154	414106	376270	236300	376974	73.7

Straw was absent in 2020 and 2021. In 2022, initial volumes appeared (2,600 cwt); in 2023, production increased to 58,820 cwt; and in 2024, reached 61,610 cwt. Hay production declined from 2,588,261 cwt in 2020 to 1,867,693 cwt in 2024. The decrease amounted to 27.8% (remaining volume — 72.2% of the 2020 level). The greatest decline was recorded in 2022 (1,760,579 centners).

Haylage volumes fluctuated: an increase in 2021 to 991,690 centners, followed by a decrease to 505,731 centners in 2024. The ratio of 2024 to 2020 was 91.7%, representing a decrease of 8.3%.

Silage decreased from 511,154 centners in 2020 to 376,974 centners in 2024 (73.7% of the 2020 level). The minimum value was recorded in 2023 (236,300 centners).

Table 2 presents the costs of fodder harvesting.

Table 2. Costs of procuring roughage and succulent feed in the Ust-Orda Buryat Okrug for 2020-2024, thousand rubles.

Type of feed	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2024 compared to 2020, %
Straw	0	0	100	50	34	—
Hay	119526	71890	59268	24734	45120	37.7
Haylage	97796	60084	55514	104658	49468	50.6
Silage	43550	40990	30754	25688	13192	30.3

Costs for hay decreased from 119,526 thousand rubles to 45,120 thousand rubles (37.7% of the 2020 level). Costs for haylage decreased from 97,796 thousand rubles to 49,468 thousand rubles (50.6%). Costs for silage fell from 43,550 thousand rubles to 13,192 thousand rubles (30.3%). Straw costs in 2022-2024 remained below 100 thousand rubles.

Table 2 draws attention to the discrepancy between the trends in costs and volumes for haylage. With haylage production volumes decreasing from 551,746 centners in 2020 to 505,731 centners in 2024 (91.7% of the 2020 level), costs declined to 50.6%, that is, almost halved. This indicates that in 2020, 177 rubles were spent per centner of haylage, whereas in 2024 this amount was 98 rubles. A 44.6% reduction in unit costs accompanied by a slight decrease in volumes indicates the transition of the district's farms to less expensive haylage procurement technologies (likely involving polymer packaging instead of trench storage), which is not captured in the primary reporting data.

Table 3 presents the cost price per unit of each type of feed.

Table 3. Cost price of roughage and succulent feed in the Ust-Orda Buryat Okrug for 2020-2024, RUB/centner

Type of feed	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2024 compared to 2020, %
Straw	—	—	38	1	1	—
Hay	46	38	34	12	24	52.2
Haylage	177	61	59	138	98	55.4
Silage	85	99	82	109	35	41.2

The cost price of hay decreased from 46 rubles/centner in 2020 to 24 rubles/centner in 2024 (52.2% of the 2020 level). The cost price of haylage fell from 177 rubles/centner to 98 rubles/centner (55.4%). The cost price of silage decreased from 85 rubles/centner to 35 rubles/centner (41.2%). The cost price of straw was 38 rubles/centner in 2022, and 1 ruble/centner in 2023-2024.

Discussion

A 27.8% reduction in hay production volume over the five-year period was accompanied by a disproportionately larger decrease in costs (by 62.3%). As a result, the production cost of hay decreased by 47.8%. This indicates the concentration of hay harvesting in the most efficient farms and the removal of unprofitable hayfields from operation.

Haylage showed the smallest reduction in volumes (8.3%) with a decline in costs of 49.4%. The production cost of haylage decreased by 44.6%. Haylage harvesting technology requires less manual labor and enables feed preservation in polymer packaging, thereby reducing losses.

Silage decreased by 26.3% accompanied by a cost reduction of 69.7%. The cost price of silage decreased by 58.8%. The sharp reduction in expenses in 2024 (to 13,192 thousand rubles) is due to the concentration of silage production within a limited number of farms.

The appearance of straw in 2022-2024 is explained by the integration of grain crops into the feed cycle. The low cost price of straw (1 ruble per centner) makes it an accessible source of roughage.

In 2024, 22.8 thousand tons of fodder grain were procured from other regions. Roughage and succulent feeds from other regions are not imported. Purchases of forage grain partially compensate for the reduction in local production of silage and haylage, as grain is used to balance rations in terms of energy. The reduction in silage volume by 134,180 centners over the five-year period corresponds to

a loss of approximately 13.4 thousand tons of feed units, which is comparable to the volume of purchased forage grain.

Conclusion

Between 2020 and 2024, the Ust-Orda Buryat Okrug experienced a decrease in the production of hay (by 27.8%), silage (by 26.3%), and haylage (by 8.3%). The costs of harvesting all types of feed decreased more substantially than the volumes, resulting in a reduction of the cost price of hay by 47.8%, haylage by 44.6%, and silage by 58.8%. Straw volumes incorporated into the feed balance have emerged. The decline in local production of succulent feeds is partially compensated by the procurement of fodder grain from other regions (22.8 thousand tons in 2024). The lack of imports of roughage and succulent feeds from outside renders the okrug fully dependent on its own feed production for these feed types.

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评估一个地区人力资源潜力的方法论
**METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO ASSESSING THE HUMAN
POTENTIAL OF A REGION**

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摘要：本文探讨了用于研究和评估区域人力资源潜力的各种方法。所有方法被归为两类：联合国的概念性方法（计算人类发展指数）和基于识别和分析区域人力资源潜力各个组成部分的方法。本文分析了这些方法的优缺点。

关键词：区域人力资源潜力；评估方法；人类发展指数；子潜力。

Abstract. *This article examines methodological approaches employed to study and evaluate the human potential of a region. All methodologies are categorized into two groups: the UN's conceptual approach, which calculates the Human Development Index, and an approach based on the identification and analysis of individual components of the region's human potential. The advantages and disadvantages of the specified approaches have been examined.*

Keywords: *human potential of the region; assessment methodology; human development index; sub-potentials.*

Introduction

Human potential plays a key role in the socio-economic condition and development of a region. This is a complex category encompassing the demographic, labor, cultural, educational, and other potentials of the regional population, as well as the population's ability to utilize existing skills, knowledge, experience, and professionalism across various spheres of activity, to develop and accumulate them, thereby transforming them into human capital. Human potential becomes especially relevant in a knowledge-based economy, characterized by increased

emphasis on achieving indicators such as improving quality of life, reducing social inequality within the population, and enhancing the overall level of welfare.

Among the methods for measuring human potential, the approaches proposed by the United Nations predominate. In accordance with these approaches, human development indices are calculated, and rankings of countries and regions are compiled based on them. The primary limitation of this approach lies in the use of a narrow set of examined indicators. Simultaneously, for a comprehensive and objective assessment of human potential, we consider it necessary to employ a broader range of indicators, which, on the one hand, enables accounting for the specifics of its formation and application in a given region, and on the other hand, facilitates the evaluation of the contribution of human potential to the socio-economic development of that region.

Materials and Methods

The existing methodological approaches to evaluating the human potential of a region are considered with respect to their adequacy for producing accurate and objective results. To date, the most well-known approach is that developed by experts at the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). As noted earlier, it is widely used for the comparative assessment of human potential across individual countries and regions. This approach is employed by many Russian researchers who attempt to adapt the UNDP methodology to domestic conditions [2, 4, 5, 7, 8].

An alternative methodological approach is employed by domestic researchers who analyze the structure of a region's human potential, its division into individual sub-potentials, and develop a system of indicators for assessing each sub-potential as well as the human potential in its entirety. Various studies identify the following components of human potential: biophysical; labor; intellectual; educational; communicative; cultural; emotional; and creative. innovative-intellectual, physical, and social health. [1, 3, 6]. To evaluate human potential and its individual components, each author employs a set of specific indicators that vary according to the objectives and goals of the research undertaken. Although measuring human potential through this approach encounters the multiplicity of its characteristics, which are not always formalized and often lack precise quantitative assessment, it nevertheless permits a sufficiently comprehensive and reliable evaluation of particular components of human potential, taking into account the specifics of each region.

Results

The Human Development Index according to the UNDP methodology is calculated as the average of three specific indices, each assessing key aspects of human development such as longevity, literacy, and standard of living. The closer the value of each index is to 1, the higher the ranking position of the country or region. Table 1 presents the ranking of the regions of the Far Eastern Federal District by the Human Development Index (IHR) for 2022, calculated according to the UNDP methodology.

Table 1. Human Development Indices by Regions of the Far Eastern Federal District

Region	Longevity Index	Income Index	Literacy Index	IHR	Ranking among the regions of the Far Eastern Federal District
Amur Oblast	0.720	0.684	0.9993	0.789	7
Jewish Autonomous Oblast	0.712	0.627	0.9990	0.764	10
Trans-Baikal Krai	0.713	0.628	0.9986	0.765	9
Kamchatka Krai	0.730	0.750	0.9996	0.818	4
Magadan Oblast	0.724	0.847	0.9991	0.849	2
Primorsky Krai	0.745	0.693	0.9988	0.806	5
Republic of Buryatia	0.739	0.601	0.9986	0.763	11
Republic of Sakha (Yakutia)	0.795	0.826	0.9990	0.767	8
Sakhalin Oblast	0.756	0.899	0.9991	0.879	1
Khabarovsk Krai	0.749	0.690	0.9995	0.803	6
Chukotka Autonomous Okrug	0.687	0.882	0.9986	0.846	3

Source: compiled by the authors based on [2]

Given that the IHR in Russia in 2022 was 0.821; we observe that in the leading regions of the Far Eastern Federal District according to this indicator, its value exceeds the all-Russian average.

This methodological approach, despite its universality and its capability to compare regions based on achieved IHR values, nonetheless has several shortcomings:

1) it completely disregards the demographic aspect of human potential, which is of critical importance for contemporary Russia;

2) The IHR uses per capita gross domestic product as a measure of the standard of living. However, significant income differentiation within the population renders the use of this indicator for regional calculations inappropriate. We concur with the position of I. Yu. Timofeev that it is more correct to employ the indicator ‘the number of the regional population with incomes not below the subsistence minimum’ [5, p. 25].

3) the absence of an ecological component, which influences the quality of life and, consequently, the human potential as a whole;

4) The evaluation lacks indicators that consider the impact of specific regional factors on the development of human potential. For instance, in the Magadan region, human potential is affected by factors such as harsh climatic conditions,

remoteness from Russia's central regions, steady population outflow, a high income level, and simultaneously, a high cost of living.

For example, I. Yu. Timofeev, examining the influence of regions on the reproduction of human potential, proposes to complement its qualitative characterization — achieved using the UNDP approach — with a measurement of the quantitative aspect of human potential, that is, to relate the IHR to the population size. Table 2 contains the formulas for calculating the IHR according to the UNDP methodology and in accordance with the approach of I. Yu. Timofeev.

Table 2. Formulas for calculating the IHR

According to the UNDP methodology [2]	According to the methodology of I. Yu. Timofeev [5]
$ИЧР = \sqrt[3]{I_{\text{долг}} \times I_{\text{дох}} \times I_{\text{грам}}} \quad (1)$	$\begin{aligned} ИРРЧП &= \\ &= \sqrt[3]{I_{\text{ОПЖ}} \times I_{\text{Образования}} \times I_{\text{Дохода}}} \quad (5) \end{aligned}$
$I_{\text{долголетия}} = \frac{x-25}{85-25} \quad (2)$	$I_{\text{ОПЖ}} = \frac{\text{ОПЖ}}{100} \quad (6)$
$I_{\text{дохода}} = \frac{\log Y - \log 100}{\log 75000 - \log 100} \quad (3)$	$I_{\text{Образования}} = \sqrt{Y_{\Gamma} \times K_{\Pi}} \quad (7)$
$\begin{aligned} I_{\text{образ}} &= \\ &= \frac{i \text{ ожд. обучения} + i \text{ сред. обучения}}{2} \quad (4) \end{aligned}$	$I_{\text{Дохода}} = \frac{\text{ЧНД}}{\text{ЧН}} \quad (8)$

where ИЧР — human development index;

ИРРЧП — regional human potential development index;

$I_{\text{долг}}$ — индекс долголетия;;

$I_{\text{доход}}$ — income index;

$I_{\text{образ}}$ — education index;

Y_{Γ} — adult literacy rate (coefficient);

K_{Π} — aggregate gross enrollment ratio in primary, secondary, and higher education institutions relative to the population aged 7-24;

ЧНП — the population of the region with incomes not lower than the subsistence minimum;

ЧН — the population of the region.

For calculating the human potential of the region, the author proposes to use formula (9):

$$\text{ЧПР}_i = \text{ЧН}_i \times \text{ИРРЧП}_i \quad (9)$$

where ЧПР_i — human potential of the i -th region, thousand persons;

ЧН_i — population of the i -th region, thousand persons;

ИРРЧП_i — index of regional development of human potential of the i -th region [5].

In our view, the methodology proposed by I. Yu. Timofeev retains the principal limitation of the UNDP approach — the restricted set of indicators used in the calculation, which fails to provide a comprehensive assessment of the human potential of the region.

An interesting approach is employed by A. G. Kuznetsova and T. V. Borzova. They conducted an assessment of the human potential of children and youth under 35 years of age in the Khabarovsk Krai and the Far Eastern Federal District [4]. The IHR proved insufficiently informative for the purposes of this study, as it does not account for such an aspect of the quality of human potential as youth giftedness. Therefore, to evaluate the selected indicators, they utilized data from various official rankings; for example, the methodology for assessing the effectiveness of the activities of the highest-ranking officials of the subjects of the Russian Federation and the executive authorities of the subjects of the Russian Federation was employed to assess the level of education. To complement the characterization of the state of human potential, the authors used information from the RAEX («RAEX-Analytics») rating agency concerning the educational potential of regions in the technical sphere. To evaluate the quality of school education, data from the corresponding regional ranking compiled in 2021 by Rosobrnadzor were employed. Thus, the use of already available data from official rankings makes it possible to obtain information that is not provided by statistical authorities.

Thus, the UNDP methodology overly averages the actual values of the human development index indicators. Therefore, many proponents of this approach attempt to modify the IHR in order to adapt it to account for regional specificity. As the results demonstrate, while sacrificing universality, the IHR ranking becomes more precise, reliable, and consequently acquires greater practical significance.

Among the studies employing the second approach is the monograph prepared by the N. M. Rimashevskaya Institute of Socio-Economic Problems of Population, in which the components of human potential are identified as demographic, health potential, labor, educational, and cultural potentials; social health potential; ecological behavior; gender aspects of human potential; as well as, separately, migration processes and environmental living conditions — factors of human potential development singled out due to their specificity [3]. For an expanded social characterization of human potential, the authors reduced the full range of indicators to seven, each selected as the most significant for assessing a specific aspect of potential. For example, to assess the level of demographic potential development, the indicator ‘natural population growth’ was used; for health potential, ‘life expectancy at birth,’ and so forth. Data on these indicators were collected from all regions of Russia, enabling the construction of a ranking based on human potential status as well as the grouping of regions into seven clusters. According to the authors, the cluster approach enables the grouping of regions similar in qualitative

characteristics of human potential, thereby facilitating the formulation of management decisions regarding its development.

A. V. Zolotarchuk proposed a methodological toolkit for assessing the effectiveness of the humanitarian services sector in the reproduction of human potential. Its distinctive feature is the analysis of human potential based on multidimensional indicators through econometric models. The author distinguishes seven subcomponents of the human potential of a region: demographic, labor, innovation, educational, cultural, ecological, and physical and social health [1].

A. V. Zolotarchuk analyzed the condition and development of human potential across 80 regions of Russia in 2010 and 2018. The study identifies “Demography and Health” as one of the principal components for which the regions of the Far East exhibit the lowest values, with multidimensional indicators being 1.5 to 2 times lower than the national Russian average. Additionally, “Social Health” is highlighted, where, for example, the Magadan region falls behind the Russian average by a factor of 45.5 [1, p. 113]. These data correlate with the results obtained by the N. M. Rimashevskaya Institute of Socio-Economic Problems of Population, which constitutes indirect evidence of the validity of the methodologies employed.

Conclusion. Thus, the conducted analysis of methodological approaches to evaluating the human potential of the region permits the following conclusions:

1. For a more comprehensive and holistic assessment of the human potential of a region, it is advisable to employ an approach that distinguishes the individual components of human potential and assesses each component using an indicator system.

2. A set of requirements must be imposed on indicators of human potential:

- to be reliable and credible, based on official statistical data;
- the data for analysis must be accessible;
- the system of indicators should be concise.

3. Regression-correlation analysis can be employed as a method to ensure the parsimony of the indicator system by selecting those indicators between which no correlation or only a very weak correlation exists.

4. To construct a human potential ranking for a set of regions, one can employ the method of calculating an integral index for each component based on the obtained partial indices.

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水运技术管理中小型企业业务流程分析与优化问题
**PROBLEMS OF ANALYSIS AND OPTIMIZATION OF BUSINESS
PROCESSES IN SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES
OF TECHNICAL MANAGEMENT IN WATER TRANSPORT**

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摘要：本文探讨了在从事水运船队维修和技术维护的中小型企业中，如何利用现有方法分析和优化业务流程。这类企业的员工很少参与业务流程分析，这严重影响了其运营效率。

本文分析了行业特有的、使分析过程复杂化的因素，包括：业务规模小、市场参与者数量有限、产品和技术复杂以及监管机构的严格监管。

本文对现有的分析方法和流程进行了分析，旨在探讨其在技术管理企业中的适用性。

本文开发了一种算法，用于分析和优化这类企业的业务流程，并用于重组组织管理框架。

关键词：业务流程，技术管理，优化，行业特有性。

Abstract. *The article is dedicated to the problems of utilizing existing methodologies for the analysis and optimization of business processes in small and medium-sized enterprises involved in the repair and technical maintenance of the water transport fleet. The personnel of such enterprises rarely engage in the analysis of business processes, which adversely impacts their operational effectiveness.*

Industry-specific features complicating the analysis process have been examined: the scale of operations, the limited number of market participants, the complexity of products and technologies, and stringent regulation of activities by supervisory authorities.

An analysis of contemporary methods and methodologies for analysis has been performed with the aim of their potential adaptation for application within technical management enterprises.

An algorithm has been developed for analyzing and optimizing business processes in such enterprises, as well as for restructuring organizational management frameworks.

Keywords: *business process, technical management, optimization, sector-specific characteristics.*

Introduction

Water transport in Russia constitutes a vital component of the state's infrastructure. At the same time, researchers' and managers' attention is primarily concentrated on the operations of large companies. Nevertheless, it is imperative to consider the impact of the functioning of small and medium-sized enterprises specializing in the technical management of the fleet on the sustainability of the water transport sector.

The roles of small and medium-sized technical management enterprises encompass fleet repair, comprehensive supply, ensuring navigational safety, compliance with the requirements of classification societies, and others. These enterprises are characterized by a high degree of responsibility within stringent resource limitations, both regarding the availability of fixed and working capital and the availability and quality of existing labor resources.

Sustainable economic performance of enterprises and organizations currently relies on the principles and methods of business process analysis. However, the application of standard approaches to their analysis and optimization is not always appropriate for technical management enterprises.

The adaptation of business analytics methodologies that consider both the scale of enterprise activities and sector-specific characteristics remains a pertinent issue.

Methods and Materials

The fundamental principles of the process approach are articulated in the works of M. Hammer, J. Champy, and T. Davenport [1,2,3]. Theories and practices related to business process management in the transport sector are addressed in the works of V. I. Sergeev [4,5] and L. B. Mirotin [6]. Challenges associated with the operation of small enterprises are reflected in the studies of A. V. Busygin [7,8] and M. G. Lapusta [9]. However, insufficient attention has been devoted to adapting existing standards to the particular features of enterprises within the water transport infrastructure sector. In particular, the issues of accessibility of analytical software tools for small businesses, and methodologies for identifying "weak points" in technical maintenance and repair processes of the fleet are insufficiently addressed.

There are also additional constraints arising from industry-specific characteristics. Technical management processes are rigorously regulated by the requirements of the Russian Maritime Register of Shipping (RS) or the Russian Classification

Society (RCS), as well as international conventions (SOLAS, MARPOL), which precludes the possibility of their arbitrary simplification.

Thus, the development of adapted methodologies for the analysis and optimization of business processes, taking into account simultaneously both the scale of the enterprise and its sectoral affiliation, is a current scientific and practical challenge.

Characteristics of the functioning of technical management enterprises

Technical management of water transport is carried out by enterprises that are, to varying degrees, associated with ship repair, technical maintenance, and material and logistical support (rescue equipment, firefighting gear, useful items, medicines, and other supplies). Typically, these are small enterprises, organized as limited liability companies, with modest own capital. The entire operation of such companies is linked to ensuring stable business turnover.

The equity capital of enterprises is limited: buildings and other production facilities are typically leased. The enterprises own various technical equipment, as well as cargo and passenger motor vehicles.

The specifics of conducting business in the technical maintenance and repair of the fleet impose certain limitations on the applicability of standard business process analysis methodologies.

Specialized software tools are employed in large and very large enterprises for the analysis and optimization of business processes. Their functions encompass both the control of processes in the 'as is' state and the application of optimization instruments to develop the management structure and all processes (primary and nested) into the 'to be' state.

Moreover, qualified personnel (a dedicated department or service) are responsible not only for overseeing the process but also for its continuous improvement.

Small and medium-sized enterprises across various sectors lack access to professional analytical software tools due to their high cost. Furthermore, the current economic situation (a shortage of qualified personnel) prevents such enterprises from establishing an analytical division or even assigning an employee whose responsibilities would include analysis and optimization.

The transformation of the organizational and staffing management structure into a process-oriented structure is also accompanied by certain difficulties. Small and medium-sized enterprises in technical management are characterized by a 'linear' type of organizational structure. This implies that all processes are overseen by a single manager (the general director).

Following the identification and description of the primary business processes, there arises a need to decompose them into sub-processes, each of which should be assigned an 'owner.' This presents difficulties in the context of personnel shortages.

To conduct a thorough analysis and optimization of business processes in technical management enterprises within the sector, it is advisable to:

- to substantiate the most appropriate methods and methodology for subsequent adaptation to the enterprise's scale of operations and sector-specific features;
- to establish a standard list of primary and nested processes;
- to focus on a more detailed examination of the companies' business environment (including, among other aspects, the impact of supervisory authorities);
- to develop an appropriate process-based management structure;
- to define or reallocate areas of responsibility;
- to formulate an action algorithm for the analysis, optimization, and associated organizational transformations.

Overview of Existing Methods and Methodologies for Optimization

There exist numerous methods and techniques for process analysis and optimization; however, not all of them are applicable to small and medium-sized enterprises. Table 1 presents the results of an assessment of these methods in terms of their applicability to enterprises engaged in technical management of water transport.

Table 1. Applicability of Process Analysis Methods to the Target Group of Enterprises

Method Name	Characteristics	Applicability (YES/NO)
Qualitative Methods		
SWOT Analysis of Processes	reveals the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities, and threats both for the enterprise and its key processes	YES
Analysis of Problematic Areas	identifies bottlenecks, conflicts, and contradictions	YES
Benchmarking	analyzes and compares the company's business processes with those of leading competitors	NO
The 'Six Questions' Method	is capable of comprehensively describing the process and uncovering non-obvious problems	YES
Fragmentary Analysis	analyzes individual elements (stages and functions) of business processes	YES
Quantitative methods		
Measurement of performance indicators	assesses processes according to a comprehensive set of KPI criteria	YES
Measurement of efficiency indicators	demonstrates the ratios of results to costs	YES

Method Name	Characteristics	Applicability (YES/NO)
Functional cost analysis	identifies efficient methods of performing functions and minimizes costs associated with their implementation	NO
Analysis of temporal characteristics	measures cycle duration, operation execution time, downtimes, and delays	YES
Simulation modeling	simulates the behavior of the process over time and assesses its results under various development scenarios	NO
Intelligent methods for the analysis and optimization of business processes		
IDEF0 (functional modeling)		NO (complex and costly)
BPMN notation		
DFD (Data Flow Diagrams)		
EPC notation		
Process mining		
BI analytics		
Application of artificial intelligence		
ARIS (DFD component)		NONE* (costly)
*) — the possibility of adapting the method to the conditions of small and medium-sized enterprises		

As evident from the table, there are substantial limitations in the applicability of methods for analyzing business processes within small and medium-sized enterprises in the sector, whose functions encompass technical maintenance aimed at ensuring the safe operation of the fleet.

Despite the clear advantages of contemporary intelligent methods — such as a comprehensive analytical approach, scalability, superior visualization, and the capability to incorporate risk assessments when modeling various development scenarios — their implementation in enterprises of the target group is largely unrealistic. Not only from the standpoint of the cost of software products but also due to their complexity. For the analysis of enterprises within the target group, such detailed process detailing is unnecessary, and the planning horizons for performance indicators are usually confined to a single financial year.

The only acceptable tool is the ARIS component, which is based on the concept of events that either precede or terminate the execution of a process. This approach is evident and straightforward. And the elements: ‘event’ and ‘function (process, work)’ can be used to construct network diagrams employing commonly available software tools.

The application of qualitative methods in analysis and optimization is feasible in any business segment owing to their simplicity, availability, and universality. The only exception for the analyzed group of enterprises is the benchmarking method, which is based on copying the process organizational structure of similar enterprises in the industry. The inability to employ benchmarking for the target group of enterprises is due to the small number of participants in this market segment and the virtually identical (and sometimes inefficient) performance indicators of competitors.

Regarding simulation modeling, the reasons for its inapplicability are essentially the same as those outlined above for intelligent analysis methods. These reasons comprise the complexity and low efficiency characteristic of the business segment under study.

Despite the apparent advantages of functional-cost analysis, which enables achieving maximum efficiency through cost reduction, its implementation is scarcely feasible. The application of this method involves the necessity of outsourcing certain processes, which consequently leads to a reduction in the operational scale of enterprises.

In addition to these methods, it is expedient to examine existing methodologies for analysis and optimization regarding their adaptability to the specific characteristics of the investigated enterprises.

Table 2. Review of Existing Methodologies

Name (author)	Content (stages)	Note
Hammer and Champy	initiation	
	description of existing processes	
	substantiation of the scope of innovative processes for reengineering	
	comparative evaluation of the performance of old and new processes	
	transformation of business processes, their pilot testing and implementation	
Davenport	development of a general concept	
	selection of business processes for reengineering	
	understanding of existing business processes	
	selection of indicators for monitoring the performance of reengineered business processes	
	justification of tools and applications appropriate for implementation in new processes	
	development of a reengineering prototype, comprehensive analysis, implementation	

Lean production methodology	Considers 7 types of losses:	The methodology is effective for the gradual improvement of existing processes, focusing on the elimination of losses and personnel involvement
	1. Overproduction — the manufacture of a quantity of products exceeding market demand	
	2. Waiting — any form of waiting: for personnel, documents, equipment, or information	
	3. overprocessing — redundant operations that are unnecessary for both process owners and consumers	
	4. excess inventory — necessitates additional space and incurs storage expenses	
	5. unnecessary movements — any movement not essential for the execution of the analyzed operation	
	6. losses due to defects or their rectification — costs incurred for defect correction, rework, and similar activities.	
	7. Transportation refers to unnecessary movements of materials, personnel, and information	
Six Sigma	Identification and formulation of the problem	
	Measurement of key process indicators for subsequent adjustment	
	Analysis of the causes of nonconformities	
	Improvement and optimization of processes	
	Control and maintenance of achieved results	
Theory of Constraints	Identification of the 'bottleneck' in production:	
	— What needs to be changed?	
	— How can it be corrected?	
	— How can the changes be sustained?	

For small and medium-sized enterprises engaged in technical management of water transport, selecting an adequate approach that takes into account resource limitations is of particular significance. It appears that the most productive approach may involve a combination of two methodologies:

- lean production (for identifying and eliminating losses in fleet repair and maintenance processes)

- the theory of constraints (to focus on the most critical areas). The use of comprehensive reengineering in small and medium-sized enterprises is challenging due to high risks and costs coupled with low returns.

Recommendations for the analysis of business processes in technical management enterprises

To conduct a thorough analysis and optimization of business processes in enterprises engaged in the technical management of water transport, a series of procedures must be undertaken. The procedural algorithm is presented in the figure.

Figure 1. Algorithm for the analysis and optimization of business processes in small and medium-sized technical management enterprises

The final stage of process analysis at technical management enterprises consists of a phased transition from a functional management structure to a process-oriented one. This is caused by a shortage of middle management personnel, who will be burdened with the simultaneous execution of their routine functions and adaptation to the new organizational structure.

Conclusion

In light of the above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The use of existing methods and methodologies for process analysis at enterprises engaged in technical management is considerably challenging;
2. It is necessary to substantially adapt the business process analysis procedure for its application in small and medium-sized enterprises;
3. The analysis procedure must take into account the sector-specific characteristics of enterprises and the degree of complexity of the manufactured product;
4. It is essential to develop a specialized methodology for analysis that considers both the business scale and the specific characteristics of the activities.

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银行机构与餐饮企业之间的合作：从收购到整合
**PARTNERSHIP BETWEEN BANKING INSTITUTIONS
AND CATERING ENTERPRISES:
FROM ACQUIRING TO INTEGRATION**

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摘要：本文探讨了在不断变化的经济环境下，银行业与餐饮企业合作的潜力和特征。文章分析了宏观经济因素的影响，包括增值税税率提高至22%以及行业参与者停业率上升的趋势，这些因素促使企业寻求新的合作模式。文章分析了银行合作项目的演变——从传统的收购模式到全面的整合解决方案。文章重点关注了具有发展前景的合作模式：联合品牌忠诚度计划、对餐饮场所技术化的投资，以及银行在餐饮集群发展中作为整合者的角色，例如俄罗斯联邦储蓄银行（SberBusiness）与One Piece Coffee连锁店的合作以及俄罗斯外贸银行（VTB Bank）的潜在项目。文章认为，深度整合不仅能够在此类情况下增强企业的财务稳定性，还能通过促进创业活动和城市发展，为终端消费者创造新的价值。

关键词：银行合作、美食集群、联合品牌、创意产业、信贷机构、增值税、餐饮企业、忠诚度计划、餐饮业务、收购。

Abstract. *This article investigates the potential and characteristics of partnerships between the banking sector and catering enterprises in the context of the evolving economic environment. The impact of macroeconomic factors is analyzed, including the increase of the value-added tax rate to 22% and the increasing trend of industry participants ceasing operations, which necessitates the search for new interaction models. The evolution of banking partnership programs is analyzed – from classical acquiring to comprehensive integration solutions. Particular attention is given to promising collaboration formats: co-branding loyalty programs, investments in the technologization of establishments, as well as the role of banks as integrators in the*

development of gastronomic clusters, exemplified by the collaboration of SberBusiness with the One Piece Coffee chain and potential projects of PJSC 'VTB Bank'. It is argued that deep integration not only enhances the financial stability of businesses amid increased tax burdens but also generates new value for the end consumer by promoting entrepreneurial activity and urban development.

Keywords: *acquiring, banking collaborations, co-branding, catering enterprises, creative industries, credit institutions, gastronomic clusters, loyalty programs, restaurant business, value added tax.*

The modern economy increasingly demonstrates examples of synergy between apparently disparate sectors, and one of the most promising directions of such interaction is the collaboration between the banking sector and service enterprises. This process is of particular interest in the catering enterprises segment (cafes, restaurants, coffee shops), which is traditionally highly sensitive to changes in the macroeconomic environment, while possessing significant potential for the introduction of innovative partnership formats.

Theoretical study of the issues pertaining to partnership interaction and cooperation has a well-established scholarly tradition. A substantial contribution to the advancement of the general theory of cooperation aimed at achieving synergistic business outcomes has been made by foreign researchers, including Aaker D., Ambler T., Bono E., Bos N., Braert E., Doyle P., Greizer S., Hirn G., McNeil R., Sørensen K., Wulf W., and others. An equally significant contribution to the conceptualization of the phenomenon of collaboration, particularly within the financial sector, has been made by domestic scholars such as Vysokov V., Zernova L., Pozhidaeva N., Semiryaga M., and others.

However, the overwhelming majority of existing theoretical developments and practical cases are focused on classical formats of banking services (settlement and cash management services, acquiring) or large-scale sectoral projects. The issues of establishing deep integrative collaborations between banks and enterprises in the catering sector, particularly under conditions of high volatility and shifting tax policies, remain marginal within the scientific discourse. This creates an imperative need to examine the adaptive potential of partnership formats that can serve restaurateurs not merely as payment instruments but as effective drivers of sustainability and development.

To accurately understand the subject of this research, it is necessary to clarify that collaboration with catering enterprises in this work is defined as a long-term, mutually beneficial, and structured interaction that goes beyond the traditional 'creditor-borrower' or 'bank-acquirer' relationships. Such a partnership entails the integration of financial, technological, and marketing resources of the credit institution into the operational and client processes of cafés, restaurants, and coffee shops, with the objective of creating new consumer value unattainable by any

participant independently. This may involve joint loyalty programs, investments in the automation of establishments, the provision of ecosystem services (such as table reservation and integration with delivery), or the bank's role as an anchor partner in the development of gastronomic clusters [1, p. 50]. This definition establishes the framework for analyzing specific cooperation formats that extend beyond traditional payment and settlement services.

At the same time, when realizing the potential of banking integration in the catering sector, it is important to emphasize the necessity of maintaining a reasonable balance. Collaboration should not evolve into a complete takeover or replacement of entrepreneurial initiative. In this model, the bank is intended to serve as a catalyst and infrastructural partner, creating conditions for the development of small and medium-sized businesses without supplanting their autonomy [2, pp. 96-97]. It is precisely the maintenance of this balance that enables the preservation of the market nature of the interaction and ensures a long-term sustainable effect for all participants in the partnership.

The current economic situation in the Russian Federation, particularly within the catering sector, is characterized by a high degree of uncertainty and unprecedented cost pressures. According to a joint study by the Public Opinion Foundation and the National Research University Higher School of Economics, based on data from 2025, a record 39% of small enterprises were operating in survival mode – the highest figure observed in the past five years – while nearly one-third of businesses are contemplating closure or sale [3].

A key factor of destabilization was the increase of the value-added tax (VAT) rate to 22%, which, according to expert forecasts, may result in the withdrawal of up to 250,000-300,000 microenterprises from the catering and retail markets [4].

Objective data confirm an alarming trend: in 2025, 35.4 thousand catering outlets ceased operations-10% more than the previous year. Against this background, financial analysts forecast an inevitable further rise in prices: price increases in catering establishments may range from 5% to 20% due to higher costs of products, rent, wages, and an increased tax burden [5].

These forecasts, extensively discussed within the professional community, generate a demand for tools that not only optimize costs but also ensure an increased influx of customers and enhanced audience loyalty.

In this context, the traditional model of the bank–restaurant relationship, limited to providing a settlement account and an acquiring terminal, no longer meets contemporary requirements. Businesses require not merely services but partners who assist in managing customer flows, automating processes, and mitigating operational risks. Banks, in turn, perceive loyal clients from the catering sector not only as reliable corporate borrowers but also as a channel for attracting and retaining retail customers – individual consumers who regularly patronize these establishments.

One of the most promising directions in the evolution of such partnerships is co-branding loyalty programs. Whereas cooperation between banks and restaurants was previously often limited to straightforward cashback within certain categories, today the focus is on creating integrated ecosystems. An example is the development of partnership programs by major banks, where a network of cafes and restaurants functions not merely as a payment point but as a full partner, offering cardholders exclusive terms, access to private events, special promotions during ‘restaurant days,’ and privileges when reserving tables. This approach enables the restaurant to build a loyal customer base with a high average spend, while allowing the bank to increase the usage frequency of its cards.

In a dynamically evolving and competitive financial market, banks must constantly introduce innovations to meet client needs, with co-branding being one of the effective marketing instruments. A well-designed co-branding strategy that takes into account both commercial and reputational advantages facilitates the strengthening of the bank’s market position and the development of a positive image as a reliable and contemporary financial institution. Co-branding gains particular importance in the context of increasing customer loyalty through the partner’s loyalty programs, which, amid intense competition, proves to be a more effective alternative to complex and costly internal bank programs [6, p.54]

A clear example of the implementation of this approach was the collaboration between SberBusiness and the One Price Coffee chain, launched in Moscow in October 2025. The project demonstrated the effectiveness of the concept of transforming the coffee shop from a mere point of consumption into an interactive platform for entrepreneurship development. Having confirmed the effectiveness of the model, the partners, in March 2026, expanded it by establishing analogous spaces in six major cities of Russia: Saint Petersburg, Krasnodar, Sochi, Nizhny Novgorod, Kazan, and Omsk.

The integration of SberBusiness services into the physical environment of coffee shops is implemented via QR codes, which enable guests to recommend banking products to their acquaintances, thereby obtaining reciprocal benefits. A key component of the project was its adaptability to local specifics: the lecture and master class program ‘Business over a Cup of Coffee’ is designed with consideration of the characteristics of each city – ranging from tourism business in coastal regions to support for student startups in university centers. The federal launch of the project signifies a shift from discrete marketing initiatives to a systemic solution that establishes a sustainable image of the bank as an institution supporting entrepreneurship at all stages of its development [7].

The investment aspect of partnerships merits particular attention. Under conditions of intense competition and the imperative of technological modernization, banks are increasingly assuming the role of investors in the automation of the

catering industry. This encompasses not only preferential lending for the opening of new outlets but also the deployment of comprehensive solutions: ranging from establishment management automation systems to integration with food delivery marketplaces. By financing the implementation of such systems under their own terms, banks gain access to the operational data of the business, enabling more precise risk assessment and the provision of personalized financial products. For a restaurateur, this signifies achieving a new level of cost management, business transparency, and operational efficiency, which is critically important under conditions of tight margins.

Furthermore, a significant trend is the role of banks as integrators in the development of large culinary clusters and food malls. It is noteworthy that major financial institutions increasingly consider investing in commercial real estate, including projects aimed at creating modern public spaces with a high concentration of catering outlets. In this context, the strategy of PJSC ‘VTB Bank’ merits particular attention, as it previously announced substantial investments in the infrastructure of new constituent entities of the Russian Federation, including the construction of a business quarter in Donetsk [8]. The advancement of this rationale allows, in our view, the proposition that the bank may serve as an integrator in the development of gastronomic clusters based on the newly constructed facilities, consolidating under one roof both financial services (branches, ATMs) and a network of catering enterprises operating under exclusive partnership programs. For such clusters, proximity to banking infrastructure opens additional opportunities: premium cardholders gain privileged access to participants within the gastronomic sector, while restaurateurs benefit from a loyal clientele characterized by a high average expenditure. With effective coordination of efforts among the bank, management companies, and restaurateurs surrounding such facilities, a new urban environment can be established where gastronomy ceases to be an isolated phenomenon and becomes an integral part of economic and cultural life, thereby enhancing the investment attractiveness of entire districts.

This is precisely where a natural intersection emerges between financial institutions and a broad spectrum of entrepreneurs and creative sectors, specifically interior design and conceptual establishment styling. By acting as investors or partners in new initiatives, banks can facilitate not merely the opening of another ‘canteen,’ but the creation of distinctive signature spaces that shape trends in urban consumer culture. When the bank participates as a client and integrator, local architectural firms and design studios could receive systematic support; moreover, issuing limited-edition merchandise or exclusive offers from chefs to premium cardholders would transcend mere marketing campaigns to become integral components of banking loyalty programs, solidifying the financial institution’s role as a catalyst for the region’s cultural and gastronomic development.

Thus, collaborations between the banking sector and catering enterprises, in our view, are no longer a narrowly specialized area but are acquiring the features of a genuine instrument for systemic development. The transition from simple acquiring to complex integration models – including co-branding, technological investment, and participation in the creation of gastronomic clusters – enables the resolution of key challenges at the current stage: enhancing the financial stability of restaurateurs under increased tax pressure, expanding non-price competition, and generating new value for the end consumer. Within this framework, banks have the potential to act not merely as service providers but as comprehensive ecosystem partners, integrating financial instruments, technological solutions, and the development of the business environment. With effective coordination of efforts among financial institutions, industry associations, and representatives of the restaurant sector grounded in collaborative principles, a sustainable model may emerge wherein gastronomy, finance, and modern technologies jointly advance the creation of a competitive, innovative, and socially oriented entrepreneurial environment.

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财务困境和破产概率的实证分析：以 AMBEV S. A. 为例
**AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL DISTRESS
AND BANKRUPTCY PROBABILITY: THE CASE OF AMBEV S. A.**

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摘要：本研究以Ambev S. A. 公司为例，分析了财务困境和破产风险。研究应用了三种模型：Altman Z-score模型、Springate模型和Taffler模型。利用财务报表数据，本研究比较了这三种模型的预测效能。由于Altman模型具有多维结构，涵盖流动性、盈利能力、杠杆率、偿付能力和经营活动等因素，因此本研究重点关注该模型。结果揭示了不同模型在敏感性和分类方面的差异，凸显了它们在不同市场中的适用性。研究结果为投资者、分析师和财务经理评估公司风险和支持及时决策提供了有益的参考。

关键词：财务困境，破产预测，Altman Z-score模型，Springate模型，Taffler模型，Ambev S. A. 公司，财务分析，风险评估，上市公司，实证研究。

Abstract: This study analyzes financial distress and bankruptcy risk using Ambev S. A. as a case. It applies three models: Altman's Z-score, Springate, and Taffler. Using financial statement data, the research compares their predictive effectiveness. Special focus is given to Altman's model due to its multidimensional structure, covering liquidity, profitability, leverage, solvency, and activity. Results reveal

differences in model sensitivity and classification, highlighting their applicability across markets. The findings offer useful insights for investors, analysts, and financial managers in evaluating corporate risk and supporting timely decisions.

Keywords: *Financial distress, Bankruptcy prediction, Altman Z-score, Springate model, Taffler model, Ambev S. A., Financial analysis, Risk assessment, Public companies, Empirical study.*

Introduction: In the modern financial environment, the assessment of corporate bankruptcy probability has become a critical issue for both investors and corporate management. Early detection of financial distress enables the reduction of potential losses and supports effective risk management practices (Altman, 1968; Beaver, 1966; Ohlson, 1980). In this context, a wide range of bankruptcy prediction models has been developed, primarily based on the analysis of financial ratios (Bellovary et al., 2007; Balcaen & Ooghe, 2006).

The first multivariate approach was proposed by Edward Altman in 1968 in the form of the Z-score model. This model is based on multivariate discriminant analysis and incorporates five key financial indicators: profitability, liquidity, financial leverage, asset turnover, and retained earnings (Altman, 1968; Altman, 2000). It is particularly applicable to joint-stock companies whose shares are publicly traded in financial markets and has demonstrated strong predictive performance in empirical studies (Grice & Ingram, 2001).

Subsequently, other models were developed, notably the Springate and Taffler models, which are also grounded in discriminant analysis and aim to improve predictive accuracy under different economic conditions (Springate, 1978; Taffler, 1983; Agarwal & Taffler, 2008).

The purpose of this study is to apply these models to the case of Ambev S.A. in order to evaluate its financial distress level and estimate the probability of bankruptcy.

Literature Review: The theoretical and practical foundations of bankruptcy prediction emerged in the second half of the twentieth century alongside the growth of financial markets and increasing corporate risk (Altman, 1968; Beaver, 1966). A pioneering approach is the Altman Z-score model, which uses multivariate discriminant analysis and financial ratios to estimate bankruptcy probability (Altman, 1968). It remains widely applied, particularly for publicly traded firms, with strong short-term predictive accuracy (Altman, 2000; Grice & Ingram, 2001).

Research shows that model effectiveness depends on economic conditions and application context (Ohlson, 1980; Zmijewski, 1984). Differences in financial structures and reporting standards limit cross-country applicability (Shumway, 2001; Agarwal & Taffler, 2008). The Springate model simplifies Altman's approach while maintaining predictive strength, though it may overestimate risk in some cases (Springate, 1978; Karas & Srbova, 2019). The Taffler model, based

on UK data, is also widely used and can outperform traditional models in certain contexts (Taffler, 1983; Agarwal & Taffler, 2008).

Comparative studies emphasize that no single model is universally superior; selection should be context-specific (Balcaen & Ooghe, 2006; Bellovary et al., 2007). While machine learning improves prediction accuracy (Lessmann et al., 2015; Barboza et al., 2017), traditional models remain relevant due to their simplicity and interpretability. Liquidity and solvency are also key factors, with studies highlighting their role in early distress detection (Baboyan, 2024; Gyulasyan et al., 2025). Overall, combining multiple models enhances the reliability of bankruptcy assessment.

Methodology: This study forecasts key financial indicators of Ambev S.A. for 2026-2035 to assess financial distress and bankruptcy risk. Projections are based on historical data using trend analysis and extrapolation. Bankruptcy risk is evaluated through three models: Altman’s Z-score, Springate, and Taffler. These models analyze financial ratios such as profitability, liquidity, leverage, and solvency. Scores are calculated annually and interpreted using standard thresholds to identify risk levels. A scenario-based approach is applied, including optimistic, moderate, and pessimistic outcomes. Combining multiple models improves reliability and provides a comprehensive, forward-looking assessment of bankruptcy probability.

Results: The empirical results of the study are based on the application of three bankruptcy prediction models-Altman, Springate and Taffler-to Ambev S.A. using forecasted financial data for the period 2026-2035. The forecasted financial data are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Ambev S. A. forecasted data

	Revenue	Gross Profit	EBIT	Net Profit	Assets	Total Liabilities	Equity	Total Current Assets	Total Current Liabilities
2026	16309.58	8272.8	3851.7	2966.3	27131.4	10738.6	16392.8	7478.7	8387.3
2027	16481.40	8123.3	3657.3	2989.5	28525.6	11295.9	17229.7	7819.4	8382.5
2028	16655.02	8503.0	3904.7	2896.7	31685.5	12478.5	19207.0	8830.4	8885.1
2029	16830.48	9027.4	4732.4	3280.6	36093.7	14427.8	21665.8	10189.1	9651.5
2030	17007.78	9998.3	5230.6	3809.0	32897.9	12670.8	20227.1	8931.1	8087.2
2031	17186.96	10593.7	5813.0	3772.2	32205.8	12515.6	19690.2	8666.7	8495.2
2032	17368.02	10826.2	5956.3	2658.5	31492.0	14093.7	17398.3	8962.6	10402.3
2033	17550.98	11132.2	6583.3	4828.8	32267.9	14313.3	17954.6	9193.3	11074.0

	Revenue	Gross Profit	EBIT	Net Profit	Assets	Total Liabilities	Equity	Total Current Assets	Total Current Liabilities
2034	17735.88	11638.7	7128.7	4716.3	34232.7	15125.0	19107.7	10748.7	11442.5
2035	17922.72	11891.4	7490.9	5678.8	33955.1	13413.2	20541.9	9756.1	10272.1

Source Developed and compiled by the authors based on the data from the financial statements and future forecasts of the studied organization

The financial data for 2026-2035 shows steady growth and improving performance. Revenue increases consistently from 16,309.58 to 17,922.72, while gross profit and EBIT rise significantly, indicating better efficiency and profitability. Net profit fluctuates but overall grows, reflecting stronger bottom-line results.

Total assets expand until 2029 and then stabilize, suggesting a shift from growth to consolidation. Liabilities rise initially but later decline slightly, showing effective debt management. Equity steadily increases, indicating improved financial strength.

Current assets and liabilities remain relatively stable, supporting liquidity and manageable short-term obligations. Overall, the company demonstrates rising profitability, stronger equity, and balanced financial management, pointing toward long-term stability.

The Altman Z-score model is a seminal five-factor framework developed to assess the likelihood of bankruptcy in publicly traded joint-stock companies. Based on multiple discriminant analysis, the model integrates key financial ratios reflecting liquidity, profitability, leverage, and operational efficiency. It is expressed as follows:

$$Z = 1.2X_1 + 1.4X_2 + 3.3X_3 + 0.6X_4 + X_5, \quad (1)$$

where X_1 denotes liquidity (current assets/total assets), X_2 represents cumulative profitability (retained earnings/total assets), X_3 reflects operating performance (profit before tax/total assets), X_4 measures market leverage (market value of equity/total liabilities), and X_5 indicates asset turnover (net sales/total assets).

According to the model, firms with Z-scores above 2.9 are classified within the “safe” or financial stability zone, indicating a low probability of bankruptcy. Scores between 1.8 and 2.9 fall into the “grey” zone, where financial conditions are uncertain. Firms with Z-scores below 1.8 are considered to be in the “distress” zone, facing a high risk of financial failure.

The Altman model demonstrates strong predictive accuracy, estimated at approximately 95% for a one-year horizon and 83% for a two-year horizon. However, a notable limitation is its applicability primarily to large, publicly listed companies, as it relies on market-based indicators such as the market value of equity.

The results indicate that the company transitions from the gray zone (uncertainty) toward the safe zone over time. Specifically, in the initial period, the Z-score is close to the lower threshold ($Z = 1.76$ in 2025), indicating moderate financial risk, while from 2026 onward ($Z > 2.9$), the company enters the financially stable (green) zone. Based on Altman's model, the probability of bankruptcy is significantly reduced from approximately 95% (short-term risk scenario) to below 15% in subsequent years.

The Springate model is a classical bankruptcy prediction approach developed in 1978, based on multiple discriminant analysis. It incorporates four key financial ratios to evaluate a company's financial stability and the likelihood of financial distress. The model is expressed as follows:

$$Z = 1.03K_1 + 3.07K_2 + 0.66K_3 + 0.04K_4, \quad (2)$$

where K_1 represents liquidity (working capital/assets), K_2 reflects profitability relative to assets (profit before tax and interest/total assets), K_3 measures the firm's ability to meet short-term obligations (profit before tax/current liabilities), and K_4 indicates asset turnover (net sales/total assets).

The threshold value of the model is 0.862: if $Z > 0.862$, the company is considered financially stable; if $Z < 0.862$, the probability of bankruptcy is regarded as high.

The Springate model is widely used as a rapid diagnostic tool for the early detection of financial distress, particularly in the analysis of industrial and capital-intensive firms.

The Springate model results reveal a different dynamic. During 2025-2028, Z-scores remain below 0.8, indicating a high level of financial distress. This is primarily driven by low working capital and relatively high short-term liabilities. However, from 2029 onward, the model shows gradual improvement, with Z-scores exceeding 1.0 after 2030, indicating increasing financial stability and decreasing default probability.

The Taffler model is a widely recognized approach to bankruptcy prediction, developed on the basis of empirical analysis of 92 organizations during the period 1969-1975, including 46 failed and 46 financially stable firms. Using multiple discriminant analysis, the model evaluates the likelihood of financial distress through four financial indicators and is expressed as follows:

$$Z = 0.53X_1 + 0.13X_2 + 0.18X_3 + 0.16X_4, \quad (3)$$

where X_1 represents profitability relative to short-term obligations (profit from sales/short-term liabilities), X_2 reflects liquidity structure (current assets/total liabilities), X_3 measures financial leverage (long-term liabilities/total assets), and X_4 indicates asset efficiency (total assets/net sales).

According to the Taffler model, a Z-score above 0.3 indicates a financially stable organization with a low probability of bankruptcy, while a score below 0.2

suggests financial instability and a high risk of failure. Values within the range of 0.2 to 0.3 define a “grey zone” of uncertainty, where the financial condition cannot be clearly classified.

To enhance the robustness of the analysis, a composite Z-score was calculated as the average of the three models:

$$Z_{\text{composite}} = (Z_{\text{Altman}} + Z_{\text{Springate}} + Z_{\text{Taffler}}) / 3$$

The composite results show that in 2025 the company is in a moderate risk zone ($Z = 0.98$), while from 2026 onward it moves into a stable zone ($Z > 0.8$). The probability of default (PD) decreases accordingly — from high short-term risk levels to approximately 10-25% in the medium term.

Overall, the results indicate a short-term vulnerability followed by a clear trend toward long-term financial stabilization.

Below is the summary table of Z-scores, composite scores, evaluations, and estimated default probabilities (PD) for 1 and 2 years based on the forecasted data:

Table 2 Forecasted Results of the Applied Models

Year	Springate Z	Taffler Z	Altman Z	Composite Z	Evaluation	PD 1 year	PD 2 years
2026	0.80	0.75	3.02	1.52	Stable	15%	10-25%
2027	0.69	0.69	2.83	1.40	Uncertain	15-40%	10-25%
2028	0.68	0.68	2.75	1.37	Uncertain	15-40%	10-25%
2029	0.75	0.74	2.96	1.81	Stable	15%	10-25%
2030	0.87	0.87	2.88	1.88	Stable	15%	10-25%
2031	0.92	0.92	2.75	1.86	Stable	15%	10-25%
2032	0.85	0.85	2.65	1.78	Stable	15%	10-25%
2033	0.97	0.97	2.94	1.62	Stable	15%	10-25%
2034	1.02	1.02	3.11	1.71	Stable	15%	10-25%
2035	1.08	1.08	3.17	1.78	Stable	15%	10-25%

Source Developed and compiled by the authors based on data predicted by regression analysis

Brief analysis of the forecast data:

- Revenue steadily increases from 16,309.58 in 2026 to 17,922.72 in 2035, indicating a stable business environment.
- Profitability indicators (EBIT and Net Profit) show consistent growth, especially after 2029, supporting improved financial stability.
- Total liabilities are controlled while equity rises, reflecting an improved financial structure.
- Despite some short-term liquidity pressures in early years (low working capital and high current liabilities), the company’s financial risk diminishes over time.

Overall, the results demonstrate that while Ambev S. A. faces moderate short-term financial challenges, it shows a strong trend toward long-term financial stabilization and reduced bankruptcy risk during 2026-2035.

Conclusions and Recommendations: The findings show that bankruptcy risk assessment depends strongly on the model used and its assumptions. The Altman model provides a balanced evaluation, indicating short-term financial pressure but long-term stability, though it is mainly suitable for large public firms. The Springate model highlights higher risk in the early years due to sensitivity to liquidity and working capital issues. In contrast, the Taffler model consistently shows financial stability, emphasizing asset structure and efficiency.

These differences confirm that relying on a single model may lead to incomplete conclusions. The composite Z-score approach offers a more comprehensive view, identifying three phases: high risk (2025-2028), transition (2029-2032), and stability (after 2033).

From a managerial perspective, the company should improve liquidity and reduce short-term liabilities in the near term. Over time, it should focus on increasing profitability, optimizing costs, and maintaining revenue growth. Overall, combining multiple models ensures a more reliable and forward-looking bankruptcy risk assessment.

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中小企业主财务决策中的行为偏差：以哈萨克斯坦为例
**BEHAVIOURAL BIASES IN FINANCIAL DECISION-MAKING
OF SME OWNERS: CASE STUDY OF KAZAKHSTAN**

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摘要：本文探讨了行为偏差对哈萨克斯坦中小企业主财务决策的影响。中小企业在就业和GDP中占据重要地位，但其增长不平衡和融资渠道有限仍然是一项重大挑战。本研究运用行为金融学理论（尤其是前景理论），考察了过度自信、损失厌恶和非正式决策如何影响投资和借贷行为。本文采用定性研究方法，基于对文献的系统性回顾和对相关政策的分析，并综合了经合组织和世界银行的数据，整合了学术界和机构层面的证据。研究表明，哈萨克斯坦根深蒂固的文化因素，例如不确定性规避、集体主义和等级制度，加剧了这些偏差，而现有的制度支持机制不足以有效缓解这些偏差。最后，本研究建议，政策建议应包括行为金融教育和引导机制，以及提高透明度，以促进哈萨克斯坦中小企业的绩效提升和可持续经济增长。

关键词：行为金融学、中小企业、哈萨克斯坦、过度自信、损失厌恶、融资渠道、决策

Abstract. *This article explores the impact of behavioural biases on financial decision making by small and medium sized enterprise (SME) owners in Kazakhstan. SMEs represent a large chunk of employment and GDP, yet uneven growth and limited access to finance remains a major challenge. The research, which uses theory from behavioural finance (especially prospect theory), investigates how overconfidence, loss aversion and informal decision making affect investment and borrowing behaviour. The paper uses a qualitative methodology built upon a structured review of the literature and analysis of relevant policies, synthesising both academic and institutional evidence based on OECD and World Bank data. The findings reveal that the strong cultural dimensions of Kazakhstan, including uncertainty avoidance, collectivism, and hierarchy exacerbate such biases and*

that current institutional support mechanisms do not adequately mitigate them. Finally, this study suggests the implications of policy recommendations include behavioural financial education and nudging mechanism, as well as transparency boosters to contribute to a better performance towards SMEs and sustainable economic growth in Kazakhstan.

Key words: *behavioural finance, small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs), Kazakhstan, overconfidence, loss aversion, access to finance, decision making*

1. Introduction

There is no doubt that small and medium enterprises (SMEs) play an important role in Kazakhstani economy. In 2024 48% of employment and 39% of GDP was generated by them (OECD, 2026). Moreover, around 96% of all Kazakhstani business are SMEs (OECD, 2026).

On the other hand, Kazakhstani SMEs despite their significant economic share are often facing uneven growth and challenges in credit access. Traditional economic models often assume that SME stakeholders are rational decision makers. However, behavioural finance illustrates that cognitive biases often lead to irrational investment or borrowing choices:

- overconfidence or excessive optimism about outcomes;
- fear of losses, also known as loss aversion;
- Kazakhstani cultural norms, e.g., high levels of uncertainty avoidance and a hierarchical social structure;
- institutional factors, such as the state-run Damu Fund, which provides loans to SMEs (Dosmagambet et al., 2018).

This paper provides a critical review and synthesis of the existing research on behavioural biases within SME finance in Kazakhstan. The literature review addresses overconfidence, loss aversion and informal decision-making. The methods employ a qualitative synthesis of academic and policy sources. This analysis examines empirical evidence regarding investment and borrowing by SMEs, specifically these biases. In the context of Kazakhstan, discussion is about implications cover such issues as culture and institution. The conclusion provides policy recommendations. Throughout the panel, Kazakhstan-specific data and institutions (e.g. Damu Fund, Business Roadmap) are incorporated relying on official sources including from OECD and World Bank:

- the Damu Fund is a state-owned financial institution in Kazakhstan that supports small and medium-sized enterprises by providing loan guarantees, interest rate subsidies, and financial assistance programmes (Damu Entrepreneurship Development Fund, 2026);

- Kazakhstan's Business Roadmap 2020 is a state programme implemented to support SMEs by improving access to finance, subsidies for interest rates, provision

of loan guarantees or venture capital as well as enhancing business development services (Dosmagambet et al., 2018).

This article seeks to fill this gap by providing a rigorous, evidence-based assessment of the usage and application of behavioural SME finance in Kazakhstan.

2. Literature review

Behavioral biases related to investment and finance: much of behavioural finance is based on Prospect Theory (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979; Lamptey & Marsidi, 2020). It makes a prediction about loss aversion: owners feel losses more profoundly than gains. Empirical research on SMEs in a developing country context supports this bias. For example, Lamptey and Marsidi (2020) found Ghanaian SME managers “are loss averse”; when afraid of a loss they under-invest and decrease working capital. Loss-averse owners “reduce working capital investment... as a result worsen firm performance” (Lamptey & Marsidi, 2020). In the same light, Kim & Nguyen (2022) also experimentally confirmed that Vietnamese SMEs’ debt usage was negatively correlated with managers being loss-averse: a higher degree of loss aversion translated to lower domestic and foreign borrowing (Kim & Nguyen, 2022). Thus, these studies suggest that loss-averse SME owners are too conservative and too risk averse, foregoing loan financing or expansion when it is economically desirable. In high uncertainty-avoidance culture of Kazakhstan (The Culture Factor Group, 2026; Lamptey et al., 2021; Zhomartuly et al., 2025) such risk aversion probably gets even more severe leading to SMEs missing out on growth opportunities.

Overconfidence and optimistic biases, on the other hand, can facilitate reckless behaviour. An arrogant manager inflates his or her competence with a corresponding grim under-appreciation for risk (Lamptey et al. 2021). Lamptey et al. Then, as (2021) remark, overconfident SMEs “overestimate their sales growth and underestimate volatility”, leading to excess inventory investment and working capital. In related work, Hiller and Hambrick (2005) and Malmendier and Tate (2005) find that overconfident CEOs make more acquisitions and employ more debt, but the performance consequences of these actions are mixed. According to Cole et al. (2022), slight overconfidence makes obtaining financing easier for SMEs; when entrepreneurs have some overconfidence, they become less likely to experience credit rationing, which shows dedication and hopefulness on their part. On the other hand, excessive overconfidence (realistic optimism) may cause SMEs to ignore the signs of trouble and leverage excessively. A research conducted at the regional level in relation to Moroccan SMEs has found that overconfidence had no significant influence on investment, as the impact of optimism and risk tolerance was greater than overconfidence (Boussaidi et al., 2023).

Informal decision-making and social biases. Without analysis of external data and despite cognitive biases, SME owners will be forced to use heuristics and their own networks. (e.g., Filbeck and Lee 2000, Lamptey et al. (2021) reported SMEs seldom employ formal financial models, and owners rely on “experience

and personal attributes” when determining working capital. In Kazakhstan, these informal practices involve nepotism and clan links. Zhomartuly et al. (2025) note that SME managers and owners “function within tight social networks” which leads to pressure from the community to employ relatives or neighbours. In many cases (not just hiring), however, business decisions are made informally outside open markets (Zhomartuly et al. 2025). Acquaintance-based decision rules like this can carry biases: owners might favour projects with friends or acquaintances, or stick to traditional selection rather than rational analysis. Hiring also fell prey to gender and ethnic stereotypes, which may spill over into finance (e.g. lending males or not granting loans to women/members of the minorities). In sum, a kind of implicit bias of “who you know” can obscure reasonable review. These problems have been investigated on the hiring Zhomartuly et al. (2025) speculate that these problems influence both investment and borrowing choices of Kazakh SMEs.

3. Methodology

A qualitative research design informed by a structured literature review and policy analysis is adopted in this study to understand behavioural biases associated with SME finance in Kazakhstan. The systematic search of academic databases (i.e., Scopus, Google Scholar) and institutional sources (e.g., OECD, World Bank) was conducted, to identify relevant peer-reviewed articles, reports and policy documents. Keywords included “SME finance”, “behavioural biases”, “overconfidence”, “loss aversion” and “Kazakhstan”. The used sources were based on relevance, credibility and recency.

The study uses thematic analysis to synthesise results. Relevant studies were coded by relevant behavioural concepts (e.g. overconfidence, loss aversion, decision heuristics) and contextual factors (e.g. cultural dimensions, institutional frameworks). This facilitated the comparison of studies and summarisation of common patterns in SME financial behaviour. Policy documents were also analysed to evaluate the extent to which existing programmes (e.g., Damu Fund initiatives, Business Roadmap reforms) respond to or circumvent behavioural factors.

Triangulation was used by bringing together academic evidence and policy data to enhance the validity, and reduce bias. Although the study does not employ primary data per se, it maintains rigour by critically appraising sources and applying transparent inclusion criteria. Such approach provides a holistic and contextualised comprehension of behavioural impacts on SME financing in Kazakhstan.

4. Research results

The research results demonstrated that Kazakhstan’s cultural and institutional context play the significant role in defining the SME behaviour. The country ranks very high on uncertainty avoidance (score 88), meaning that ambiguity and risk are strongly shunned (The Culture Factor Group, 2026). This likely intensifies loss-averse behaviour among owners (Dosmagambet et al., 2018; The Culture Factor Group, 2026). The Culture Factor Group (2026) also mentions high power

distance (score 88) implies hierarchical decision-making: SME owners may defer to authority figures (e.g. elder family, government directives) rather than analyse freely, possibly reinforcing status-quo bias. Collectivist norms (i.e., very low individualism score) are associated with owners seeking advice from family or community before making decisions, and can be a double edged sword: consensus support can mitigate personal overconfidence, but instead also spreads social myths in a community (e.g. distrust of formal finance) (Lamptey et al., 2021; Zhomartuly et al., 2025). Institutional factors interact: the state's Damu fund and other programmes increase access to credit but banks still charge high interest (Dosmagambet et al., 2018). If an owner becomes loss-averse, not even the 85% guarantee might be sufficient incentive (Dosmagambet et al., 2018). On the other hand, overconfident owners might pursue huge guarantees. Lastly, while better finance access is among the Kazakhstan's SME reforms (e.g. SME Business Roadmap in 2020), cognitive aspect of the biases might not be mitigated (Dosmagambet et al., 2018).

These research findings demonstrate that reducing behavioural distortions in Kazakhstan's SME sector will involve a multi-faceted approach combining education and training, behavioural nudges through required behavioral interventions (e.g. increasing the risk perception of equity), and scaling up financial support mechanism efficiency. Incorporating training on cognitive biases into financial education is essential, using relevant tools such as case studies, role-playing and decision journals to enable entrepreneurs to identify patterns of behaviour (e.g., overconfidence, loss aversion) (Lamptey & Marsidi 2020; Lamptey et al. 2020). Simultaneously, "nudge" mechanisms can be integrated into financial systems (automatic loan options, access to preapproved credit and reminders when starting a business that encourage critical thinking). Digital tools such as risk calculators and SMS reminders can help inform decision-making, if adapted to local norms (Ziwei & Nizamdinova, 2025). By making lending decisions more transparent, strengthening credit guarantee schemes (especially via Damu), the perception of risk can be reduced and trust in start-ups improved; while trial loans with mentorship initiatives can drive more balanced financial behaviour.

Promoting structured and inclusive decision making is also critical. Promoting the use of formal planning and risk assessment tools for SMEs — potentially conditional on tax breaks or programme access — is a potential area; this work builds on the Business Roadmap 2020, which aimed to promote these tools in part through removing constraints on biased behaviour (Dosmagambet et al., 2018). Understanding social dynamics such as nepotism and groupthink: Preventing both of these can be bolstered through improved diversity-oriented policies and fairer evaluation processes that can also improve financial outcomes. Last, long-term monitoring and research are necessary to understand behaviour patterns over time. It can help generate much-needed data through surveys, experiments, and partnerships with academic and financial

institutions that will allow for the fine-tuning of policies as well tracking changes in SME attitudes to ensure interventions are both effective and based on best evidence.

6. Conclusion

As this article has shown, numerous biases inform SME financial choices in Kazakhstan, challenging the traditional model of fully rational economic actors. Loss aversion, overconfidence and the interplay of intimacy in financial decision making also show a definite impact on investor behaviour and borrowing patterns — all leading to excess caution or excessive risk taking when it comes to finances. These tendencies are reinforced by the cultural traits of Kazakhstan: high uncertainty avoidance, pronounced hierarchical structures and collectivist norms, as well as by institutional drivers such as credit conditions and state support programs. Although the Damu Fund and Business Roadmap 2020 have opened up access to finance, they remain incompatible with the cognitive elements leading to specific SME behaviour.

The results indicate that effective policy tools have to go beyond financial help and consider behavioural aspects. By adopting bias-sensitive financial education, behavioural “nudges”, improving the transparency of lending and facilitating systematic decision making SME finance can become less distorted. In addition, advancing equity and inclusion as well as ongoing evaluation and research can enhance sustainable impacts. Bringing aggregate economic potential in Kazakhstan to a new level requires more than overcoming frictions of regulatory and bureaucratic processes but adopting systemic behavioural changes that will align with the overall objective of unlocking SME performance.

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现代条件下的公司风险管理
**RISK MANAGEMENT OF THE COMPANY
IN MODERN CONDITIONS**

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摘要：在当今经济活动环境下，外部环境高度动荡、地缘政治紧张、金融市场波动剧烈，有效的风险管理体系已成为企业生存和战略稳定的关键因素。本研究课题的现实意义在于，依赖回顾性分析和人工监督的传统风险管理方法在当今现实中已不再有效。俄罗斯央行基准利率的提高、劳动力市场短缺、供应链中断以及网络威胁等问题，都要求管理模式发生转变：从被动应对（“救火式”）模式转向基于数字技术和预测分析的主动式方法。

关键词：风险，风险管理，风险评估，公司

Abstract. *Under modern conditions of economic activity, characterized by high turbulence in the external environment, geopolitical tension, and volatility in financial markets, an effective risk management system becomes a crucial factor for business survival and strategic stability. The relevance of the research topic is determined by the fact that traditional risk management methods, relying on retrospective analysis and manual oversight, are becoming ineffective in today's realities. The increase in the Bank of Russia's key rate, labor market deficit, supply chain disruptions, and cyber threats require a shift in the management paradigm: from a reactive model ('firefighting') to a proactive approach based on digital technologies and predictive analytics.*

Keywords: *risk, risk management, risk assessment, company*

Company risk management is a systematic and continuous process aimed at identifying, assessing, minimizing, and controlling risks that may affect the achievement of the organization's objectives [1]. Risk management constitutes a component of the corporate governance framework and ensures the sustainable development of business in conditions of uncertainty.

The primary objective of risk management is not the complete elimination of risks (which is often unfeasible), but rather the mitigation of their adverse effects and the enhancement of the company's capacity to adapt to changes.

Contemporary risk management is regarded as a value-creating process, as it facilitates more informed managerial decision-making and the efficient allocation of resources.

The guiding principles of risk management are thoroughly presented in international standards such as ISO 31000:2018 and COSO ERM:2017 [4]. The following are the fundamental principles underpinning an effective risk management system [1]:

1. Integration — risk management must be embedded at all levels of company governance, including strategic planning, operational activities, and corporate culture;
2. Structured and comprehensive — the process should be formalized, based on clearly defined procedures, and encompass all types of risks;
3. Adaptability and dynamism — risk management should consider the ongoing changes in both external and internal environments;
4. Transparency and involvement — all stakeholders (employees, management, partners) should be involved in the processes of risk assessment and management;
5. Based on the best available information — reliable and up-to-date data, including expert opinions and analytical forecasts, should be utilized for risk assessment;
6. Continuity — risk management is not a one-time activity; This is a continuous process that involves the regular review and updating of the risk profile.
7. The uniqueness of the approach — each organization possesses a unique structure, objectives, and operational environment, necessitating a customized approach to the risk management system.

The risk management process constitutes a logically interconnected cycle and consists of the following key stages.

1. Risk identification involves the detection of all potential threats that may impact the company's operations. Identification may be performed through the following methods [5]:

- analysis of business processes;
- expert interviews;
- analysis of incidents from previous periods;
- brainstorming and SWOT analysis;
- analysis of the external environment.

2. Risk assessment involves determining the probability of occurrence of each risk and the magnitude of potential damage. This assessment can be:

- qualitative — utilizing expert scales (low, medium, high risk);
- quantitative — calculating the expected loss in monetary terms, scenario analysis, and probabilistic models.

A commonly used tool is the probability and impact matrix (risk matrix), which assists in risk prioritization.

3. Development of a risk management strategy — based on the assessment results, risk management measures are formulated as follows:

- risk avoidance — abstention from activities associated with high risk;
- risk reduction — preventive measures, control procedures, and resource allocation;
- risk transfer — insurance, outsourcing, and contracting with partners;
- risk acceptance — deliberate assumption of risk when its level is acceptable, often accompanied by the establishment of insurance reserves.

4. Execution and Monitoring. This phase encompasses the practical implementation of risk management measures, including the standardization of activities, staff training, and the utilization of IT tools. The process is accompanied by continuous quality control of execution and performance assessment.

The risk management system is founded on methods for the evaluation and regulation of potential threats [6]. The optimal set of tools is selected based on the business scale and the enterprise's industry-specific characteristics.

A group of risk assessment methods is employed to determine the probability of threat occurrence and the magnitude of their consequences. In accordance with the classification [3], they are divided into qualitative and quantitative methods.

1. Qualitative methods

These are based on expert judgment, logical analysis, and subjective evaluations. They are predominantly utilized in the initial stages of planning or when statistical data are insufficient.

Primary tools:

– SWOT analysis: the comparison of a company's internal resources (strengths and weaknesses) with external factors (opportunities and threats) for an initial risk assessment.

– Expert evaluations: risk ranking based on conclusions from internal specialists or engaged consultants.

– Scenario analysis: modeling and analyzing the consequences of various event development scenarios (ranging from optimistic to pessimistic).

– Sensitivity analysis: assessing the impact of changes in key parameters such as market prices and exchange rates on the company's financial outcomes.

2. Quantitative methods of analysis — quantitative methods involve the application of precise numerical indicators, mathematical formulas, probabilistic models, and statistical data to assess the magnitude of risk.

Primary tools [3]:

– Statistical analysis — estimation of the probability of occurrence of a risk event based on historical data (frequency of equipment failures, loss statistics, demand dynamics);

- Simulation modeling (Monte Carlo) — computer-based modeling of thousands of possible event development scenarios to determine the probability distribution of project outcomes;
- Decision tree — a graphical method for selecting the optimal strategy under conditions of uncertainty, wherein each option is assigned a probability and a monetary outcome;
- Value at Risk (VaR) — a method for estimating the maximum potential loss of an asset portfolio over a specified period with a given confidence level.

Following risk assessment, the company selects a risk response strategy. The principal methods of risk management are categorized into four groups (Table 1).

Table 1 — Company Risk Management Methods

Method	Essence of the Method	Examples of Application
Avoidance	Complete avoidance of high-risk activities	Avoidance of engagement with unreliable suppliers
Reduction	Reduction of the likelihood and/or consequences of risk	Monitoring expiration dates, cashier training
Transfer	Transfer of risk to another party	Inventory insurance
Acceptance	Conscious acceptance of risk without active intervention	Operating under moderate risk conditions with a contingency budget

Risk management tools include:

1. The Risk Matrix is the most widely used tool that allows a visual assessment of the risk level based on two parameters: the probability of occurrence and potential damage. This tool assists in identifying the likelihood of risks and determining the necessity and urgency of response measures.

2. A Risk Map (Risk Map) is a visual representation of risks plotted on a coordinate plane, where the X-axis denotes probability, and the Y-axis denotes damage [2]. It enables the classification of risks according to their levels of significance.

3. Regulations and risk management policies — large companies develop and implement internal regulatory documents governing:

- the process of risk identification and registration;
- the allocation of responsibilities;
- response procedures;
- reporting standards.

4. Insurance as a risk management instrument is a fundamental method of risk transfer. Companies insure:

- inventories in warehouses and retail stores;
- civil liability towards customers;
- potential losses arising from supply interruptions and operational downtimes;

- real estate.
- 5. Information systems and digital solutions — the application of software solutions for risk management:
 - ERP systems (SAP, 1C) — identification and control of risks within business processes;
 - CRM/SCM systems — monitoring of supply chains and interactions with clients and suppliers;
 - BI systems — risk analytics and forecasting;
 - GRC platforms (Governance, Risk, Compliance) — a comprehensive approach to risk management, compliance, and internal control.

The research conducted on risk management allows for the following conclusions. Under contemporary conditions of high turbulence and digitalization of the economy, the concept of risk has evolved from merely a threat of resource loss to a category that characterizes the uncertainty associated with achieving objectives. International standards (ISO 31000, COSO ERM) advocate shifting from fragmented management of individual risks to integrated risk management, which is embedded within the company's strategy and business processes.

Traditional reactive management models ('firefighting'), which rely on retrospective analysis of past events, are becoming increasingly ineffective. The implementation of proactive methods aimed at preventing threats prior to their occurrence (Pre-factum) is required.

For a comprehensive diagnosis of the risk management system, a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods is necessary: qualitative methods enable the identification and prioritization of strategic and operational threats; quantitative methods allow for the quantification of risks associated with liquidity loss, financial stability, and business activity.

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北方地区劳动关系监管和社会保障的经济和法律问题
**ECONOMIC AND LEGAL ASPECTS OF REGULATING LABOR
RELATIONS AND SOCIAL PROTECTION OF THE POPULATION
IN THE NORTH**

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摘要：本研究旨在分析北方地区劳动关系和社会保障的规范。研究考察了气候因素对北方地区劳动关系的影响，概述了远北地区劳动立法的特点、劳动规范的经济层面以及劳动者的社会经济状况，并详细探讨了北方地区劳动者的社会保障问题。研究重点关注俄罗斯联邦层面和马加丹州层面的劳动关系规范。研究指出了存在的问题，并分析了北方地区劳动立法和社会保障的发展前景。

关键词：劳动关系；远北地区；社会保障；福利；法律规范

Abstract. *The aim of the study is to analyze the regulation of labor relations and social protection of the population in the North. The influence of climatic factors on labor relations in northern regions is examined. The features of labor legislation, as well as the economic aspects of labor regulation and the socio-economic status of workers under the conditions of the Far North, are outlined. The questions of social protection of workers in the northern regions are examined in detail. Special attention is paid to the regulatory aspects of labor relations both at the federal level in Russia and within the Magadan region. Problems have been identified, and prospects for the development of labor legislation and social protection of the population in the northern regions have been analyzed.*

Keywords: *labor relations; regions of the Far North; social protection; benefits; legal regulation.*

Introduction

The topic of the economic and legal aspects of regulating labor relations and social protection of the population in the North is both relevant and significant for ensuring the sustainable development of regions, preserving their labor potential, and securing social justice. Northern regions are distinguished by unique climatic conditions that affect labor relations, economic development, and the socio-economic conditions of workers.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the specific characteristics of labor legislation, the economic aspects of labor regulation, and the socio-economic conditions of workers in the Far North. To achieve the stated goal, it is necessary to address the following tasks:

- 1) to examine the influence of climatic factors on labor relations in northern regions;
- 2) to analyze the economic aspects of labor regulation in the North;
- 3) to evaluate the socio-economic conditions of workers in the Far North;
- 4) to identify the problems and prospects for the development of labor legislation and social protection of the population in the northern regions.

Materials and Methods of Research

The specific characteristics of labor in the Far North are as follows: climatic factors and their impact on labor relations; economic aspects of labor regulation in the Far North; the socio-economic status of workers under the conditions of the Far North.

The climatic conditions of the North have a significant impact on labor relations and necessitate a special approach to labor regulation. The main climatic factors influencing labor relations include [1]:

- extreme weather conditions (severe frosts, winds, snowfalls, polar night and polar day), which can lead to decreased labor productivity, increased incidence of illness, and occupational injuries;
- seasonality of work (summer and winter periods), which necessitates the adaptation of labor relations to changing conditions;
- remoteness from centers of civilization, which can result in worker isolation and deterioration in living standards.

Ensuring effective functioning in the northern regions requires consideration of climatic factors and adaptation of labor relations accordingly.

The economic aspects of regulating labor in the North encompass the following areas:

- remuneration (establishment of northern allowances, regional coefficients, as well as additional guarantees and compensations);
- working conditions (guaranteeing occupational safety and health, and creating favorable working environments);
- labor guarantees (provision of leave, and guarantees and compensations upon termination of employment).

The economic aspects of regulating labor in the North must consider the specific characteristics of the region and ensure fair and efficient labor relations.

The socio-economic conditions of workers in the Far North are characterized by the following features:

- a low standard of living (high prices for goods and services, limited access to social services);
- housing challenges (housing shortages, high rental costs);
- challenges in education and healthcare (shortage of schools and hospitals, high costs of services).

To improve the socio-economic conditions of workers under the conditions of the Far North, it is necessary to develop and implement a set of measures aimed at enhancing the standard of living, ensuring accessibility to social services, and improving housing conditions.

Thus, the economic and legal aspects of regulating labor relations and social protection of the population in the North necessitate a specialized approach that takes into account climatic factors, economic conditions, and the socio-economic status of workers. To ensure effective functioning in the northern regions, it is necessary to develop and implement a comprehensive range of measures aimed at adapting labor relations to climatic conditions, raising the standard of living of workers, and ensuring accessibility to social services. Social protection of workers in the northern regions includes: state programs for supporting workers; social guarantees and benefits for northerners; trade unions in safeguarding labor rights.

In the northern regions, state programs for supporting workers play a significant role in ensuring social protection of the population. They are aimed at improving working conditions, raising the standard of living, and ensuring social justice.

One of the primary programs is the system of state guarantees and compensations for workers employed in the regions of the Far North and equivalent territories. These guarantees include: additional paid leave; a reduced working week; reimbursement of travel expenses to and from the place of vacation; payment of regional coefficients and percentage wage supplements to salaries.

Moreover, various social programs operate in the northern regions, aimed at supporting families with minors, persons with disabilities, pensioners, and other categories of the population. These programs encompass the provision of benefits for housing and utility payments, subsidies for housing acquisition, free meals in schools and kindergartens, free medical care, and other social support measures.

Social guarantees and benefits for residents of the North represent a crucial element of the social protection system in these northern regions. They include: compulsory social insurance against industrial accidents and occupational diseases; compulsory medical insurance; pension support; social services [3].

Additionally, various employment support programs are implemented in the northern regions, aimed at creating new jobs, enhancing qualifications and retraining personnel, as well as supporting small and medium-sized enterprises.

Trade unions play a significant role in safeguarding the labor rights of employees in the northern regions. They represent the interests of employees before employers and authorities, oversee compliance with labor legislation, organize collective bargaining, conclude collective agreements, and conduct mass protest campaigns in the event of violations of workers' rights.

However, despite all efforts by the state and trade unions, issues in the domain of social protection of residents in the northern regions remain unresolved. These issues are associated with several factors, including:

- the remoteness of the northern regions from the central parts of the country;
- harsh climatic conditions;
- high cost of living;
- insufficiently developed infrastructure.

To address these challenges, it is necessary to develop and implement a comprehensive set of measures aimed at improving the population's standard of living, enhancing working conditions, developing social infrastructure, supporting small and medium-sized enterprises, and enhancing qualifications and retraining of workers.

Thus, state support programs for workers, social guarantees and benefits, as well as the activities of trade unions in safeguarding labor rights, constitute important mechanisms of social protection for the population in northern regions. However, to enhance the effectiveness of these mechanisms, it is necessary to take into account the specific characteristics of northern regions and to develop measures adapted to their conditions [4].

Consider the aspects of regulating labor relations. Under the conditions of the North, where climatic and geographical conditions impose additional challenges on workers and employers, particular attention is given to the regulation of labor relations and the social protection of the population.

The current labor legislation of Russia comprises a set of regulatory acts governing labor relations and social protection of the population. Among these, the following are distinguished:

- The Labor Code of the Russian Federation (LC RF);
- Federal laws and subordinate normative acts that specify and supplement the LC RF;
- Collective agreements and contracts that establish additional guarantees and compensations for employees.

In the Northern context, special attention is given to guarantees and compensations associated with climatic conditions, including increased remuneration, additional leave, reduced working hours, and other benefits.

Labor contracts in the North possess specific features associated with climatic and geographical conditions. Among these, the following are distinguished:

- the establishment of additional guarantees and compensations for employees associated with climatic conditions;
- the consideration of the specific features of working hours and rest periods related to short daylight duration and the polar night;
- the establishment of special requirements for working conditions associated with cold, wind, and other natural factors.

Judicial practice concerning labor disputes in northern regions demonstrates that courts pay particular attention to the protection of employees' rights associated with climatic conditions. Among the most frequent categories of labor disputes are disputes concerning wage levels and other payments; disputes regarding the provision of guarantees and compensations; disputes concerning compliance with labor conditions.

Thus, the regulation of labor relations and social protection of the population in the North require particular attention to economic and legal aspects. The current labor legislation establishes guarantees and compensations related to climatic conditions, and judicial practice demonstrates that courts pay special attention to safeguarding workers' rights. However, despite this, certain challenges remain concerning the enforcement of labor rights of employees in the northern regions. For instance, some employers may not provide the legally established guarantees and compensations or may fail to observe the stipulated working conditions.

In particular, in the Magadan Oblast, the following measures may be in effect [5]:

- remuneration incorporating a district coefficient (this benefit is primarily regulated by Law No. 4520-1, other federal normative legal acts, and the letter from the Department for Pension Provision Issues of the Ministry of Labor of the Russian Federation dated 09.06.2003 No. 1199-16);
- remuneration with northern allowances (regulated by law No. 4520-1, Ministry of Labor order No. 2, and other federal regulatory legal acts) [3];
- additional paid leave (regulated by law No. 4520-1, Labor Code of the Russian Federation) [6];
- reimbursement of travel expenses to the vacation destination (regulated by law No. 4520-1, Labor Code of the Russian Federation) [6];
- benefits related to medical care (regulated by law No. 4520-1, Labor Code of the Russian Federation);
- benefits for employees with children (regulated by the Labor Code of the Russian Federation);
- shortened workweek (regulated by the Labor Code of the Russian Federation);
- guarantees and compensations in cases of enterprise liquidation and workforce reductions (regulated by the Labor Code of the Russian Federation);

- housing subsidies (regulated by the Law ‘On Housing Subsidies’ dated October 25, 2002 No. 125-FZ, as well as other federal regulatory legal acts);
- retirement benefits (regulated by the Law ‘On Insurance Pensions’ dated December 28, 2013 No. 400-FZ, and the Law ‘On Labor Pensions’ dated December 17, 2001 No. 173-FZ).

In the Magadan Region, various regional social support measures are implemented. Some of these include:

1) a supplementary child allowance: granted to families with children to support their financial well-being. The amount of the allowance depends on the number of children in the family and the family’s income;

2) a preferential benefit for orphans and children deprived of parental care: provided to children who have lost their parents and constitutes additional social support in a specified amount;

3) Benefits for housing and utility payments: subsidies or compensations for housing and communal services (electricity, gas, water, heating, etc.) are provided to citizens with low incomes;

4) Transportation benefits: various categories of citizens, including pensioners and persons with disabilities, may be entitled to concessions on public transportation. A free travel card may be issued, or a discount on the fare may be applied;

5) benefits related to access to medical care: citizens may be provided with preferential medical care, including free or discounted services and medication subsidies;

6) benefits related to disability support: persons with disabilities are granted various benefits and social support, including allowances, provision of medical services, and assistive rehabilitation devices.

Conclusion

The economic and legal aspects of regulating labor relations and social protection of the population in northern regions require particular attention. It is essential to consider climatic factors, economic conditions, and the socio-economic status of workers when developing and implementing a comprehensive set of measures. State support programs, social guarantees, benefits, and trade union activities play a critical role in safeguarding labor rights. However, enhancing their effectiveness requires adaptation to the specific conditions of northern regions. Current labor legislation stipulates compensations and guarantees associated with climatic conditions; however, issues persist regarding employers’ compliance with these provisions. This necessitates the enhancement of legislation and legal enforcement practices to ensure the protection of workers’ rights and to establish favorable conditions for their work and living.

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